

A Continually Receding Horizon

**Making, performing, and improvising with
semi-autonomous double bass feedback instruments**

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this dissertation are original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This dissertation is my own work and contains nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

Chapter 1 contains text previously published in Melbye (2022).

Section 2.8.1 contains text previously published in Melbye (2021a).

The FAAB described in chapter 4 was made in collaboration with Halldór Úlfarsson. The physical design characteristics of the instrument are courtesy of Úlfarsson.

Echoes of Unspecified Origins was composed and performed in collaboration with Julia Reidy.

Towering Silence was composed and performed in collaboration with Ingrid Schmoliner.

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¹ The translation is mine, the original read: 'das klingt, als würden drei Riesen in den Hals von riesigen Glasflaschen pusten und probieren, tiefe Töne zu erzeugen'.

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Abstract

This thesis explores double bass feedback systems, with a focus on the FAAB (feedback-actuated augmented bass)—a self-resonating vibrotactile feedback string bass instrument equipped with onboard DSP. Developing against a background of an extensive acoustic instrumental practice in improvised and experimental music, the thesis examines how salient properties of timbral complexity and performative resistance may be applied in an extended electro-acoustic domain. An analysis and discussion of interaction and human-machine improvisation informed by neocybernetic and enactivist theories of autonomy and interactional asymmetry leads to the development of a conceptual framework for the creation of adaptive signal processing architectures. This framework is applied to the design of a set of algorithms, the behaviours of which are described in the context of performance, improvised as well as composed. The discussion is guided by the conviction that what is often conceived of as digital/material binaries is better understood in a shared performative domain. In the discussion of performance, attention is paid to how the FAAB affords the reconsideration of old—as well as the development of new—instrumental techniques and modes of performance, through the unpredictable, yet largely deterministic behaviour of the instrument. The final chapter of the thesis discusses resistance, mastery, and virtuosity, again in the context of a performance practice with the FAAB. With the instrument eluding traditional notions of performative control, materialist, queer, and decolonial theories are employed in a discussion of precariousness and failure as artistic opportunities particularly suited to feedback musicianship and human-machine improvisation.

The practice-based contribution of the thesis consists of a set of solo and duo performances using three different feedback bass configurations. The majority of these highlight the role of the FAAB in developing a largely improvised solo performance practice in which the feedback-induced and algorithmically extended behaviour of the instrument affords timbral, amplitudal, and interactional complexity. The two collaborative works situate the FAAB within a performance ecology comprised of other performers, compositional scaffolding, and a set of laptop-based multichannel signal processing algorithms developed in extension of the embedded DSP of the FAAB. The accompanying DSP library consists of familiar low-level

algorithms. Yet, their creative integration with a feedback instrument and the implementation of an adaptive and largely autonomous high-level digital infrastructure contributes to the field of feedback signal processing, and can be of value to practitioners beyond the specific field of feedback.

The identification of instrumental resistance as being intimately tied to the establishment of interactional asymmetry and instrumental autonomy affects the cultivation of a performance practice as well as an aesthetic, both of which are grounded in an appreciation of unmastery and failure. This does not entail the absence of skill or tools for evaluation, but rather paves the way for the development of aesthetics as well as skillsets that accommodate the dynamic and precarious ecologies emerging through nonlinear human-machine relationships.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

In February 1998, I was a 17-year-old electric bass player, playing in rock bands but getting into jazz and occupied with the idea of playing the double bass. Acting on a tip that an instrument was for sale at a music school two hours from my home, my father and I drove to inspect it. At the time, I had little idea of what to look for in a double bass, so when presented with the instrument, I could only ascertain that it had no cracks and was made of solid wood. Upon our return home with the bass that afternoon, I embarked on a journey of technical and sonic engagements and investigations that now, 24 years later, is still occupying my time in due measures of excitement and frustration.

During my initial endeavours at learning the instrument, it became apparent to me, that, despite the decent quality of the bass, the many years of standing/lying/falling over in a music school had taken its toll on the instrument's setup, most significantly the bridge, which was horribly warped and unreasonably high, lifting the strings far off the fingerboard. I pity the students who must have struggled to get any acceptable sound from this unwieldy beast, their first encounter with a double bass being defined by a demand for a magnificent physical engagement simply to press down and pluck the stiff steel strings. While suspecting that a better setup and a new bridge might have eased my hardships, living in a forest in the countryside, I knew no other double bass players and, as such, had no physical or social reference against which to measure my struggle.

In the early days of jazz double bass playing, amplification was largely unavailable and as such, bass players relied on the empathy of fellow musicians as well as specific instrument setups in order to be heard. The action of the strings, that is, their distance to the fingerboard, was often significant, requiring strong hands, while at the same time being mediated by the relative flexibility of the then ubiquitous gut strings. The resulting sound was percussive, creating an intersection between harmony and rhythm which was useful for driving a band, but also posed certain obstacles to the fluid execution of melodic lines. Two technological

advances changed the situation: while having been introduced decades earlier, the availability of commercial piezoelectric transducers and amplification in the 1960s allowed bass players to lower their action and still be heard. At the same time, many bass players changed to steel strings which afforded increased sustain and pitch clarity, heralding an explosion in fast-paced and smooth virtuosity. Due to my limited exposure to other double bass players at the time, I was largely unaware that the setup of the bass I had just purchased remixed the material history of jazz by combining modern stiff steel strings with what was then considered an archaic action much too high for contemporary bass playing. Rather than changing the setup, and due to equal parts of ignorance and stubbornness, I devoted my time to overcoming the physical resistance of the instrument and at the same time became skilled in blister management. By the time I entered the academy of music a few years later and was advised by my teacher to lower my action, the damage was already done: I had assimilated the resistance—and sound—of the instrument into my musical practice. Despite several attempts at reverting to a sensible setup, whenever the instrument became easier to play, and I was able to assume the role of a virtuosic bass player as expected by some teachers and fellow musicians, I experienced a lack of physical engagement with the instrument and the music, not to say a discomfort in the lowering of acoustic output, requiring me to play with an amplifier. With an increased ease of playing, the sound of the instrument changed dramatically: the acoustically loud, rich and spectrally complex thud of a tense string transferring its energy to the body of the double bass gave way to a sustained and almost sinusoidal sound displaced from its origin through the intermediary of an amplifier and speaker. In frustration, I then raised my strings, and the cycle started all over again. It took me a decade to accept that my struggles originated in a disjunct between the affordances of my setup and what was expected in mainstream and modern jazz, rather than a failure on my part to practice enough. By adapting my practice to the material constitution of the instrument, its peculiarities, becoming habitually embodied in my sensorimotor skill sets and responses, ultimately shaped the domain in which music took place. In manifesting as potential as well as limiting condition for sound-making, matter came to co-constitute what Simon Waters (2007, 2021) and John Bowers (2002) have termed the performance ecosystem and performance ecology, respectively. These related but not identical terms describe the socially, historically, materially and technologically distributed situation of music-making, and will be discussed further in 2.6.1. Applying such systems perspectives, the question becomes how, and if, to resolve the conflict between the material affordances of the instruments and the norms imposed by style and convention.

After going through numerous bridges and string types, in 2013 I landed back where I began, with the stiffest steel strings on the market—Thomastik Spirocore Heavy gauge

(n.d.)—extended over a bridge that my luthier informed me was as high as they come. At this point, I had largely transitioned from a career as a jazz bass player to one of performing on the European circuit for improvised music and free jazz. While these practices embody their own traditions and occasionally embrace strong opinions on, and expectations of, the role of players and instruments, I found that the sound of my playing, and the high energy input needed to drive it, here found a place for exploration. Partially liberated from the role of metronomic timekeeper and harmonic anchor, I was at greater liberty to explore the timbre of the instrument. High-tension steel strings forcefully plucked and bowed, a precondition of which is a medium-to-high action, yield very specific characteristics: the upper partials of the string stand out in great clarity and, with the bow in particular, invites shaping of timbre, for example through the actuation of multiphonics (Thelin 2011b), in addition to other extended techniques such as spiccato (using the bounce of the string to generate rapid bowing patterns) and subharmonics (the production of partials below the bowed fundamental) (Dresser 2010; Kimura 1999).

As my focus on arco and solo playing increased, I additionally developed an affinity for difference tones and beat frequencies (Roederer 2012, p. 34). At first explored intuitively and later, with increased rigour, these phenomena are still a central part of my musical practice in both the acoustic and electro-acoustic domains. In addition to extended technical and timbral explorations, the resistance of the instrument, relating to its physically demanding setup, rather than being a source of frustration and inhibition to technical fluency, in the improvised situation took on a different character. While lending a certain performative drama to concerts, the pushback from the bass also accommodated the exploration of sometimes less intuitive avenues and tactics. Having to deal with the unforeseen results of strings skipping underneath my fingers—or simply breaking during performance—begged me to embrace the precarious situation I had set up for myself. In addition to improvising with other musicians, the intentions of whom are often underspecified, in my solo performances I was improvising with an instrument, the responses of which did not always correlate to my intentions.

1.1 Research questions

At the same time as my coming-to-terms with the resistive and timbral peculiarities of the double bass, in 2013 I began exploring digital audio synthesis and signal processing. These endeavours were, and to some extent still are, practised outside the immediate domain of double bass performance. Yet, they triggered a sequence of considerations and questions, three of which frame and contextualise this thesis. The first question asks: *How, and to what*

extent, can a technically and timbrally extended instrumental practice be expanded beyond the acoustic domain and into an electro-acoustic space?

This thesis explores the creation of a body of work that situates the double bass within an electro-acoustic ecology. It does so from a specific personal perspective; that of a lengthy acoustic composition and performance practice combined with a curiosity for extending and altering this practice through amplification and signal processing. In addition to the already mentioned exploration of electro-acoustically augmented timbre and technique, the second research question asks *how the resistant and precarious performer-instrument relationships that I consider a central part of my acoustic practice may express themselves in this new context?* Unsurprisingly, these ambitions have unleashed a host of other questions, some of which I attempt to address in this study.

It was during work on this PhD thesis that feedback emerged as an important part of my artistic practice. However, once established, it proliferated into most of my creative endeavours, in addition to informing my thinking about music, as well as subjects beyond the scope of this study. Feedback, whether manifesting as air pressure waves, mechanical vibrations, or through digital control signal loops, permeates this study and provides a guiding thread, as well as a method, with which to address timbral and interactional complexity in an electro-acoustic domain. Deriving from a discussion of feedback undertaken in chapter 2, the third research question asks: *How may feedback be used to generate asymmetrical relationships affording interaction and improvisation?*

1.2 Portfolio, theory, and practice-led contributions

The artistic output of the thesis comprises a selection of videos and audio files documenting performances and recordings produced between 2019 and 2021. The written submission describes, discusses, and analyses the instruments featured in these settings, as well as the performances themselves. As will become clearer throughout the thesis, the term instrument is here understood to mean a dynamical assemblage of resonant materials, electronics, and digital code, moulded through a social and historical context. As such, I consider the instrument designs and signal processing algorithms discussed here to constitute their own artistic practices, intimately engaging with composition and performance on a creative level. The thesis oscillates between technical descriptions, reflections of performance, and philosophical discussion, which reflects my understanding of the heterogeneity of its subject. Having little to no formal training in mathematics or programming, I have acquired basic

skills in these disciplines in response to the demands of the creative process¹. I do not perceive computer code or equations as distinctly different from the artistic work itself. Rather, I perceive them to be material, social, and political agents entangled with the processes in which they come to matter.

1.3 Methodology

The current study revolves around a practice in which the making of—and performance with—an instrument is conducted by the same individual (the one notable exception being the collaboration with Halldór Úlfarsson described in chapter 4). For a research methodology, this poses a unique set of challenges, especially with regard to evaluating instruments and performances. Since this thesis emerges from, and is entangled with an established artistic practice, autoethnography, rather than, for example, user studies, is central to the research. Evaluation constitutes the investigation of how constructing, programming, performing, practicing, and theoretical development, through their location within the same subject, individually and in concert address each other as well as the research questions. More specifically, as a long-time performer, it is in the process of *performing* (public, as well as in my studio) with the instruments and algorithms produced throughout this thesis that I come closest to some sense of qualitative evaluation of all the other processes. It would be tempting to suppose that a problematic performance with an otherwise conceptually impeccable instrument or algorithm suggests that the physical design or code base need rethinking in order to provide a better vehicle for transducing musical intent and expression. However, similar to my experience described above of creatively embodying a physically challenging instrument setup, the methodology applied in this study gives priority to the emergence and co-constitution of music, over the essentialist idea that something musically pre-given is lying around waiting to be expressed (see also Melbye (2022)). In many instances during the study, I have found that difficulties in making musical sense of the new tools being developed, rather than a failure on the part of the tool, were often due to my unfamiliarity with its potentials, the salient properties of which would only become apparent through long-term association.

As a visual aid to the methodology described above, figure 1.1 below illustrates some of the processes and relations playing out in the research. As most diagrams describing dynamic processes, this reductive illustration does not do justice to the complexity and continuous

¹ Early in the research I made use of the math courses (especially on the subject of trigonometry) offered for free by Khan Academy (n.d.). For learning C++, I relied on Andrew McPherson's (2020a) excellent YouTube tutorials, also offered free of charge.

reconfiguration of relationships. Yet, it is still useful for identifying some of the central processes in my investigation and how they may relate to each other at any given point in the research.

Figure 1.1 Research methodology

It becomes apparent, then, that the methodology embodies its own set of feedback processes, enabled through the coupling between making, playing, and thinking. While circularity is an inherent property of feedback, it is still worth trying to identify an initial trigger for the the processes described in this thesis: in beginning a new work, algorithm, or instrument I have been driven by the ambition that it would eventually be performable in front of an audience. That is, the impetus is creative and oriented toward an artistic output. This probably derives from my career as a musician: I enjoy making things, but the itch to play them takes precedence. As such, initial instrument design and future modifications have proceeded in continuous dialogue with practice and performance. In a feedback instrument, any adjustment, be it the installment of a new speaker, or the modification of the distance between electromagnetic pickups and strings, may have global and fundamental consequences for how the instrument sounds and behaves. Changing the physical constitution of the instrument changes its performability, triggers the development and exploration of new techniques, skill sets and performance tactics, which, in turn, affords the additional physical modifications. Consequently, the relationship between playing the instrument and its physical modification, rather than simply consisting in optimizing the instrument for performance, becomes a curatorial practice of opening up or closing down new possibilities—what I will

later in the study refer to as *horizons*. This circular relationship is echoed in the software space as well: the acoustic feedback loop of the instrument magnifies the consequences of signal processing, creating nonlinear global impacts from local digital modifications. Throughout the research very basic, and, at times patchily written, early stages of algorithms supplied the basic operations for an assessment through performance, which in turn provided the experience and understanding for rewriting the code. Naturally, this changes the nature of performance, closing the feedback loop between plans and actions, and renders evaluation a dynamic process in which the standard against which anything is evaluated itself becomes a product of the process.

1.4 Chapter overview

Chapter 2 situates the research undertaken in an artistic as well as theoretical context. Here, I discuss how the nonlinear and complex behaviours that I cherish in acoustic instrument performance have been explored in the creation of digital and analogue performance systems. Through this discussion, feedback, implemented in the audio domain as well as applying to control processes, emerges as a candidate for creating timbral and behavioural complexity in the electro-acoustic domain. In this chapter, I additionally undertake a discussion of interaction and improvisation. With improvisation being central to my musical practice, the investigation of how human-machine improvisation can be established through the concept of *interactional asymmetry* is essential. Furthermore, I discuss the possibility of post-human improvisation, in which the machine establishes sense-making capabilities indigenous to its own construction of a world.

In chapter 3 I describe two feedback double bass systems operating in the audio and control domains, respectively. The discussion undertaken in the previous chapter regarding feedback and the use of audio feature descriptors to create complex situated and immanent behaviour, is here put to practical and creative use in the performances *What the Frog's Eye tells the Frog's Brain* and *attics for all, floors for none*. The intersection of theory and practice additionally allows me to further analyse and discuss the differences and commonalities between various domains of feedback.

One of the contributions of this thesis lies in the description and discussion of personal attitudes and idiosyncratic methods pertaining to performance, making, and technology, within a practice of feedback musicianship. Rather than offering a general blueprint that can linearly be applied to other artistic or technological practices, it is perhaps in the methods and processes explored, rather than their outcome, that artists and researchers may find the most inspiration and knowledge. The thesis does offer two distinct practical

and one philosophical contributions: firstly, the description of the development of the FAAB (feedback-actuated augmented bass) in chapter 4 describes experiences and practical considerations emerging from the development of, and performance with, a novel feedback string instrument. Feedback musicianship has been around for a long time, but has recently seen much academic interest and research (Eldridge et al. 2021; Impett et al. 2022; Kiefer and Overholt n.d; Magnusson et al. 2022). This thesis in particular contributes to the research field emerging around *self-resonating vibrotactile feedback instruments* (Eldridge et al. 2021). Secondly, directly related to the physical design of this instrument, and building on concepts developed in chapter 3, in chapter 4 I describe the creation of three specific signal processing algorithms that afford resistance, interaction and improvisation through the establishment of feedback-induced instrumental semi-autonomy. As in chapter 3 the digital designs are described in the context of performances, in this case *We're running out of Sand*, *Answer use replace, insert, append*, and *Di s Co nT*, while the works *Echoes of unspecified Origins* and *Towering Silence* describe the use of the FAAB in collaborative contexts. Both the signal processing architectures and my understanding of interaction and improvisation, in addition to being guided by 20 years of performing and improvising, are informed by a neocybernetic and enactivist reading of embodied cognition and sense-making. Yet, this study does not attempt to equip an improvising machine with human perceptual and cognitive features. Rather, the argument of the study—which is put to practical use in chapter 4—is that there is nothing preventing us from designing improvising machines that behave in other-than-human ways. This, then, brings me to the discussion undertaken in chapter 5. Here, I attempt to put my money where my mouth is and discuss the consequences of establishing an augmented asymmetry between a semi-autonomous feedback instrument and a performer whose agency and control have become compromised. This last contribution is informed by posthumanist, feminist, decolonial, and queer readings of failure, resistance, mastery, and virtuosity. Proposing a critical reconsideration of these terms, this chapter additionally addresses the underlying ethical and practical implications of what happens *when things slip*.

1.5 Overview of portfolio and additional output

1.5.1 Portfolio

Where mentioned in the text, individual works from the thesis portfolio are accessible as hyperlinks leading to Vimeo or Soundcloud. Time codes in blue are clickable, leading directly to the time index of the example. Additionally, links to work directly relating to the thesis, but not included in the portfolio, are accessible throughout the text.

Below follows an overview of the portfolio, in order of appearance in the text. A list of works and performances produced during, and in relation to, the thesis, can be found in [Appendix A](#).

- **What the Frog's Eye tells the Frog's Brain (2019)**
<https://vimeo.com/327281165>
- **attics for all, floors for none (2020)**
<https://vimeo.com/430341503>
- **We're running out of Sand (2020)**
<https://vimeo.com/447257162>
- **Live concert in NRW Forum, Düsseldorf (2021)**
<https://vimeo.com/727162855/0beaedbe28>
- **Waveset Demos (2021)**
<https://vimeo.com/showcase/9912377>
- **Answer use replace, insert, append (2021)**
<https://vimeo.com/747567186/6e82778283>
- **Di s Co nT (2021)**
<https://vimeo.com/666244503>
- **Echoes of Unspecified Origins (2021)**
<https://on.soundcloud.com/au8Xi>
- **Towering Silence (2021)**
<https://vimeo.com/699466741>
- **When things Slip — Glitch Parade (2020)**
<https://vimeo.com/747395676/5fce29d8ea>

1.6 Online backup and resources

In the service of archival redundancy, the portfolio is accessible through Zenodo from the following address: <https://zenodo.org/record/7897404#.ZFzvBHZBzRI>, while the pultzLib library can be accessed here: <https://zenodo.org/record/7924995#.ZF91KHZBxmQ>. Zenodo does not allow for linking to a file within that file itself, which renders it impossible to

provide a link to the text you are currently reading. Yet, a search for the thesis title on Zenodo will return the digital version. Although far less stable and future-proof than Zenodo, I will continue to update my personal website www.adampultz.com with material, some of which will relate to the work described in this thesis.

Chapter 2

Context

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the artistic and theoretical background against which my research has developed. The fields touched upon here—electro-acoustic music, human-computer interaction, cybernetics, feedback musicianship, and experimental lutherie, to name a few—are far too expansive to fully survey in any single study, which is also not my ambition. Rather, I discuss them in the context of my personal practice, with a particular focus on how they provide a scaffolding for developing and answering the research questions presented in the preceding chapter and reiterated here:

- How, and to what extent, can a technically and timbrally extended instrumental practice be expanded beyond the acoustic domain and into an electro-acoustic space?
- How may resistant and precarious performer-instrument relationships express themselves in this new context?
- How may feedback be used to generate asymmetrical relationships affording interaction and improvisation?

2.2 Extended double bass techniques

My acoustic instrumental practice is situated in a tradition of extended double bass techniques, the development of which radically picked up speed with the introduction of steel strings in 1961 (Waters 2021, p. 6). The spectral and timbral precision that these strings offered enabled double bass players such as Bertram Turetzky (1974) and Barre Phillips (1968) to develop a language that utilised the newly expanded frequency range and more rapid response of the

instrument. Mark Dresser (2010) and Håkon Thelin (2011a), to name a few double bassists, have since explored, developed, and formalised many extended techniques, contributing to the establishment of a tradition in continuous development, a more recent example being the work of bassist, vocalist, and composer Jordan Sand (n.d). These rich and sophisticated timbral practices emerge from the relationship between expert musicianship and a large instrument with a wide frequency range, a complex spectrum, and an often significantly nonlinear behaviour. For example, in Guettler and Thelin's (2012) research into double bass multiphonics the authors observe the nonlinear stick-slip relationship between bow and string and the resulting phase-locking of multiple pitches, causing the emergence of a complex texture of several identifiably sounding tones.

2.2.1 Nonlinearity and complexity

Since the terms nonlinearity and complexity will appear throughout this text, I will briefly define how they are understood in the context of the current study:

Nonlinearity

A *nonlinear* system is one in which the relationship between the input and the output is not one of superposition (Auyang 1998, p. 178). Superposition satisfies the principles of additivity

$$F(x_1 + x_2) = F(x_1) + F(x_2)$$

and homogeneity

$$F(ax) = aF(x)$$

Simply put, the output of a nonlinear system does not correspond linearly to changes in input.

For real-world examples of linearity and nonlinearity in instrument performance, Auyang (ibid., p. 178) describes how a violin string's linear vibration is comprised of the superposition of its individual modes. To this, we can contrast the example from Guettler and Thelin described above, in which the application of a bow to the string introduces nonlinear behaviour once bow pressure and bow speed cross certain lower or higher thresholds.

Complexity

The use of the term *complexity* is ubiquitous in both colloquial and scientific language. In this study, I mainly use complexity in three contexts: the timbre of a sound, the behaviour of an instrument (be it acoustic or electro-acoustic), and musical interaction.

I consider a sound complex when it has audible partials, for example the multiphonics discussed above. While the spectrum of a string multiphonic is largely harmonic (consisting of integer partials in addition to the fundamental), other complex spectra may be inharmonic, as in the case of the sound produced by a cymbal¹. This definition is related to standard terminology, in which a complex waveform is understood to be a combination of sinusoidal waveforms of different frequencies and amplitudes. In this study, terms such as complex timbre or complex spectra is often used to heuristically describe the perception of a sound that exhibits non-periodicity, ambiguous fundamental pitch, or has some degree of noise.

Complex behaviour in instrument performance, for example generated through the use of extended techniques, will often yield complex timbres. Yet, where the perception of timbre operates on short time-scales (McAdams 2019, p. 25), in the current study, complexity in how an instrument behaves is understood to operate on longer time-scales—roughly from about a few seconds upward to several minutes. For example, as will be discussed later, feedback, under certain conditions, will cause an instrument to exhibit long-term behaviour that does not linearly correspond to changes in excitation (meaning that short-term superposition will no longer apply).

Consequently, feedback will be shown to be an important driver of complexity in interaction and improvisation, through the former's importance for the adaptive and self-organizing processes discussed in section 2.8. Complexity is here understood as an emergent property of the often nonlinear interaction between the several components of a system (human and non-human).

I understand the term complexity in a relational context. That is, it is not an abstract mathematical concept, but a real-world entity, the experience and understanding of which is situated in a web of relations (see also Gell-Mann (2002, p. 1)). Returning to how timbral complexity may manifest through extended technique: depending on the granularity which one applies to the subject, complexity emerges in the interaction between tendons, muscles, bow hair, strings, wood, and so forth. A certain gesture or movement, such as spiccato, constitutes a transduction of energy through bow, string, and instrument body. The resulting sound is an often complex timbre compounded of a continuous pitch, or pitches, and a steady and rapid pulse of the bow striking the string.

¹ Admittedly, only an ideal two-dimensional string would vibrate completely harmonically. Due to its three-dimensionality, a real-world string exhibits some inharmonicity. That is, some of its partials will be non-integer ratios.

2.2.2 Mapping

In extending an acoustic instrumental practice into an electro-acoustic domain, it can be useful to approach the performance of technique as a mapping of gesture to sound, even when such an approach constitutes a reduction of the actual reality of the operation to a mere two parameters. The transduction of energy between hand, bow, string, and instrument body can be likened to the mapping taking place between, on the one hand, a MIDI or OSC controller, and on the other, a sound event, like the mapping of hand gestures to sound synthesis in Michel Waisvisz's (1985) *Hands* interface. The difference, of course, is that a musician working with a digital mapping interface can decide the nature of the mapping through the application of complex transfer functions, discussed by, amongst others, Bowers (2002, p. 61). In contrast, the acoustic instrumentalist is largely confined to physical laws, such as those governing friction and acoustic interference, not to mention physiological limits on the part of the player.

If we further compare the mappings of many commercial interfaces with those found in relationships between performer, gesture, and acoustic instruments, another difference emerges: when moving the slider of a MIDI interface, the value of which has been assigned to a volume parameter in a DAW (Digital Audio Workstation) or other digital software, the relationship between slider state and amplitude is often linear or, at best, mapped according to a decibel distribution (see also Bowers (*ibid.*, p. 62)). In the case of acoustic instruments, gesture-to-sound mappings are rarely that simple. Whether a given technique is considered extended or not, the way it maps to an acoustic output is often non-literal and nonlinear. Bowing a double bass string, although involving the back-and-forth motion of the bowing arm, does not map to an increase and decrease of amplitude in the sound produced. Rather, it assures a sustained tone and continuous quality of timbre, with bow pressure² and bow speed in combination with left-hand pressure³ being determining factors in the resulting amplitude. Apart from bowing speed, here it is in movement invisible to the audience, such as minuscule changes of muscle-tension in the bowing hand and the finger touching the string, that causes perceptible changes in sound quality. String multiphonics are a product of such subtle motor behaviour, as is the technique of producing subharmonics, explored on the double bass by Mark Dresser (2010) and extensively researched and documented on the violin by Mari Kimura (1999)⁴. The complexity of these phenomena is by no means visually

² Or, in the case of pizzicato-playing, the force of the plucking finger.

³ Assuming that one is bowing with the right hand and pressing the string with the left.

⁴ Bowed-string subharmonics are not identical to the notion of subharmonics found in Just Intonation practices. In the latter, the subharmonic—being an inversion of the harmonic—is not a physical property of sound, but a theoretical abstraction (Partch 1974). Subharmonics on string and reed instruments involve the manipulation

represented in the gestures producing them; rather, large or sudden movements may in fact cause a *reduction* in complexity.

To sum up: in many acoustic instrument practices, we witness a high degree of complexity and nonlinearity, often driven by sophisticated motor behaviour on the part of the player. In the following section, I will discuss how complexity can emerge in electro-acoustic and digital musical practices.

2.3 Nonlinear, complex, and dynamical systems

2.3.1 Tom Mudd

The complex, yet ultimately deterministic mapping of gesture-to-sound relationships in acoustic instrument performance may serve as a guide, though not a rule, for the implementation of complex mappings in other domains, for example as explored by Tom Mudd (2017). Mudd's research is based on the digital implementation of complex and nonlinear dynamical systems, such as chaotic oscillators, for the generation of interesting and 'surprising' (p. 11) sonic behaviour. As described by Mudd (*ibid.*, p. 3), such behaviour can resemble the often complex mechanisms of acoustic instruments. By applying nonlinear transfer functions to input data generated from a physical gesture, the motion-to-sound relationship becomes nonlinear and difficult to predict in detail, providing an opportunity for continued musical exploration of the digital instrument. Of special interest to this thesis is Mudd's discussion of the 'essential nonlinearity' (*ibid.*, p. 37) of bowed instruments, comprising a feedback-coupling between a linear element, such as a string, and a nonlinear one, for example a bow.

2.3.2 Hysteresis, phase space, and attractors

The phenomenon of hysteresis is important in this context. Hysteresis describes a property of nonlinear dynamical systems in which the system state depends on current as well as past states: when the system has entered a particular state, for example as a function of its input amplitude crossing a threshold, amplitude falling below this threshold will not immediately cause the system to revert to the previous state. Instead, the system will stay locked in the new state, only changing when input amplitude falls below a second, lower threshold (*ibid.*, p. 40). From the perspective of an acoustic practice, hysteresis describes the way in which a minuscule increase in bow pressure may cause a multiphonic to exhibit strong energy around

of string vibration through bow and finger pressure in the case of the former, and the manipulation of the air stream in the case of the latter.

certain partials that remain sounding even when relaxing the bow pressure again. The track *Boolean* from my solo double bass album *Measures* (Melbye 2017a) provides an example of such behaviour. From 17:17, in addition to beat frequencies and difference tones, bowed string multiphonics exhibit unstable and nonlinear tendencies, oscillating between partials in ways not linearly corresponding to changes in bow pressure or speed. While it seems unlikely that double bass luthiers consciously design for such behaviour, to players such as myself, this nonlinearity is one of the many wonderful things about playing an acoustic instrument. In digital systems, hysteresis is rarely a given and often needs special consideration, such as discussed in the work of Tom Mudd, John Bowers (2002), and many others.

Hysteresis is well-documented and researched phenomenon in the fields of systems sciences, complexity, and chaos theory. Here, the term *phase space* is often used to describe the set of possible solutions to the equations governing a system. Within this phase space, we find attractors, comprising states to which the system may gravitate (see (Mudd 2017, p. 22) for a selection of references). Resonant frequencies, for example dominant partials in multiphonics, or the familiar feedback howl of a microphone directed toward an speaker, are examples of such attractors in the musical domain. With musical instruments being complex dynamical systems exhibiting hysteresis, we may find it useful to visualise their behaviours as a phase portrait. Figure 2.1 is taken from Eldridge et al. (2021), visualising 'each of the four main strings on a feedback cello in action' (ibid.) (the feedback cello will be discussed in section 2.5.1).

Figure 2.1 Phase portrait of each of the four strings of a feedback cello (Eldridge et al. 2021)

The complexity of acoustic instruments as well as those designed by, amongst others, Mudd, stand in contrast to some initiatives within sonic HCI (human-computer interaction) design that aims to reduce instrumental complexity in order to make instruments more playable and easier to learn. As discussed by Morreale et al. (2020) there is little to indicate that an overly simplified instrument should yield any benefits to the long-term development of the player, suggesting that nonlinear or dynamically evolving mappings may yield greater

room for exploration of the digital domain (p. 162). For the performer, an instrument offering a certain sense of complexity may in fact accommodate open-ended exploration and the discovery of new timbres.

What we may draw from these observations is, that if we wish to retain some salient characteristics of acoustic instruments in the digital domain, we need to look at the complex and sometimes unpredictable behaviours of these instruments.

2.3.3 Agostini Di Scipio's Audible Eco-Systemic Interface Project

An alternative approach to the creation of complex musical behaviours comes from Agostino Di Scipio, whose focus on interaction in live performance is accompanied by—and contextualised through—a critique of reductive and linear approaches to HCI. According to Di Scipio (2003), in many supposedly interactive systems, interaction is mostly unidirectional, flowing from human to machine, with the human acting as the interface between machine and environment and comprising the ‘the only source of energy and change’ (p. 270). Di Scipio observes that ‘the sound-generating system is not itself able to directly cause any change or adjustment in the ‘external conditions’ set to its own process’ (ibid., p. 271). In other words, the system lacks the possibility of modulating or interacting with its environment. While acknowledging the implicit fact that the human agent is listening and possibly responding to the output of the system they are operating, human response as a function of the system’s output is still optional, situating the locus of interaction with the human (ibid., p. 270). Drawing on cybernetic and constructivist theories of cognition, Di Scipio proceeds to establish a crucial point: interaction as it manifests between living organisms is only possible between autonomous systems able to observe their own internal state and regulate themselves accordingly. Yet, autonomy is not solipsistic. On the contrary, it is conditioned by a coupling of the system to its environment:

They [ecosystems] are autonomous (i.e., literally, self-regulating) as their process reflects their own peculiar internal structure. Yet they cannot be isolated from the external world, and cannot achieve their own autonomous function except in close conjunction with a source of information (or energy). (ibid., p. 271)

According to Di Scipio (ibid., p. 271), this biologically rooted definition of interaction is absent in much HCI design where the instrument, lacking autonomy, is unable to engage in interaction.

Di Scipio’s *Audible Eco-Systemic Interface Project* (AESI) proposes a sonic model of the biologically informed notion of interaction, based on audio feedback architectures combined

with adaptive signal processing. Audio feedback has been an established musical practice for decades, but Di Scipio’s practice stands apart by incorporating an additional feedback property, expressed as the coupling between audio feature descriptors and processing variables. In the simplest case (the lower chart in figure 2.2), the amplitude of the incoming signal is inversely controlling the output that is being sent to the speaker, allowing the system to control itself through negative feedback and stay within certain bounds (Di Scipio 2022).

Figure 2.2 Minimal examples of uni- and bi-directional modes of interaction

In a historical context, this form of negative feedback has much in common with James Watt’s *governor*—a self-stabilising device for the steam engine invented in 1788 (Maxwell 1868), and a cornerstone in the development of control theory. However, it was with the advent of the discipline of cybernetics that feedback became appreciated as ubiquitous in mechanical, as well as biological, systems. The particular kind of feedback utilised by Di Scipio was discussed by the cyberneticist William Ross Ashby (2014) under the name of *double feedback*, describing the ability of living organisms to adapt to changing environmental conditions by relying on sensorimotor feedback couplings (pp. 83–85). In order to distinguish this operation from audio feedback, I will refer to it as *control feedback*, as it is essentially a control operation, whether used to suppress or increase throughput in the system (see also (Melbye 2021a, p. 23)). Other examples of digital control feedback can be found in the Duffing oscillator described by Mudd (2017, p. 29), which implements

non-audio feedback immanent to the system itself, irrespective of the latter's relationship to its environment. Control signal feedback has additionally been implemented in some commercial compressors, where the compressor, rather than operating on the amplitude of its input, monitors its own output (Reiss 2011, p. 20).

Nicolas Collins' *Pea Soup* quietly revolutionised feedback musicianship and signal processing by being the first work to feature control feedback through a coupling of envelope following to signal phase shift (Collins 2020b; Di Scipio 2022). Di Scipio's implementation of control feedback in the digital domain significantly increases, not just the possible analysis methods, but also the signal processing possibilities. Where previous feedback musics usually included a human performer, AESI, in addition to the resonant frequencies of—and anything happening in—the room, relies on ambient sound as its source material, which, in turn, is a function of the audio system's output. By observing its environment in which traces of its own sonic actions manifest, the machine becomes self-observing, establishing sound itself as the interface through which interaction manifests (Di Scipio 2003, pp. 271, 275). This shifts the locus of interaction from a performer to the relationship between the DSP (digital signal processing) system and its acoustic environment—that is, to the behaviour of the audible ecosystem. The musical consequences of these shifts are significant. To a much higher degree than previously, the work becomes a function of the real-time interaction between performer, space, and algorithm, or possibly, analogue circuits. In Brian Eno's *Music for Airports* (Eno 1978) sound comes to constitute the ambience to human experience. In contrast, with AESI, Di Scipio problematises the perceived primacy of the human as the locus of sonic interaction, effectively questioning who becomes the ambience to what.

2.3.4 Dario Sanfilippo

In expanding upon—and collaborating with—Di Scipio, Dario Sanfilippo has developed a series of feedback works where audio signals provide both source material and control data (Sanfilippo 2019). Like Mudd, Sanfilippo explores the properties of complex, nonlinear, and chaotic⁵ systems for generating novel behaviour. A special focus of Sanfilippo's is *Complex Adaptive Systems* (CAS)⁶. The theory of CASes was conceived and developed by a group of complexity scientist around the Santa Fe institute, including Stuart Kaufmann, Murray Gell-Mann and John Holland, the latter defining CASes as 'systems that have a large number of components, often called agents, that interact and adapt or learn' (Holland 2006,

⁵ Chaotic is here understood in the context of chaos theory, meaning a nonlinear, yet deterministic system, the long-term evolution of which is often difficult, if not impossible, to predict (see (Gleick 2008)).

⁶ I have chosen to use all upper-case characters for spelling CAS, in contrast to Holland (Holland 2006).

p. 1). CASes and related fields such as *Artificial Life*⁷ and *Evolutionary Algorithms* (EA) have been explored by several musicians and artists (Eldridge 2008, 2022; Eldridge and Bown 2018; Impett 2001; McCormack 2001). By applying CASes within the context of feedback networks with minimal or no human interference, Sanfilippo's move shifts the focus from a CAS interacting with a human agent to that of an autonomous or semi-autonomous sonic ecology. A case-in-point is the work *Audible Icarus* (Sanfilippo 2022) in which one millisecond of a room's ambient sound is fed to a digital system that proceeds to develop its behaviour along completely deterministic principles. The sonic properties of the initial sample provide sufficient information to create diverse and rich behaviours over the course of several iterations.

Sanfilippo's (2019) use of higher-order audio descriptors such as spectral tendency, noisiness, and density further allows him to apply a higher level of abstraction to the adaptive dynamics of the audio signal than what is possible through amplitude measurement. In addition, his application of nonlinear processing (ibid., p. 133), waveshaping (ibid., p. 91), and specialised zero-crossing granulation techniques (ibid., p. 86) shifts the aesthetics of his work away from the drone-like and immersive expressiveness of much feedback music to something more closely associated with glitch artists such as Ryoji Ikeda (2005) or Nicolas Collins' (2022) work with electromagnetic feedback. Working in the FAUST language which is not optimised for FFT processing, Sanfilippo's algorithms rely on time-domain processes rather than the more CPU-expensive frequency-domain calculations—a feature of significance to the current thesis and any DSP environment in which processing power is limited.

2.3.5 Autonomy and semi-autonomy

In Di Scipio and Sanfilippo's work, the terms *autonomy* and *semi-autonomy* are widely used. In section 2.3.3 we saw that Di Scipio, somewhat in passing, equates autonomy with self-regulation. In a later paper, co-authored with Dario Sanfilippo, the authors elaborate on their understanding of the term by introducing a bio-cybernetic view of the autonomy as:

a structural openness, a constant exposure to an 'external' space. Different from automation, a fruitful notion of autonomy includes an operational openness to heterogeneous forces and actors in the environment: the system's necessary closure (defining its identity, its self) consists in a loop onto itself through the environment, which provides a pool of possible sources of information, and the

⁷ Artificial Life, or ALife, describes the diverse field of computational practices inspired by the evolution of living systems, and is discussed in greater detail in section 4.7.4.

space where other agencies are themselves active in their autonomic process.
(Sanfilippo and Di Scipio 2017)

In section 2.4.1 I will discuss the oftentimes precarious operation of applying biological terminology to non-biological systems. Here it suffices to say that, while I am sympathetic to the above definition of autonomy in the biological domain, its application to the machine domain must consider the stark differences between organisms and mechanical/computational systems with no metabolism and limited ability for self-repair, to name a few essential properties of most life forms. It is clear from Di Scipio and Sanfilippo's definition of autonomy that it by no means signals a complete independence of the agent from its environment. On the contrary, autonomy is suggested to only exist as a property of co-dependent systems. Yet, I remain wary of using the term for the systems described in this study and generally favour the term semi-autonomy, defined by Sanfilippo (2022) as 'a machine with some degree of adaptation that cannot alter the network's structure enough to change the relationship among variables or agents'. Semi-autonomy is still distinct from automation and describes a certain sense of independence between system and environment, yet does not exclude the possibility that the design and upkeep of the system may be the actions of an external agent, rather than being caused by the long-term evolution of the system itself.

2.3.6 Mapping revisited

In Mudd, Di Scipio and Sanfilippo's work, we can observe discrete, yet related approaches to mapping: Mudd's (2017) work relies on the digital implementation of complex and nonlinear transfer functions to produce nonlinear dynamics, but also incorporates digital feedback (p. 117), endowing the system with evolving dynamical behaviour. In Di Scipio and Sanfilippo's work, complexity is an emergent property of the mapping becoming a function of sound itself and thereby establishing several control feedback loops, informing the audio feedback and, hence, the sonic identity of the system. Affording human-machine interaction on the temporal scale of a performance, the complex timbral and spectral micro-events emerging in these systems are of particular interest to this study, specifically the first research question, that is concerned with the relationship between acoustic and electroacoustic timbre. The dynamical digital and electroacoustic practices described above share a rapport with the complex and nonlinear behaviour of double bass acoustics, in that all are timbrally and materially immanent to the system. This suggests that nonlinear dynamics emerging from feedback processes may constitute a promising avenue of investigation in terms of extending the complex timbre and behaviour of acoustic instruments into an electro-acoustic and digital space. Furthermore: through the establishment of some degree of systemic autonomy we are

provided with important clues to answering the second research question of this thesis, which is concerned with how resistant and precarious instrument-performer relationships may be established in the electro-acoustic domain. In order to begin engaging with the third research question, which revolves around the use of feedback as a driver of such relationships, we will need to go on a foray into the fields of cybernetics, neocybernetics, and autopoiesis in order to explore how feedback is contextualised within these epistemologies.

2.4 Cybernetics and neocybernetics

The mapping strategies developed by Di Scipio and Sanfillipo are intimately related to the cybernetic tradition of studying feedback as a means for both the generation, and control, of complex systemic behaviours. In addition to supplying operational strategies for the building of systems, cybernetics and *autopoiesis*—a second-order cybernetic development I shall shortly discuss—are at the root of Di Scipio’s discussion of interaction. While a general discussion of cybernetics is beyond the scope of this study⁸, due to its relevance to both feedback and interaction, a brief introduction is necessary:

Although not invented by Norbert Wiener, the term cybernetics was popularised by this American mathematician in his book *Cybernetics or Control and Communication in the Animal and the Machine* from 1948 (Wiener 2019). Starting out as a mainly mathematical discipline, cybernetics quickly became associated with the Macy conferences—an annual interdisciplinary meeting between anthropologists, psychologists, mathematicians, and engineers, discussing a range of subjects, from information theory to psychotherapy. As the discipline developed in the 1960s, a new field emerged, that of second-order cybernetics: led by the Austrian engineer Heinz von Förster along with the anthropologists Margaret Mead and Gregory Bateson, this development gave cybernetics—until then a science of systems and feedback mechanisms—an epistemological spin. Second-order cybernetics acknowledges that the scientist is themselves a system observing a system and, as such, need to account for their own presence in the observational process. Von Förster’s (2003b) observation, that systems always interact with an environment, further renders the notion of a hard boundary between subject and object, observer and observed, problematic, in turn challenging Newtonian objectivity and Cartesian dualism—two cornerstones of much western identity and epistemology. Following Clarke and Hansen (2009) I will refer to second-order cybernetics with the term *neocybernetics* from now on.

⁸ I can refer to Pickering (2011) for a thorough discussion of the British tradition of cybernetics, while Hayles (2000) presents a relevant critique of the disembodied notion of information in much cybernetic thought.

2.4.1 Autopoiesis

In order to more fully appreciate neocybernetic notions of circularity, feedback, systems and environments, we need to have a closer look at the concept of *autopoiesis*. With the publication of the book *Autopoiesis and Cognition: The Realization of the Living*, Chilean biologist Humberto Maturana and Francisco Varela (1980) proposed a model of cognition based on biology, in particular the architecture of the cell. Autopoiesis describes the minimal conditions for what constitutes a living organism as a metabolising, self-reproducing, and self-individuating system.

Operational closure and structural coupling

Two terms of central importance to the development of my argument are *operational closure* (originally called *organizational closure*) and *structural coupling*. I will briefly outline them here:

Operational closure is defined by Di Paolo et al. (2017) as ‘a network of precarious processes in which each process enables at least one other process in the system and is, in turn, enabled by at least one other process in the system’ (p. 113). As an example, Di Paolo et al. (ibid.) describe an autocatalytic set of chemical reactions, where a ‘network of molecules and reactions in which each molecule is produced by a reaction that is itself catalyzed by other molecules produced by the network, such that as a whole the set is able to catalyze its own production’ (p. 112). Similar to the discussion of autonomy in section 2.3.5, operational closure by no means entails a hermetically sealed system. Rather, it constitutes part of the puzzle of understanding how the identity of the individual is sustained throughout its relationship with other organisms and the environment. Any system depends on an environment in which it can access food and energy and deposit waste. A single-celled organism relies on a membrane and internal operationally closed processes, such as metabolic functions, for its continuous identity as a individual. Yet, without food, and in many cases, sunlight, the operational closure will break down and the cell die. Similarly, the cell itself provides important functions for other cells to maintain their existence. Maturana and Varela (1980) define these relationships as structurally coupled, that is, constituted by ‘a history of recurrent interactions between two (or more) systems’ (p. 75).

Figure 2.3 illustrates a simple example of operational closure within—and structural coupling between—three agents (pink circles) situated in an environment (green background). For the sake of ease in visually navigating the figure, the agent on the left is drawn bigger than the other two agents and feature more detail, yet, it should be assumed that all agents are somewhat structurally similar. Each agent possesses a semi-permeable border allowing

exchange with the environment, for example through the absorption of nutrients, excretion of waste, as well as through sensing. Illustrated by bi-directional arrows between the three agents, the latter are in a relationship of structural coupling. The blue-green circles illustrate the operationally closed processes taking place within agents, for example the autocatalytic processes described above.

Figure 2.3 Operational closure and structural coupling

Later in his life, Varela (1991) proceeded to develop these ideas into a biological foundation for the understanding of cognition: through its operational closure, the cell is understood to exhibit minimally intentional and cognitive behaviour. Furthermore, the structurally coupled higher-order relationships comprising multiple cells may give rise to emergent phenomena such as intelligence and consciousness. An embodied theory of cognition based on principles of autopoiesis was further developed under the name of *enactivism* by Varela, Evan Thompson and Eleanor Rosch (2016) in the book *The Embodied Mind: Cognitive Science and Human Experience*.

The autopoietic machine?

It is not difficult to see why the notion of the autopoietic machine may be of interest to designers of sonic ecosystems and autonomous computational agents (Di Scipio 2003; Hayes 2019; Sanfilippo 2019). Autopoiesis affords a model of minimal autonomy and, as such, can serve as an inspiration for conceptualising adaptive behaviour in agent-based systems such as CASes. Importantly, the interactions afforded by couplings between simple individual agents

may generate emergent complex phenomena conducive to sonic exploration. The machines described by Maturana and Varela are potentially substrate-independent and could theoretically be realised in any medium that affords metabolism and self-reproduction. But here is also the catch: autopoiesis—literally meaning self-production or self-creation—describes biological features such as metabolism and enclosure in a semi-permeable membrane. As such, autopoiesis is only by analogy applicable to digital systems, although there theoretically is no hindrance to the creation of a hybrid system comprising both digital and biological features⁹. As a response to the application of autopoiesis to domains such as sociology, Varela insisted that the former does not apply to every autonomous and recursive system (Protevi 2009, p. 101). In more recent work by Di Paolo et al. (2017), this concern appears in a different context, with the authors discussing their biologically rooted notion of intentionality and agency versus the claim that digital-mechanical and non-reproducing “intelligent” systems, such as autonomous missile guidance systems, exhibit agency (p. 178) (for a discussion of agency in sonic HCI practices, see Melbye (2021a)).

In a study such as the current one, that concerns itself with both the design of—and performance with—new instruments, I want to proceed with caution when applying what was originally a theory of biological systems to software and hardware. Although it is not inconceivable that metabolising computational wetware may one day become ubiquitous, or that self-replicating mechanical automata could exhibit life-like behaviour (such as imagined in Stanislav Lem’s (2020) *The Invincible*), the systems discussed in the present study are sharply defined by, and unable to evolve beyond, their physical and algorithmic design. When I argue for the application of biological terms to an algorithmic or mechanical space, I am therefore not arguing for identity between these domains. Rather, proceeding by, what Gilbert Simondon (2020) refers to as *veritable analogy*, the aim is to establish an ‘identity of rapports and not a rapport of identity’ (p. 107). In other words, this study is not concerned with establishing strict operational identities between, say, biological and digital systems. Rather, it seeks to identify how certain behaviours can be shared between different ontological domains without a strict cross-domain correspondence between the operations causing these behaviours.

In this section, I have provided a brief overview of how feedback was central to the discipline of early cybernetics. With neocybernetics and the notion of autopoiesis, feedback assumes a less outspoken, yet still central role in defining many of the circular processes taking place in systems that are operationally closed and structurally coupled to other systems. I will explore practical, theoretical, and artistic aspects of feedback in greater depth later

⁹ *The Extended Mind Thesis* (Clark and Chalmers 1998) claims that cognition extends beyond brain and body, to include our relationship with objects. The use of computers—and in particular smartphones—for cognitive offloading, could suggest that digital-biological systems are already ubiquitous.

in this chapter (section 2.11). Proceeding to situate feedback within a practice, such as my own, that comprises both instrument design and development, as well as performance and improvisation, I will now turn to a discussion of these subjects.

2.5 Experimental lutherie, DIY electronics

Where the nonlinear audio synthesis of Mudd's *Gutter Synth* (Mudd 2019) operates in a software-based space, Di Scipio and Sanfillipo's feedback networks are coupled to their acoustic environment through microphones and speakers. If we allow ourselves to describe these heterogeneous assemblages as instruments, their playability implies a step away from the traditional notion of instrumental performance, in which an acoustically resonant object is actuated by a performer, the technical expertise of whom is conditioned on a performance tradition preceding their own rigorous training. As a musician trained on the acoustic double bass, my own practice is indebted to this more traditional understanding of instrument and performance. In order to better understand how this practice may intersect with practices and instruments such as those discussed above, I will proceed to discuss a selection of new (and not-so-new) musical interfaces, the designs of which derive from already established instrument traditions, while also comprising signal processing and sound synthesis.

In the instrument design practices discussed below, digital mapping operations become embedded in an acoustic instrument that physically maps gesture to sound, such as when a string is plucked or bowed, or a reed moved by the flow of air. Furthermore, these instruments are in many cases played by performers with a background in traditional instrumental practices and training. Relying on both custom-designed circuitry and hardware, in addition to commercially available technology, the making of such instruments is informed and enabled by both DIY and hacker-space culture, resources such as Nicolas Collins' (2020a) book *Handmade Electronic Music*, as well as microprocessors like Arduino (n.d) and Raspberry Pi (n.d). Of importance to this thesis, and specifically designed for audio purposes, the Bela (McPherson 2017) microprocessor developed at Queen Mary's University in London is an audio cape created for the Beagle Bone Black board. The Bela allows for multichannel processing (up to 8 input and 16 output channels) of audio at sample rates of up to 48 kHz and a bit-depth of 16, with hardware latencies below the millisecond.

While acoustic instruments and laptop computers have long been interfacing with each other, such as Chris Chafe's (n.d) *Celletto* and Jonathan Impett's (2001) *meta-trumpet*, microprocessors are now increasingly finding their way into new instrument designs, for example Rafael Andrade's (2022) 3D-printed 16-stringed instrument *Knurl* and Sukandar Kartadinata's (2018) guitars. Kartadinata has also designed and built several commissioned

instruments, such as Axel Dörner's trumpet interface, Konrad Sprenger's motor-driven guitar and Julia Reidy's adjustable fret guitar (Kartadinata 2020).

Apart from Sprenger's guitar, the actuation of which relies on motors, the instruments mentioned above all comprise acoustic bodies, physically actuated by a performer. As such, their performance embraces aspects of traditional instrumental practice, in addition to operating in digital domains not limited to the physical laws governing acoustics.

2.5.1 The halldorophone and self-resonating vibrotactile feedback instruments

Of special interest to this thesis is Halldór Úlfarsson's (2018, 2019) *halldorophone*—a cello-like feedback instrument embraced by, amongst others, the composer and performer Hildur Guðnadóttir. The instrument features a built-in speaker being fed by the amplified pickup signal of the strings. The speaker vibrates the body of the instrument, establishing a mechanical coupling to the strings, and consequently causes a feedback loop to emerge. The halldorophone body has been designed from the ground up and, while sharing certain design features with the acoustic cello, has a semi-hollow body, making it acoustically more inert than the traditional cello. In contrast, Alice Eldridge and Chris Kiefer (2017), in collaboration with Úlfarsson, have applied the halldorophone principle to acoustic cellos, equipping them with pickups and amplifiers and inserting a speaker in the back of the instruments. The particular feedback mechanism of the halldorophone and feedback cellos—that of a mechanical coupling sensitive to perturbations by the player—places them in a family of instruments identified by Eldridge et al. (2021) as *self-resonating vibrotactile feedback instruments* (SRIs).

2.6 Virtual, hyper, meta-whatever

With the above discussion pertaining to just a fraction of new instruments, it may be useful to address what appears to be some underlying trends in new instrument design in general:

In particular within academic circles there has been a tendency to name new instrument designs with a prefix or adjective, with an incomplete list comprising *hyper-* (Machover 1989), *hybrid* (Waters 2013), *meta-* (Impett 2001), *virtual* (Mulder 1998), *augmented* (Michon et al. 2017; Úlfarsson and Melbye 2020), and *infra-* (Bowers 2002, p. 58; Bowers and Archer 2005). Of particular significance to this study, Bower's (2002) discussion of *infra-* stands out by contrasting the augmentation of 'virtuosic playing of a traditional instrument with additional control over computer generated contributions' (p. 58) in hyper-instruments with

infra-instruments that 'have some failing which might make a player's efforts to engage with it be of interest for exhibiting variable interactivity' (2002). While unpredictability, asymmetry and failing will be discussed later, here I want to point to the concern that the quest for developing and naming new instruments is an endeavour accompanied by a danger of juxtaposing the new designs with already existing and supposedly fixed instrument designs. What we consider to be established instrument designs are themselves products of a long and ongoing development. This development process, in addition to the emergence of more or less fixed designs of traditional instruments, has spawned a great number of prototypes, dead ends, failed experiments and completely viable, yet ultimately unpopular, specimens, now confined to the footnotes of history. That many instruments are not fixed designs, but ever evolving, is noted by Simon Waters (2021) in his observation that 'a musical instrument is not an object, but a process' (p. 3). Even for instruments assumed to have reached a certain developmental maturity, such as specimens of the violin family, the recent invention of steel strings and later, amplification with piezo and electromagnetic transducers, has significantly changed the music being made. It is difficult to imagine Chick Corea's (1972) group *Return to Forever* without the virtuosic steel-string driven double bass playing of Stanley Clarke, whose technical proficiency would have expressed itself quite differently on an unamplified double bass with high action and gut strings. Musical instruments, whether they be acoustic, electric, or digital, do not just rely on technology for their production and use, they are technologies in and of themselves. Whether performing with a novel digital instrument equipped with multiple sensors and DSP, such as Jonathan Impett's meta-trumpet, or an acoustic double bass, we are engaging with sophisticated technologies. In the case of the double bass, it represents the accumulation of collective as well as individual knowledge and has been considered cutting-edge at various, and not too distant, points in history. Additionally, as pointed out by Waters, the social context in which instruments are embedded co-configures their identity: the fiddle and the violin, while being physically identical objects, are not identical instruments in their social construction. The first is used in Irish folk music, while the latter is part of the assemblage that we call European classical music (Waters 2021, p. 5).

My discussion of Water's juxtaposition of object and process should not be taken to imply a dualism between these two terms: rather than asserting a negation of the instrument's objecthood or materiality, I argue that the recognition of its processual and social properties point to the fact that the material and the social are intimately intertwined to the extent that they co-constitute each other. The invention of steel-strings is a socio-technological event. At the same time, the playing of steel strings, and how they differ from gut-strings, are directly related to their material configuration. On a more personal level, it is the engagement with the materiality of the instrument, both as a physical, tactile object, *and* as a socially configured

channel of music-making that fuels my love for playing (for a more in-depth discussion of material configurations in my own practice, see Melbye (2022)).

If instruments are indeed processes, we may ask whether the use of an adjective or prefix signals a radical break with, or addition to, the instrument in question? Are not all instruments augmentations of some previous iteration of the process producing them? Or is there some particular point in the history of the development of musical instruments at which the notion of these novel terms becomes viable? Waters (2021, p. 6) argues that the non-standard instrument is a typical feature of human/instrument entanglements and that what is perceived to be an innovation is often an application from other practices (ibid., p. 5). This, of course, does not exclude the use of adjectives, but rather begs us to consider the instrument in its socially and technologically entangled and complex historical context. The double bass has always been in flux and process, rather than formalised once and for all. As such, digital technology is but one of multiple possible technologies producing an instrument's augmentation. This being the case, I will argue that it is still useful to trace the multiple identities emerging in the ongoing development of musical instruments, while proceeding with a particular focus on the introduction of digital technology.

2.6.1 Digital and acoustic instruments

Thor Magnusson (2019) observes that the digital instrument maker lives in a world different to both that of the luthier of acoustic instruments, and the designer of their electronic counterparts. Although the digital instrument relies on what Magnusson calls *technoscientific materials* (audio interface, amplifier and speakers, as opposed to wood, skin and horsehair) for the propagation of sound, the balance between, on the one hand, materials and, on the other, the abstract representation of sound in the shape of code, is skewed toward the latter (p. 56). According to Magnusson 'The digital system is material in its body, electric in function and symbolic in control' (ibid., p. 57). Such distinctions can be useful, especially in Magnusson's project of preparing the groundwork for a *digital organology* (ibid., p. 59). However, the question arises, at which point do they run the risk of underestimating the instrument's situatedness within a social and material performance ecology? Digital instruments interface with the world through vibrating and resonant objects, and computer code is only one part of the assemblage of programming languages and materials that allow us to talk about an instrument in the first place¹⁰. As such, the instrument may be digital in control, yet it is also firmly embodied in, and filtered through, material technologies, the resonant properties of which determine the quality of the sound produced. Consequently, they limit the amount

¹⁰ I am here omitting socio-economic relations, as these are not particular to either the digital nor the acoustic instrument.

of control one can exercise over the actual output of the instrument. This remains the case whether the instrument is largely software-based, such as Mudd's Gutter Synthesis instrument or an acoustic/digital hybrid such as Impett's meta-trumpet. While the resonant frequencies of speakers and amplifiers do not impact the sound of the instrument in the same way that a brass or wooden body does, they form part of the sonic ecology. Ultimately, they co-constitute the instrument. We do not just hook up our audio interface to a PA system to propagate the sonic representation of the code executed on our laptop. In sending audio to speakers, we partake in the assemblage of an instrument, the transductive process of which comprises a graphical user interface (GUI) or physical controller, high-level code, assembly language, binary digits, logic gates, digital-to-analogue converters (DAC), amplifier, speaker coil, and air pressure waves. Consequently, we should take care not to disassociate the instrument from its transduction between the digital and the analogue domain, or even the domain of air pressure waves, as if a musical instrument can exist independently of the sound it produces¹¹. Code is only ephemeral until we consider that any binary command is useless unless material conditions for its operation are present. We're operating at ever-increasing CPU instructions per cycle, made possible by advances in technologies negotiating the manipulation of matter. Ultimately, the promise of quantum computing challenges Newtonian determinism to negotiate the probabilistic subatomic behaviour of matter itself. But even with good old binary computing, the reality of digital music is material: optimising physical space for faster access to memory and reducing power consumption in digital processors have very real consequences for the digital luthier and musician: as studied by McPherson and Zappi (2015) the latency of the audio hardware and software impacts the "feel" of the instrument and the precision with which it responds to input (and, as I will discuss in 4.2.3, for the feedback musician, it affects the quality of the feedback). The sample rate will have an impact on interpolation between discrete sample values and, hence, the smoothness with which an analogue signal can be approximated in the digital domain, while bit-depth impacts decimal precision and signal-to-noise ratios.

The closer we observe the relationships between the supposedly disparate domains of the digital and the physical, or the virtual and the material, the more opaque the boundaries separating these domains become. This does not mean that differences evaporate in the cauldron of a flat ontology—such as Bruno Latour's (2007) actor-network theory—, but rather, that dynamic relationships are established through an ongoing, rather than pre-established boundary-making. This is what philosopher of science and technology Karen Barad (2007) refers to as an *agential cut*:

¹¹ Of course, the transductive process does not stop at the translation to airwaves: the (human) perceiver could be considered part of the assemblage.

the agential cut enacts a resolution within the phenomenon of the inherent ontological (and semantic) indeterminacy. In other words, relata do not preexist relations; rather, relata-within-phenomena emerge through specific intra-actions. (p. 140)

An agential cut is not just an analytical exercise, but is performatively enacted through the measuring agencies and apparatuses involved in observation. As such, we can appreciate that it is not only in the writing about instruments and technology that the agential cut can help establish useful, yet local, distinctions. Likewise, boundaries and differences are continuously drawn in performance, in which the digital, analogue, acoustic, and biological operate in an ongoing flux of differentiation and identification. In the context of the current study, agential cuts provide a useful understanding of the entanglement of heterogeneous domains, and will appear again in the analysis of modes of transduction and system/environment relationships in feedback networks (see also Melbye (2022) for a discussion of Barad's notion of the *apparatus* in relation to musical instruments).

Magnusson's (2019) observation, that the amount of code in any digital instrument is significant compared to the physical properties at play (p. 56), is reasonable if we, in addition to the audio synthesis and DSP code, consider the algorithmic instructions allowing the computer or microprocessor to function in the first place. Nonetheless, as we have seen, it is difficult to disentangle and quantitatively measure code against the technology and physicality of audio interfaces, physical controllers, amplifiers, and so forth. What does seem obvious, is the complexity and specialisation involved in the manufacture of digital instruments. This is acutely expressed in the situation of something failing or breaking: if any part of the acoustic double bass breaks, I will visit a luthier for a repair. With the digital instrument, depending on what breaks, the musician or luthier would need to engage with software updates, backward compatibility, audio or MIDI interface manufacturers, computer repair shops and so forth. It is beyond the scope of this text to fully engage with the socio-economic relations that produce, and are produced by, technology and instruments. Yet, relevant to this discussion is Magnusson's (ibid.) observation that the 'evolution of music technologies (. . .) is a history of increased theoretical encapsulation in musical instruments' (p. 109) and that digital instruments in particular are imbued with an increased level of epistemic dependencies (ibid., p. 57). Importantly, as the amount and depths of specialised technological knowledge is inscribed into the structure of new instruments, so the space of their possible operation is transformed, for example through the increasing computational headroom of real-time signal processing, synthesis, and the use of machine learning. While this could appear to be a trivial fact, its impact on instrument design, composition and performance is anything but trivial. Without understanding the mathematical foundations of

the Fourier Transform or Neural Networks, musicians are now able to use these technologies to generate synthesised or processed audio in real-time. In some cases, such techniques may shorten the distance between imagined and actualised sound and musical behaviour, while in others they create the condition for imagination in the first place. Accordingly, we can acknowledge the increasing epistemic dependencies of digital instruments described by Magnusson, while bearing in mind that acoustic instruments also rely on a set of highly specialised technologies. Consequently, if nothing else, we can appreciate that while terms such as hyper, meta-, etc., run the danger of upholding an often unhelpful dualism between old and new, acoustic and digital, their behaviours of the instruments they describe exceed what would be possible through strictly acoustic-mechanical means.

Taking a broader view, it becomes apparent that the pantheon of prefixes and adjectives discussed in section 2.6, in addition to signifying differences across technological domains, also implies the situatedness of the instrument within a social, historical, disciplinary, and cultural context. Importantly, rather than attributing the emergence of an extended instrument to the design process exclusively, it is in its uses that such extension requires a practical meaning, making possible the identification of differences in the first place. Simon Waters (2021) observes that traditional organology fails to consider that, without being embedded in ‘the activity which defines them as musical’ (p. 5), ‘Musical instruments on their own tell us very little’ (ibid.). Following Waters’ lead from an earlier keynote (Waters 2017), Thor Magnusson (2019) pleads for a digital organology that includes the ‘physiological, the technical, and the social’ (p. 65). In addition to these three domains, the practice and performance of—and the composition for—instruments, to my mind, are essential activities without which any instrument would become reduced to a lower-dimensional objecthood underflowing with meaning. Often taking place behind closed doors, solo practice and composition are usually solitary practices, the activity of which (pattern practice, technical exercises, and “noodling around”) may seem nonmusical to the casual observer. While instrument practices may not always directly manifest in how the musician actually performs, they nonetheless set the stage for the social activity of performance through the development of relationships with musical material and processes, whether that be a score, improvisation, or an instrument. The organology developed by Magnusson, then, is situated in a performance ecology (Bowers 2002) or ecosystem (Di Scipio 2003; Waters 2017), acknowledging that the musical instrument, and with that, any notion of extension, is enacted across several domains, time scales, and activities not reducible to physical or digital features alone. An ecosystemic approach allows us to navigate these domains while acknowledging their leaky ontologies, mutable boundaries, and agential cuts. Paraphrasing Simon Waters, in order to make instruments “tell us more”, in the following section I will apply an ecosystemic

perspective to a discussion of interaction and improvisation as they may play out in human-machine relationships. As will become more clear, this "telling" is in fact a dialogue, informed by the intersection of my own practice as an performer and improviser with the themes brought up in the above and following section.

2.7 Interactivity

While it is possible to perform entirely composed music on at least some of the instruments discussed above, leaving nothing to be decided during performance, they all primarily live within a domain of real-time exploration. As such, they can be situated within a larger taxonomy of interactive music systems—or *interactive composing instruments*, a term coined by Joel Chadabe (1997) in his pioneering work in this field. Chadabe's definition implies that the instruments are (at least seemingly) able to make musical decisions and to respond to a performer, with instrument and performer both partaking in a 'shared, symbiotic control of a musical process' (ibid., p. 201). In this process, the performer influences the instrument through a physical control interface, while themselves being influenced by the music produced by the instrument (ibid.). Impett (2001) conducts a critical discussion of Chadabe's assumptions, which acknowledges that his design choices are partly technologically determined by the time at which the instruments were built (p. 26). Yet, against the pseudo-random processes described by Chadabe (Chadabe 1997, p. 286) Impett contrasts the notion of *situated nonlinearity*, defining it as

an unpredictability which arises not from randomness but from the deterministic dependence of the behaviour of the system on a complex of parameters. These may be physical, auditory, environmental, or derived from the evolution of the system itself. (Impett 2001, p. 26)

To this I will add that Chadabe's (1997) use of the word *seemed* in italics, in writing that 'The CEMS System and the SalMar Construction (...) at least *seemed* to make musical decisions' (p. 291) is significant. I have already discussed Di Scipio's claim that the ability of both human and machine to modulate their environment is a prerequisite for his understanding of interaction. In the context of a discussion of improvisation, I will proceed to discuss why this ability can not be constituted by entirely randomised processes.

2.7.1 Interactivity and improvisation

Following Chadabe (ibid., p. 292), Rowe (2001, p. 277) and Lewis, (1999, 2018) I argue that interaction is closely related to the practice of improvisation or—to use Rowe's termino-

logy—interactive composition. Interactive composing systems afford engagement with the musical work in ways that are not entirely (or at all) planned in advance. With an instrument that exhibits complex (whether it be arbitrary or situated) behaviour, the performer need to adapt their behaviour to the systems with which they are interacting. Yet, the notion of improvisation itself means different things in different contexts: Rowe (2001, pp. 277–278) references Eric C. Clarke’s (1988) article *Generative Principles in Music Performance* that makes statements such as ‘free jazz [. . .] eschews the constraints of a pre-planned structure, and attempts to avoid the use of recognizable ‘riffs’” (p. 12), that free improvisation is an ‘almost entirely undetermined format’ (ibid., p. 7), and that the be-bop improviser ‘may try to construct an improvisation so as to include as many ‘quotes’ from other sources as possible’ (ibid., p. 13). Since Rowe’s project is to develop stylistically situated improvising machines, it makes sense to attempt to identify certain aspects of any given style. However, coming from a background in bebop, free jazz, and free improvisation, I find it difficult to follow Clarke’s reductionist analysis of these musical idioms. Surely, bebop relies on licks, but even a musician as fond of referencing other sources as Sonny Rollins hardly attempt to include as many as possible. Although identified as “free”, free jazz has developed its own set of motifs and riffs, many of which were established at the time of publication of Clarke’s article in 1988. Although not always melodic or harmonic, such tropes can be clearly recognisable across performances, and are shared by individual improvisers. One need only listen to Ornette Coleman, Albert Ayler, Cecil Taylor or Peter Brötzmann to appreciate this fact. Similarly, free improvisation—a practice strongly influenced by European musicians (Lewis 1999, p. 101), despite Derek Bailey’s (1993) ambition of creating and sustaining a non-idiomatic approach to improvisation, can be highly idiomatic. While Clarke’s article does make clear that improvisation is not a single process invariant across styles, his account misses that it is a social and situated practice, rooted in culture and history. Perhaps this is what leads Rowe to suggest that while no general machine improviser yet exists, in the future it may be possible to create one that could recognise a given musical style and adapt its behaviour accordingly (Rowe 2001, p. 278).

Before addressing the development of improvising machines further, I will approach improvisation from a different perspective. Such a perspective implies a personal orientation that carries with it certain values, aesthetics and biases. Firstly, my musical orientation is shaped by a history of engaging with a way of improvising that can largely be defined as originating in Europe in the late 1960s¹². It has since branched out into multiple other traditions (Rose 2017), and influenced a variety of musical practices, such as the *Echtzeitmusik*

¹² To a lesser, but still significant extent, I also consider the free-jazz movement emerging in the US in the early 1960s as part of my orientation.

(Beins et al. 2011) that emerged on the Berlin scene in the 1990s, the traces of which today still reverberate through many musical practices, including my own. Secondly, the following analysis is informed by a neocybernetic and enactivist perspective, as I believe that these epistemologies are well suited to understanding aspects of autonomy and human-machine improvisation. In addition to providing a background against which my analysis can be critiqued, I believe that disclosing my aesthetic and epistemological orientation may afford the reader a better appreciation of the musical and design-specific outcomes of the following discussion and the thesis in general.

2.8 Improvisation

2.8.1 Interactional asymmetry

Reminiscing about the weekly improvisation meeting *The Gathering*, Maggie Nicols (in Rose (2017, pp. 73–74) explains: ‘you’d get a period where it would be the same people and it would get incredibly coherent, almost insular, almost to the point where it was stagnating. And then somebody would come who would just completely disrupt everything – but it kept it fresh’. In Rose’s (ibid.) words: ‘the process of improvisation develops and benefits through not being too tied to one way of doing things. This not-fixed, potential instability gives rise to creativity and new opportunities within the continuum of the activity’ (p. 74).

In the above example, improvisation is identified as a precarious process in which the establishment of unstable relationships between performers, or a performer and the group, becomes essential for maintaining a field of musical possibilities to be creatively explored. Developing the idea of instability further, I will introduce the enactivist notion of *interactional asymmetry*—a term coined by Di Paolo, Buhrmann, and Barandiaran (2017, p. 116). Of special interest to the current study is Ravn and Høffding’s (2022) application of interactional asymmetry to improvisation in both dance and music. In Ravn and Høffding’s words:

Interactional asymmetry characterizes the ability of the organism to regulate the processes of interaction with its environment. (...) in relation to human capacities in particular, the involvement of interactional asymmetry in exercising one’s agency allows one to not passively go with the flow, be blown away by the wind, or be pushed off track under the influence of another. (p. 522)

According to Di Paolo et al., interactional symmetry, in addition to self-individuation and normativity, is a requirement for the establishment of a biologically rooted definition of agency. Here, normativity refers to the fact that, for a system to be considered an agent, the

regulation of its interactions with an environment must happen in accordance with intrinsic goals and desires (Di Paolo et al. 2017, p. 120). In the enactivist tradition, self-individuation is understood to emerge through the organism's operational closure (ibid., p. 113) (see also section 2.4.1), and is what sustains it as an individual throughout its structurally coupled relationship to its environment (ibid., p. 119)¹³.

The openness required by structural coupling comes at a price: whether observed at the level of the individual agent or network-level of interacting agents and their environments, precarious relationships between far-from-equilibrium systems are the norm. We can see how this applies to the process of group improvisation: to facilitate interaction and hence sustain the improvisational process, the improviser retains a structurally coupled relationship to their environment, including other improvisers. At the same time, merely adopting or parroting the behaviour of other performers, or even the group, without somehow modulating the coupling to these, undermines the dynamics of improvisation by compromising the operationally closed self-individuation of the improviser.

If indeed improvisation happens in the structurally coupled relationship between operationally closed agents and their environments, it follows that improvisation is not an essence of these agents but an emergent property of their relationships (Loaiza Restrepo 2018, p. 164). The social dynamics of group improvisation are sustained through this non-equilibrium and, as such, the oft-used term "playing together" does not do justice to what is essentially a precarious and open-ended process of exploring asynchronous and asymmetrical relationships between individual agents.

If we apply an analysis of the relational aspects of improvisation to the design of what John Bowers (2002) calls *improvising machines*, it becomes clear that simply listening and responding to input from a performer according to the conventions of a style of music provides a weak condition for the establishing of asymmetrical relationships¹⁴. Listening is certainly important in improvisation, but it is only one part of the establishment of a metastable situation rich in potentiality. Importantly, improvisation cannot be an immanent feature of an improvising machine, but must be established through its relationship to its environment. This may become clearer if we reduce the situation of improvisation to a relationship between a performer and an instrument. By removing the agency of other human improvisers and for the moment accepting an (albeit leaky) performer-instrument

¹³ Elsewhere (Melbye 2021a), I have engaged more fully with Di Paolo et al.'s discussion of agency in the context of human-machine improvisation.

¹⁴ Not to mention that the boundaries between different styles of music are opaque to say the least. Improvisers may use stylistic idioms across genres, and the task of defining the percentages of say, bebop or free improvisation, in a free jazz improvisation, becomes absurd.

dichotomy, we may gain a better understanding of human-machine relationships in the process of improvisation.

2.8.2 The solo improviser

Drawing on Judith Butler's work, in his discussion of group improvisation, Stapleton (2013) writes: 'It [improvisation] requires a willingness to risk one's values (...), to give up a stable understanding of identity, to risk one's very being, in responding to the address of another' (p. 172). In the case of a solo performance, the enactment of improvisation, in the absence of another, may be less evident. If improvisation is enacted and relational rather than intrinsic and presupposes an agent open to environmental perturbations, then we need to understand how a precarious scheme may be established in a solo practice.

Quoted in Borgo (2016), in Phil Hopkin's film *Amplified Gesture*, Evan Parker states:

You couple yourself to that instrument and it teaches you as much as you tell it what to do. (...) So there are things that you have under control, but every so often something will go wrong. You'll lose control. (Parker in Hopkins (2009))

Parker's use of the teaching analogy and his description of loss of control aligns with Di Paolo et al.'s (2017) development of a sensorimotor agency model:

In order for learning agents to be able to respond to varying environmental situations, they must be metastable (temporarily stable). (p. 102)

This suggests, that for solo improvisation to be possible, the relationship between performer and instrument must rely on a precarious and metastable learning agent (in this case the performer) coupled to an environment (here the instrument), the control over which is only partial. Why stability can only be temporary, not just in improvisation, may be illustrated through Heinz von Förster's *order from noise principle* (Foerster 2003b, p. 11). According to von Förster, a self-organizing system depends on a supply of entropy in the shape of 'cheap, undirected energy' (ibid., p. 13) from its environment, without which the system will be unable to adapt to changes in that very same environment. In the case of an improvised solo performance, the instrument not only translates musical ideas and gestures into sound pressure waves; in constituting an environment it also perturbs the stability of the performer, causing them to reconfigure their sensorimotor states through a process of self-organization similar to that of group improvisation, where 'critical levels of complexity, responsiveness, and surprise can be reached and maintained over the course of an extended performance' (Borgo 2005, p. 81). Edgar Landgraf (2009) observes that 'improvisation and

the overall incorporation of contingent elements inject “noise” into the system: they provide a resource pool from which the system can draw new impulses to create new forms and build new structures’ (p. 188).

The above brief foray has contributed some important perspectives on how interactivity and improvisation can be understood in the context of the present study: improvisation is a *metastable* process scaffolded by the interactional asymmetry between individual operationally closed agents (be they human or not). Listening is important (as are other means of accessing the environment and the actions of other agents), but is insufficient for generating the kind of complex, responsive, and surprising behaviour described by Borgo above. Interactional asymmetry, characterized as ‘the ability of the organism to regulate the processes of interaction with its environment’ (Ravn and Høffding 2022, p. 522), has been identified as a key driver of such behaviour. Through the discussion of metastability in group and solo improvisation it was found that the self-organization of the performer relies on access to entropy. The next session will take a closer look at how such entropy may come about, its relationship to randomness, and how it may apply to machine improvisation.

2.9 The improvising machine

2.9.1 Noise and adaption

By applying the principle of order from noise, we can see that a mutual establishment of entropy is taking place between human and machine. However, the nature of this entropy is agent-dependent. That is, the entropy used by the machine for its self-organizing processes may originate with the human’s actions, even if these actions, to the human performer, will often seem entirely logical and appropriate. Similarly, consider an improvising machine, the non-probabilistic actions of which, to the improviser, are complex and opaque. Here, the asymmetrical relationships reflect a degree of entropy introduced to the human agent, even if the processes of the machine itself are ordered, low-entropic, and deterministic. The context-dependency of noise allows us to re-evaluate the probabilistic processes described by Chadabe as having a seeming quality of “choice-making”: it is not clear from Chadabe’s description exactly what constitutes the pseudo-random processes he describes. However, randomness, in the context of bidirectional interaction poses a challenge to adaption: a system relying exclusively on arbitrarily generated behaviour will be unable to adapt to the changing conditions of its environment, as it would need to randomly cycle through all possible responses to any given stimuli in order to reach a satisfying solution—not exactly what we would expect from interactions between humans, or any organism for that matter.

Yet if we consider that perfectly logical and deterministic behaviour on the human end may signal an increase of entropy on the machine end, and vice versa, we can appreciate that interactional asymmetry can arise from the establishment of complex relationships between structurally coupled and operationally closed agents.

This does not mean that randomness should be discarded. In discussing the improvising machine *Voyager*, George Lewis (1999) addresses different tactics in applying filtered white noise to endow the system with a sense of personality, ultimately resembling ‘various states that were experienced as the music was improvised’ (p. 106). Lewis points out that “random” noise is used in the training of neural nets (ibid., p. 105), while randomness in evolutionary algorithms will be discussed in 4.7.4. Nonetheless, it is vital to consider where in the system, and to which degree, randomness is implemented. On the one hand, as we have seen in the discussion of improvisation (section 2.8.2), noise may be the driver of self-organizing processes, while on the other, it may compromise those very processes, as discussed in 2.7.

2.9.2 Embedded behaviour

As an alternative to randomness, Impett (2001) suggests that ‘By grounding a work in the detail of its environment and performance, the contributing factors can be unpredictable without being non-deterministic or arbitrary.’ (p. 41). This ecosystemic approach to interactivity, also favoured by Di Scipio (2003), relies on the generation of complex behaviours by a more thorough embeddedness of the system in its environment than what is the case with Chadabe and even Lewis. Lewis’ notion of a system with a sufficiently detailed representation of input, along with a similarly detailed mapping to output (Lewis 1999, p. 106), is taken further by Impett, whose use of orientation and motion sensors on the meta-trumpet points out that sound represents only one feature of a system’s environment. This begs the question of what “a sufficiently detailed representation” is in the first place? We may further ask, to which extent Rowe’s project of developing a general improvising machine seems feasible if it is supposed to exclusively rely on audio feature descriptors? Improvisers orient themselves in a complex environment of auditory, visual, haptic, and olfactory cues (to name a few), processed through socially and culturally conditioned histories. As such, the notion that listening would be sufficient to respond to a human seems problematic. On the other hand, needing to involve ever-expanding representational mechanisms of the world puts the very idea of representation into question. This only renders Rodney Brook’s (1991) observation that it is ‘better to use the world as its own model’ (p. 139) even more relevant, while justifying Lewis’ argument for sufficient, as opposed to complete, detail.

Rowe’s discussion of a general improvising machine that would be able to identify styles of music and then improvise convincingly in that style, leaves me with the question of

why we would want to make a machine that improvises like a human, provided that our concern is not educational, commercial, or a simple proof-of-concept? By applying the enactivist understanding of improvisation discussed above, we may approach improvisation as a relational feature of biological as well as possible machinic relationships, rather than as an exclusive human capacity. Consequently, we can explore ways of perceiving, knowing, and cognising not tied to our own evolutionary make-up. This is no novel idea and is echoed in ALife pioneer Christopher Langton's (1989, p. 1) plea for for 'locating life-as-we-know-it within the larger picture of life-as-it-could-be'. In the following section, I will conduct a preliminary discussion of what such machine perception and improvisation might look like, setting the stage for the application of those principles to the design of the instruments described in chapter 3 and 4.

2.10 Posthuman improvisation?

2.10.1 Machine perception

Digital implementations of models of human auditory perception, such as the Bark (Zwicker and Fastl 2013, pp. 159, 164) and Mel (ibid., pp. 112, 164) frequency scales are widely used in speech recognition (Hossan et al. 2010) and can provide the improvising machine with access to something akin to human hearing. Kiefer and Eldridge, for example, use Mel Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCC) to analyse the signal of a feedback cello, the result of which is used to train a neural network that in turn modulates the cello's signal (Hart n.d). Following such use of a higher-order audio descriptor for generating complex behaviour affording improvisation, I will proceed by asking if we can imagine other audio descriptors that extract information beyond the capabilities of human hearing? Human perception, having evolved to fit an evolutionary niche, represents only one aspect of reality, and in our design of improvising machines there is nothing preventing us from equipping them with sensory features unlike, or beyond, our own. Importantly, Di Scipio's (2022) observation that audio descriptors are not 'value-free retrieval of data presumably belonging to an external, objective world.' (ibid., footnote 9) but rather constitute a construction of reality¹⁵, suggests that we may see our task as creating improvising machines, the behaviour of which could be developed following guidelines that need not orient themselves according to the human perceptual apparatus. With a less sweeping statement than Langton, I will argue that in building improvising machines, perception and improvisation as we know it in

¹⁵ Construction is here understood in the context of *radical constructivism*, that suggests that reality is a function of the organism's, or the system's, internal processes operating on environmental perturbations (see also von Glaserfeld (2013, p. 115) and von Förster (2003a).

the human domain can be a reference rather than a goal. Human-Machine improvisation can create potentials beyond those we encounter in improvisation between humans exclusively. In relinquishing the notion of listening as a representation of an external world and, as with Impett's meta-trumpet, equipping the instrument with additional access to its environment through motion sensors, the instrument and environment become coupled through channels that co-constitute what is being "measured". Audio features and motion are no longer representations but rather correspond to Gibson's (1979) notion of *affordances*—that is—correspondences between the environment and the individual perceiving agent rather than representations of an external reality. In the current study, apart from the piezoelectric, airborne, electromagnetic, and mechanical transduction implied in the instruments' physical design, audio feature descriptors constitute the sole sense with which the machines have been endowed. Yet, the notion that passive reception of sensory stimuli is sufficient for interaction will be challenged by the design of a perceptual system that diversifies behaviours through the internal modulation of those stimuli.

2.10.2 Affordances, environment, world

The notion of a constructed reality can additionally be approached through a discussion of Gibson's (ibid.) *ecological theory of visual perception*, and his coinage of the term affordance, which has seen extended use in the sonic HCI literature (Çamcı et al. 2020; Magnusson 2019; Rodger et al. 2020). As observed by Anthony Chemero (2009, p. 109), Gibson's original writing is not always as clear as one could hope for, which has led to some confusion and disagreements as to what constitutes an affordance¹⁶. In proposing a definition of affordances, Chemero illustrates the concept with the notion that a copy of David Foster Wallace's (2011) tome *Infinite Jest*, to a mouse has the affordance 'climbability' (Chemero 2009, p. 110). In contrast, provided that certain preconditions such as age, culture, education, social status, etc., are met, to some humans Wallace's work affords reading. As such, affordances are not properties of the environment waiting around to be picked up by an organism, but are context-dependent. Chemero, in developing an updated theory of affordances, turns to the enactivist school of cognitive science (Thompson 2007; Varela et al. 2016) to introduce autopoietic sensory-motor couplings into an understanding of organism-environment relationships (Chemero 2009, p. 152). We have already seen how recent developments in the enactivist discipline offer useful tools and terminologies for addressing cognitive structures in improvising machines. I will here proceed to develop a distinction between *environment* and *world*, based on Varela's project of grounding cognition in biology through the theory of

¹⁶ I here rely on Chemero's understanding of affordances.

autopoiesis (Varela 1991). In Varela’s terminology, life—even something as simple as the single-celled organism—moves about in an environment (ibid., p. 85). But it is through the relationship of the organism to its environment that a world emerges (ibid., p. 86). The environment, to the observer, is the totality of stuff that constitutes the organism’s surroundings. Yet, it is through interaction with the stuff that matters to the particular organism—nutrients, predators or mates—that a *surplus of signification* (ibid.)—and hence a world—is created. Going back to Chemero’s example: the world of the mouse is very different from that of the human.

How would enactivism and autopoiesis apply to an improvising machine equipped with a simple sensory-motor system? Amplitude-detection is one of the most common audio descriptors available and would at first sight seem an uncontroversial technique, until we begin investigating the difference between two of the most widely used amplitude trackers—envelope following (also known as peak-detection) and RMS (Root-Mean-Square). Already RMS, in itself, poses a challenge, in that its ideal implementation introduces a delay equal to half of the time window over which the measurement is done, rendering it unsuitable for real-time systems. Accordingly, real-time RMS employs an operation including an infinite-impulse response (IIR) filter to approximate the ideal non-real-time measurement (Reiss and McPherson 2019, p. 148)¹⁷.

While RMS is useful for describing the evolution of amplitude over time, envelope-following, by providing separate attack and release times, allows the detection of peaks and transients in the signal, making it useful for controlling dynamics such as compression, where it is desirable to smooth out sudden changes in amplitude. Both RMS and envelope following provide valuable information about signal amplitude, and neither can be said to offer a better representation of reality than the other, the choice of measurement relying on the context of the situation. I will discuss amplitude-detection options further in section 4.7, but for now, we can acknowledge that the world of the improvising machine will depend on how it perceives its environment. Hence, the machine’s world is intimately entangled with its sensory and cognitive apparatus.

In addition to the claim made in section 2.8.1, that enactivism can be used to study human-machine improvisation, we have already discussed the applications of, and concerns with, autopoiesis in sound-based practices (2.4.1). Without making any strong claims of autopoiesis in improvising machines, we may, however, still benefit from the environment-

¹⁷ The complete difference equation for real-time RMS is

$$y^2[n] = \alpha y^2[n-1] + (1 - \alpha)x^2[n] \quad (2.1)$$

(Reiss and McPherson 2019, p. 148).

world model proposed by Varela. By moving beyond human notions of perception and recognising the ability of organisms to construct a world from their interactions with an environment, we can approach the design of our improvising machines through the lens of sense-making as a surplus of signification. That is, the machine should be able to construct a world of its own, through its (albeit humanly) curated interaction with an environment. This interaction is conditioned by the machine's access to a limited selection of features that may or may not correspond to human perception. More importantly, they are understood to not correspond to any assumed external reality. Obviously, the design, creation and continuous supervision of the machine is still a human act excluding any strict notion of autopoietic organisation. However, the sense-making properties of the machine could supposedly establish a precondition for—if not complete—then at least semi-autonomous behaviour. While this does not invalidate models relying on pre-established styles of music, it allows the musician the possibility of designing and interacting with systems, the qualitative evaluation of which can be guided by the exhibition of novel and complex behaviour, rather than anthropocentric notions of perception and musical style. In the current study, only semi-autonomous networks are considered, yet it is conceivable that the principles studied may be applied to fully autonomous machines as well.

2.10.3 Situatedness and immanence

In section 2.7 I discussed Jonathan Impett's use of the term *situated nonlinearity* that describes the ability of a system to generate behaviour from parameters that are 'physical, auditory, environmental, or derived from the evolution of the system itself.' (Impett 2001, p. 26). The Duffing oscillator, implemented by Tom Mudd and discussed in section 2.3.3, similarly exhibits complex and unpredictable behaviour. Yet, in contrast to situated nonlinearity that can arise from *both* external ('physical, auditory, environmental') as well as internal ('the evolution of the system itself') parameters, the Duffing oscillator's complex behaviour is generated by a feedback loop immanent to the system itself. In the following, I will use the term *situatedness* to describe processes that rely on access to an environment (for example frequency detection of the input of an electromagnetic pickup), while the term *immanence* will refer to processes internal to the system itself (for example a control feedback loop established between the output and input of a DSP algorithm). The above discussion of affordances, environment, and world makes it clear that situatedness and immanence are closely related (situated does not mean access to an objective reality, and immanence is most often entangled with perturbations from the environment), something that will become more apparent throughout the following two chapters. Yet, the distinction is useful in addressing how a system with limited access to its environment can generate complex behaviour through

immanent processes. In particular, it suggests that interactional asymmetry may be served by the system's dual property of being able to sense its environment (that is, being situated), while also being able to modulate its interactions with that environment (through its immanent processes).

Figure 2.4 illustrates the properties of a general agent-environment relation and builds on the operationally closed and structurally coupled processes of figure 2.3. The agent is *situated* through its access to its environment, here exemplified by orange circles nested on the semi-permeable boundary of the agent. For a human agent, such environmental access is determined by the senses of smell, hearing, vision, touch, and so forth, while a machine could have access to pitch, amplitude, electromagnetic radiation, infrared light, or other environmental properties unavailable to most humans. The strawberry-coloured circles on the agent boundary represent motor and vocal skills used for interacting with the environment and could be constituted by speech, manual operations such as grabbing or throwing, salivation, or the secretion of hormones. Or they could be novel machinic actions operating in domains beyond the human body's immediate sphere of influence, such as electromagnetism or light radiation. Similar to the operationally closed processes described in figure 2.3, the *immanent* processes of the agent are represented by blue-green circles within the agent itself. These processes could be constituted by the excitation and firing of neurons in the brain, or biochemical reactions in the body in general. On a higher level, learning, habit, and memory will play an impact on the constitution of immanent processes. Central to the current discussion, the presence of immanent processes means that the sensory stimulus of the agent is being modulated by internal processes. While co-determining what and how the agent perceives, these immanent operations contribute to the emergence of the agent's *world* in that they introduce a surplus of significance in relation to the agent's environment, as discussed above in section 2.10.2. In addition to the construction a world, the fact that these immanent processes allow the agent to modulate its interactions enables *interactional asymmetry*. This is illustrated through the asymmetrical black arrows between the agent on the left and the two agents on the right (similar to figure 2.3 the size and detail of individual agent do not suggest hierarchies of complexity or agential importance). Situatedness, immanence, and interactional asymmetry all contribute to the emergence of some sense of autonomy, the nature of which will vary between agents. In the figure below, autonomy is illustrated through the blue irregular circles. As with the dotted semi-permeable border of the agent, autonomy does not suggest that the agent is sealed off from its surroundings and enjoys some sort of unlimited and unchallenged freedom of choice. Rather, as discussed by Sanfilippo and Di Scipio (2017) in section 2.3.5, autonomy implies an 'operational openness to heterogeneous forces and actors in the environment'.

Figure 2.4 Situatedness, immanence, interactional asymmetry, and autonomy

A theoretical framework with which to explore the question of how resistant and precarious relationships in electro-acoustic music-making and instrument design is beginning to emerge. Yet, it is largely still unclear how this may be implemented practically. In section 2.3.6 I ventured the hypothesis that feedback may offer a useful mechanism for the generation of complexity in both the timbral and the interactional domains. The discussions regarding sense-making and autonomy above appear to support this speculation, through the observation that both rely on feedback loops internal to the system, in order to create a sense of structural identity. Only when a system is able to generate responses based on observations of its own state can it construct a world and, hence, deliver autonomous responses. This is reflected in Mudd's (2017) observation that participants in a sonic HCI study expressed a desire for unpredictability to be an immanent and emergent feature of instruments, while perceiving randomness as extraneous to the systems (p. 255). In closing the overview of artistic and research-related practices, I will therefore focus on feedback, with the intention of developing a better understanding of the fundamental features of this phenomenon and how they may apply to an artistic practice.

2.11 Feedback

Feedback as an artistic method stretches back to at least the 1950s, an overview of which is available in (Sanfilippo and Valle 2013). Current trends involve the *Feedback Musicianship*

Network (Kiefer and Overholt n.d)—an initiative led by Chris Kiefer and Dan Overholt, and a recent special issue of the *ECHO* journal focusing on artistic feedback practices (Impett et al. 2022). While the 15 journal submissions are dominated by open-air feedback systems, two articles featuring SRIs are included (Brandtsegg 2022; Melbye 2022). Electromagnetic feedback is the focus of an artist statement (Collins 2022), and one article concerns itself with cybernetic feedback principles in theatre (Polymeneas-Liontiris and Demeglio 2022). In addition to discussing feedback as it manifests across different material and social domains, the journal issue features theoretical in-depth analyses of feedback principles (Di Scipio 2022; Sanfilippo 2022; Thomasi 2022) as well as applications of Science and Technology Studies (STS) and critical, feminist, and queer theory to the understanding of how feedback is situated in the broader contexts of aesthetics, identity and ethics (Melbye 2022; Whale 2022).

The proliferation of feedback practices, both within and outside academia, suggests that feedback has reached a certain maturity and diversity of expression. This, in turn, calls for critical reflection and the development of a common vocabulary that expands on—and develops beyond—such terms as the *Larsen effect*¹⁸. Significantly, the question arises to which extent, if at all, feedback behaves differently across domains such as air, solids, and electromagnetism?

2.11.1 Feedback and adaption

Feedback offers a unique ecosystemic approach to generating complex behaviour in audio systems. As such, it is an alternative route and a complimentary tool to the generation of control signals from, for example, gesture recognition, complex transfer functions, or stochastic algorithms. Additionally, feedback can afford the emergence of semi-autonomous behaviour. While semi-autonomy is not a given, control feedback infrastructures developed by—amongst others—Di Scipio (2022), Sanfilippo (2019), Tomasi (2022), and Kiefer et al. (2020) are suggestive of a trend of utilising audio information retrieval and signal processing to endow systems with adaptive capabilities.

Even simple adaptive systems can exhibit emergent complex behaviour. As has been shown by the roboticist Rodney Brooks (1991), a set of simple rules or independent agents may be better at solving tasks than a structurally complex system organised through a top-down approach. In contrast to the informationally dense, logic gate-based decision-making of the robots prevalent at the time, Brooks' robots used environmental (light, proximity)

¹⁸ One of the first technical descriptions of audio feedback was by the Danish scientist Absalon Larsen (1911), after which the term *Larsen effect* has been used to describe feedback, often in more technical discussions, although the term has become colloquial in French (Kjerbye Nielsen 1984, p. 140).

sensors coupled to their motor-system (wheels, legs), constituting a simple sensorimotor feedback loop. This non-representational approach to environment-modelling allowed Brooks' machines to successfully navigate obstacles when moving about in a given space, without needing to be fed detailed information about their environment or the responses required to negotiate it. Similarly, complex behaviours in audio feedback systems need not depend on high-level rules. Rather, they may emerge from the interaction of several lower-level agents, as has been convincingly demonstrated by Agostino Di Scipio's (2022) use of RMS as the source data for a diversity of mappings to signal processing algorithms. Jonathan Impett's ongoing work with the meta-trumpet mirrors such operational parallelism, using cellular automata and evolutionary algorithms to generate a system of distributed agents.

2.11.2 Stability and metastability in feedback systems

Similar to the case of semi-autonomy, complexity is not guaranteed in a feedback system. As observed by Kiefer et al. (2020), audio feedback may cause a system to enter a basin of attraction with a single resonant frequency defining the system's behaviour (see also McLaughlin (2022) and Melbye (2022)). By gaining stability, the system's potential for development is diminished, limiting the space in which music may evolve. It is not only in music that this phenomenon has been observed: Ludwig van Bertalanffy (2015) observes that, if homeostasis was the goal of evolution, the latter would have achieved its goal with the amoeba (p. 192). In contrast, adaptive control structures can contribute to keeping the system metastable, that is, in a state of potentiality that allows the system, performer, or both, to explore multiple states without getting lodged in any single attractor. While basins of attraction will still exist in the phase space of a metastable system, the presence of negative feedback mechanisms can prevent any such basin from becoming too deep and locking the system in a single state. On the other hand, a system void of attractors, that is constantly changing its behaviour, offers few possibilities for interaction. The challenge, then, is how to design a system in a way that allows for it to feel sufficiently responsive without these responses becoming arbitrary. Such a state, hovering near a phase transition, has been studied extensively and identified by, amongst others, Christopher Langton (1990) and Stuart Kaufman (1995), to be operating at *the edge of chaos*. Sanfilippo's (n.d) DSP library *Edge of Chaos*—developed in the FAUST programming language—constitutes a software infrastructure designed to explore such metastability (see also Sanfilippo (2019, p. 100)).

By observing the usefulness of having our feedback systems be metastable, we can identify two levels of behaviour:

1. The system is sensitive to perturbations—that is, the system, if perturbed, will respond by changing its state. This is for example not the case when feedback has forced the system into a deep basin of attraction that will override any external perturbations.
2. The system can modulate itself: the system, even if left on its own, will continue to explore its phase space, changing and generating its own behaviour. Additionally, rather than simply responding to input, the modulation can be a function of immanent processes deriving from the internal state of the system.

2.12 Conclusion

In this chapter, I have delineated the background against which this thesis will develop. Through a discussion of new musical instruments, in particular those embodying digital architectures, it has become clear that their design is a practice firmly embedded in a long tradition of experimentation, stretching back past the discovery of binary computing and even electricity.

Additionally, I have attempted to negotiate the murky waters of boundary drawing, both in relation to the digital/material, physical/virtual, and system/environment. In this endeavour, Karen Barad's notion of agential cuts have assisted me in retaining a sense of differentiation in the face of dynamically shifting identities and leaky epistemological containers.

A tentative path toward the development of an improvising machine has been derived from the understanding that improvisation is a precarious process in which agents interact with, and adapt to, each other. In order to retain the metastability of such a situation, the agents need to exhibit interactional asymmetry—that is, the ability to regulate their interactions with their environment and other agents. Through the development of feedback systems able to monitor and respond to their environment in addition to their own state, situatedness and immanence can be established. This, in turn, shapes the conditions for autonomy, and hence the establishment of interactional asymmetry, ultimately affording interaction and improvisation.

Deriving from the more generalised architecture of figure 2.4, figure 2.5 illustrates a tentative step toward toward the visualisation of a semi-autonomous feedback system. The leftmost agent represents an audio system able to sense its environment through a microphone, and interacting with that environment through a speaker emitting sound waves. We can conceive of the environment as a room with multiple reflective and dampening properties, due to walls, floors, furniture, windows, and humans. Being a feedback system, the gain of the audio system will be sufficient to allow for a self-reinforcing loop between output and input, that is, between the sound waves emitted by the speaker and the direct and reflected

sound waves (illustrated by oscillating arrows) picked up by the microphone (the microphone of course also picks up ambient sound not initially produced by the speaker). Once audio enters the system, several processes modulate the signal before passing it on to the speaker. These processes can derive from the situatedness of the agent, that is, they can derive from properties of the signal itself, such as amplitude, frequency, and noisiness, to name a few. As will be discussed in section 3.2.1 such features may additionally derive from the output, rather than the input of the system, in which case they will be immanent to the system itself. Importantly, these features may be used to drive adaptive and self-organising processes in the system, for example the amplitude scaling used by Di Scipio and discussed in 2.3.3. As can be seen by following the arrows representing these internal processes, such processes may come to constitute control feedback loops within the system itself. Similar to figure 2.3 and 2.4, each of the processes illustrated here enable, and is enabled by, at least one other process, and as such, contribute to the interactional asymmetry established between the feedback system and its environment. In other words, the audio circulating between the system and its environment is modulated by processes internal to the system, which in turn renders interaction bi-directional. This feature can extend beyond interaction in the audio domain: an arrow extends from the agent to the right and reaches one of the internal operations of the audio system. One example of such a relationship could be the use of a MIDI controller to adjust parameters in the DSP domain of the audio system. Yet, because the MIDI data is being modulated by other processes that can either be situated or immanent, the mapping between fader and the parameter being modulated is rendered non-linear, complex, and beyond the full control of the agent operating the controller.

Figure 2.5 Tentative architecture of a semi-autonomous feedback system

Through the two main feedback loops illustrated here, namely the audio feedback between the input and output of the system, and the control feedback taking place within the system itself, a certain sense of systemic autonomy emerges. While the system may not satisfy the conditions for biological or autopoietic autonomy, it is nonetheless able to modulate its interactions with its environment, based on the construction of a simple world. In the following two chapters, I will explore how such semi-autonomy may be implemented in various feedback architectures.

The design of and performance with such architectures raise important questions regarding what new relationships become established between the performer and the machine. I have already touched upon the role of resistance in my own acoustic practice. In addition, we previously saw Evan Parker using terms such as ‘losing control’ and things ‘going wrong’ when speaking about solo performance, while Tom Mudd discussed nonlinearity as a means of affording ongoing exploration of new instruments (2.3.1). It should be clear that, by relinquishing agency and interacting with a semi-autonomous machine, the internally constructed world and decision-making process of which may be different from ours, the interactional asymmetry may play out in ways unexpected. How does resistance become situated in the relationship to such a machine? Further, to which extent can we evolve musical and technical skill sets that accommodate, not only the new timbral possibilities, but also the increased complexity of input-output relations? If, as earlier suggested, human notions of perception and improvisation may be a reference rather than goal for such a machine, we are in need of a recalibration in terms of how we evaluate and understand our encounters with it. This will be explored in chapter 5.

Chapter 3

Frogs and attics: A study of two feedback systems

In this chapter, I will discuss two performance systems, each employing a different feedback process in combination with the double bass. Each system will be discussed in turn, providing a progressive understanding of the various ways in which feedback can be used as a creative tool for sound generation, in addition to providing a tentative framework for the design of an improvising machine.

3.1 Feedback and frogs

3.1.1 Open-air and mechanical feedback

In section [2.11](#) I inquired to what extent differences between feedback in discrete domains can be identified. To proceed with an answer, I will discuss two modes of feedback: open-air and mechanical.

A minimal example of open-air feedback, described by Di Scipio (2022), manifests in a coupling between an open-air microphone and a speaker: any sound, manifesting as air pressure waves in the microphone's environment, will be registered as an electrical charge. This signal is amplified and sent to a speaker cone driving a membrane according to this electrical charge, thereby generating changes in air pressure and, hence, sound. Provided that the system is operating at a sufficient amplitude, this process will become self-reinforcing, ultimately resulting in the Larsen effect, or simply, audio feedback. In this example, it is significant that we perceive the feedback phenomenon in the same domain in which it operates, namely as acoustic air pressure waves. In contrast, a coupling between an exciter

placed on a solid, such as a plate, that in turn shares a mechanical coupling with a transducer, such as a contact microphone, is mechanical. While the vibrated solid comes to serve as a speaker membrane, creating air pressure waves, the latter are a by-product—rather than the medium—of the mechanical feedback process. Nonetheless, it is largely through this by-product that we perceive the feedback phenomenon, although the performer will often experience the actual mechanical self-resonance on their own body. According to Eldridge et al. (2021), provided that the system is sensitive to physical interaction by the player, we can consider it a *self-resonating vibrotactile feedback instrument (SRI)*.

For a recent example of a largely mechanical feedback architecture, I will turn to an instrument described in Øyvind Brandtsegg's (2022) article *Making a pitch map for a vibrotactile feedback instrument*. Here, the author discusses a system comprising an exciter mounted on a fibreglass plate coupled to a piezo pickup which is attached to the performer's hand. When touching the plate, a closed mechanical loop is formed, resulting in feedback.

Figure 3.1 Øyvind Brandtsegg's self-resonating vibrotactile feedback instrument.
Photo: Øyvind Brandtsegg

The fact that Brandtsegg with some accuracy and consistency across playing situations can map the frequency response of the system, points to a difference between at least some mechanical and open-air feedback systems: the vibrating surfaces, or mediums, of mechanical feedback systems are often fairly rigid and comprise surface areas on the order of a few cubic centimetres. In contrast, the propagating medium of open-air systems is often situated in a performance space of several cubic metres, with numerous surface reflections, often further complicated by moving human bodies. As an exception, the first scientific publication on the phenomenon of audio feedback by Absalon Larsen (1911), described

an open-air system, the frequency of which was tuneable due to the encapsulation of the vibrating medium within copper tubes, whose lengths were determined by the operator (Kjerbye Nielsen 1984, p. 141). In this special case, the limited spatial extension of the copper tubes and the air within these afforded a high level of control over the environment of the system. This, then, presents a cue with which to deepen our understanding of the system-environment terminology that has evolved in the ecosystemic literature on feedback (Di Scipio 2003; Sanfilippo 2019; Sanfilippo and Di Scipio 2017): preamps, ADCs, DSP processors, DACs, and amplifiers constitute the system, with input and output represented by microphones and speakers, respectively. The environment, then, is the space through which air-pressure waves propagate. Applying this definition to a mechanical audio feedback architecture such as Brandtsegg's, we see that the system itself is bounded by pickups and transducers, whereas the environment becomes the solids through which acoustic waves propagate.

Here, I will invoke the agential cuts discussed in section 2.6.1, to help me navigate the complexity of feedback architectures, where system-environment boundaries are mutable and enacted through the process of interacting with the totality of the structure. In the example just given, we can identify multiple subsystems and environments in relation to the system itself. If we, for example, identify the DSP processor as a system unto itself, then ADC and DAC constitute input and output, with the environment describing the remainder of the electro-digital domain, in addition to the performance space. Similarly, by identifying a system to comprise the entire feedback loop (the electro-digital domain coupled to the space), the environment can be conceived of as the electricity feeding this system, the building in which the space is located, and so forth. While making a cut in such a place is entirely valid, in the current context, it is less enlightening for a deeper understanding of the feedback process itself.

While the multiplicity and mutability of system-environmental couplings within and beyond feedback architectures will be useful to keep in mind in the current chapter, their implications will be more fully appreciated in the discussion of feedback transduction in section 4.4.

3.1.2 What the Frog's Eye tells the Frog's Brain

In 2018, in the hope of pushing the strings of my acoustic double bass into self-oscillation, I attached a piezo microphone (hereafter referred to simply as piezo) to the front of the instrument, feeding the signal into an amplifier that in turn fed a tactile transducer (hereafter referred to as transducer) placed on the back of the bass. Rather than amplifying any string vibrations, the signal becoming amplified turned out to be that of the vibrations of the

body, effectively creating a mechanically coupled feedback loop that excluded the strings altogether.

A double bass body feeding back on itself in the mechanical domain is not dissimilar to open-air feedback: the system quickly settles on a single frequency with a strong fundamental and few—if any—harmonics, sonically approximating a sinusoidal waveform. Bowing or plucking the strings, as they are effectively external to the strong coupling of the closed mechanical loop, does little to change the feedback. The system, I found, left to its own devices had limited musical potential. However, I soon discovered that applying hand pressure to the double bass body would cause the frequency of the feedback to change, the frequency depending on the amount of pressure applied, as well as the location of the hand, on the instrument body. Altering the vibrational properties of the instrument body through hand dampening reconfigured how the signal was reflected throughout the body, ultimately accommodating for the establishment of new resonant properties. Similarly, changing the pickup and transducer placement proved to alter the signal path, and hence, the feedback response.

The instrument was eventually named *What the Frog's Eye tells the Frog's Brain* (hereafter *Frog*) in homage to the paper of the same name, authored by Lettvin et. al (1959).

Choosing to focus solely on the mechanical feedback phenomenon, I placed the double bass back down horizontally, with the scroll resting on the floor, the lower back slightly elevated to accommodate for the protrusion of two transducers attached to the back of the instrument. After some experimentation with transducer placement, I settled on the upper and lower back, respectively, with each transducer offset from the centre by about 3 cm (see image 3.2). For performance, I positioned myself kneeling next to the instrument, allowing me to use both hands for applying pressure.

The piezos were placed on the front of the instrument, inside the f-holes, toward the bridge. The choice of placement was guided by what felt to accommodate the largest potential frequency range and the best response to hand pressure. Placing the piezos inside the instrument is visually less obtrusive. It also allows for the exploration of the entire surface of the front of the instrument without concern for touching the piezos, thereby avoiding any potential handling noise. The fixed location of both piezos and transducers means that the possibility of altering the physical distance between these systemic nodes is lost, although this can to some extent be digitally modelled using phase shifts. Instead, the possibility of varying the gain of each piezo in addition to its panning relationship to either transducer was used to increase systemic variety.

A variety of piezos have been used, including a Schaller *Oyster S/P* (n.d), a K&K Sound *Big Shot* (n.d), and an Ehrlund *Pickup* (n.d). Before being sent to the audio interface,

Figure 3.2 Transducer placement on the *Frog*

the pickup signal is routed through an impedance converter made by Jo Gries (n.d.). The transducers used are Dayton Audio *DAEX30HESF-4* (n.d[b]) or *DAEX25FHE-4* (n.d[a]) and are driven by a S.M.S.L *SA-36A PRO* (n.d[a]) amplifier.

Early experiments with the instrument showed that some spectral and musical variation is possible purely through variations in hand pressure and position, as well as the modulation of panning configurations. However, these operations yield a quite limited domain of exploration, likely to become tedious to performer and audience alike. Consequently, with the intention of introducing additional variation through the modulation of the feedback signal, a DSP stage was added between piezos and transducers. The DSP, discussed shortly, is implemented in SuperCollider running on a laptop, with discrete algorithms for each microphone-transducer pair. To accommodate for the use of both hands for applying pressure on the double bass body, an early decision was made to generate most processing variables from audio features. A MIDI controller was used to control some processing variables, in addition to the control of wet/dry mix for each algorithm.

3.1.3 Improvising with the Frog

Performances with the *Frog* have been largely improvised and confined by the limited timbre of the instrument. As with many feedback systems, the natural behaviour of the *Frog* tends toward one or, at best, a few single frequencies, from where the system will only diverge if

perturbed. Even when hand pressure is applied and polyphony achieved, it is one comprised of clearly distinct narrowband feedback tones. Performed solo, as well as in group settings, it is the relationship between frequencies, rather than individual ones, that I find most exciting to explore. However, an exploration of the *Frog*'s frequency topology, like that undertaken by Brandtsegg, is an avenue of research which, although promising, has not yet been undertaken.

In addition to the clear sonic identity established by the instrument, the domain in which improvisation and performance takes place is largely defined by slowly changing timbres. I rarely do quick hand movements, preferring to let textures develop over long time stretches while observing subtle changes in amplitude, timbre, or balance, between simultaneously sounding frequencies. While there is a tradition of slow-moving, repetitive, and drone-like timbres in experimental music and sound art, for example in the work of Alvin Lucier (2002), Eliane Radigue (2004), Phil Niblock (2009), and William Basinski (2014), in acoustic improvised musics, bands such as Trigger (n.d) and my own group Flamingo (n.d) have both explored improvisation through repetition and sustained textures. As such, performances with the *Frog* are historically and personally situated in a practice of real-time explorations of timbral morphologies on extended time-scales. The limited pitch set and timbre afforded by the instrument makes it a good candidate for this kind of slow musicking: change becomes relative to the slow morphology of constrained material. However, the change that does *not* happen, that is, when the system has become entrenched in a deep basin of attraction, and a single feedback frequency is continuously sounding, still carries the risk of musical tedium. In the early cybernetics movement, this risk was eloquently expressed in the critique directed by Grey Walter at Ross Ashby's feedback-governed *Homeostat*—a machine designed to regain homeostasis in the face of perturbation: according to Walter, Ashby, in his aim to establish homeostasis, had in fact created a *machina sopora*, that is, a sleeping machine (Pickering 2011, p. 164). In performing with an instrument that relies on feedback to generate continuous sound, I am balancing on the sometimes precarious ridge separating minimalism from boredom. Perhaps paradoxically, the advantage I have over Ashby is, that while both the *Homeostat* and the *Frog* rely on perturbation by a human, in performing with the *Frog*, the human-machine relationship is more firmly embedded in a tradition of live performance, where things are supposed to happen. Performatively engaging with the drama of things *not* happening offers a way to establish periods of stasis, in contrast to which the slow overall movement of the performance can seem relatively active.

Whereas most performances with the *Frog* have lasted 20 to 30 minutes, in the longest performance to date, I played for 105 minutes at the 2019 edition of the NOW now festival in Sydney, Australia. Even though the performance was conceived of as a sound installation, rather than a concert, some audience members stayed for the entire duration, surely experien-

cing, as did I, a mix of accomplishment and relief as the music came to an end. In such a case, musical narrative—the traditional notion (at least in the Global North) of the development, tension, and resolution of thematic material—became secondary to the establishment of a focus on the very slowness of development. Waiting became a performative act in itself, with myself and the audience alike sometimes spending minutes observing the instrument in stasis until the feedback changed on its own, or I decided to interfere.

3.1.4 Performing the Frog

On the 25th of March 2019, I performed with the *Frog* at the venue Labor Sonor in Berlin. Being the culmination of a string of performances in Sydney, Melbourne, Copenhagen, Gothenburg, and Stockholm, this performance also marked the penultimate solo concert with the *Frog* so far. The video documentation presents an insight into the music produced with this instrument, at a point at which I had developed a performance practice with which I felt comfortable. This documentation is available from <https://vimeo.com/327281165>.

From the earliest stages of working with the *Frog*, I have been fascinated by its tactility. As a double bass player, I am familiar with shaping timbre through the application of finger pressure on strings and bow, as well as experiencing the sensation of a large resonating body becoming coupled to my own. Yet, physically engaging a self-resonating instrument with the palms of my hands shifts my focus away from the actuation of sound to that of modulation. In applying hand pressure to an already vibrating object, the hand becomes a sensor as much as a device for manipulation. The moment the palm of my hand establishes contact with the surface of the instrument body, the act of aural listening becomes intimately coupled to the tactile sensation of the grain of the wood, as the vibrations of the latter are transferred to my hand. At this moment, an awareness emerges of the many points across the entire surface of palm and fingers available for engaging the instrument. To achieve a change in timbre, it is sometimes sufficient to lightly touch the instrument body with the tip of a finger, while the application of the entire palm can be used to soften, or filter, a high-pitch feedback build-up. The topology of the instrument body becomes a map that can be explored in terms of sonic morphologies: applying pressure on the lower bout tends to cancel out low-frequency feedback, the inverse being the case with engaging the upper bout. However, within these larger topologies, small local variations in location and hand pressure can have significant systemic effects. If performed at a volume soft enough to allow for the instrument to retain sensitivity to perturbation, the sonic outcome of minuscule changes further depend on which state the system is currently in. During low-frequency feedback, applying pressure to the upper bout has little effect, while mid-range or high frequency

feedback generally seem to respond to pressure across a greater section of the instrument body. The instrument will additionally behave differently depending on the exact location of piezos and transducers, which, although having been formalised to a certain degree, is often prone to slight variations each time the instrument is set up for a performance. As such, travelling with the instrument (which requires dismantling) or even more unpredictably, performing on borrowed instruments, introduces a degree of uncertainty that only adds to the sensation that every performance is a process of getting to know the instrument through an exploration of its topology. This exploration is intensely haptic, having led audience members on two different occasions (Melbourne in Australia, and Berlin in Germany) to associate the performance with the practice of *Reiki*. The impression of a ritualistic massage is possibly amplified by the fact, that I play the instrument kneeling in the Seiza posture favoured by some mediation practitioners and assumed during sutra chanting in some schools of Zen Buddhism¹.

Figure 3.3 Performing with the *Frog* at Hošek Contemporary, Berlin, 2018. Photo: Lena Czerniawska

3.1.5 Signal processing

The algorithms employed in the *Frog*'s DSP domain are described below. While time codes are provided for some algorithms, the effect of others are difficult to distinguish as discrete

¹ My own experience of the Seiza posture derives from chanting in the Soto Zen lineages of Kodo Sawaki, Taisen Deshimaru and Shunryu Suzuki Roshi.

events. Each time code is a clickable hyperlink, directing to its precise position in the online video.

Notch-filtering

Feedback limiting is a feature of many modern PA system and employs a frequency tracker tied to a bandpass filter with a narrow q . When feedback is detected, the filter is activated in order to attenuate the frequency. A similar mechanism is employed in Nicolas Collins' digital implementation of Pea Soup, where the performer can remove particularly persistent feedback frequencies before the start of the performance (Collins 2020b, p. 8). For the *Frog*, I implemented a similar design featuring two distinct modes of operation:

- Automatic control: the centre frequency of the filter is being updated with the output of the frequency tracker at regular time intervals, causing the continuous cancellation of dominant frequencies ([04:55](#) - 5:50).
- Onset activation: the centre-frequency is updated whenever an amplitude onset is detected. This allows the performer to gently tap the instrument to change the feedback. In combination with effects such as granulation, that may introduce transients, this mode can yield fascinating musical behaviour. Where a transient triggers a new frequency that in turn triggers the granulation to introduce more transients, the result is positive control feedback. Alternatively, if a transient causes the system to reach a spectrally stable state less likely to produce additional transients, it will manifest as negative control feedback ([06:20](#) - 7:00).

Frequency variation

The output values of the frequency detector are stored in an array containing information about the most recent 20 seconds of the system's history. If any frequency occupies more than 80% of this array, a short delay is introduced to the output of a piezo, the latter chosen at random by the algorithm. The delay equals the reciprocal of the tracked frequency divided by two, and introduces a short Doppler shift, which is usually sufficient to generate a state change ([03:00](#)).

Spectral centroid comparator

The spectral centroids of both input (piezos) and output (transducers) are measured and compared to give a measure of the amount of change introduced by the processing. The inverse of this difference is mapped to the frequency of a LFO (*low-frequency oscillator*)

controlling the speed of the panning between piezos and transducers. As such, by exploring the phase space of microphone-transducer couplings, a negative control feedback loop that attempts to correct spectral instability in the DSP domain is established.

Spectral flatness-controlled delay

Like spectral entropy, spectral flatness is an audio descriptor used in speech recognition. It measures the amount of entropy in the signal, with a value of 1 amounting to white noise and a value of 0 being that of a sinusoidal waveform. The inverse of the flatness value is scaled to between 0.001 and 0.01 and mapped to the frequency of an LFO controlling the time value in a delay line with cubic interpolation. Since pure feedback resembles a sinusoidal waveform, and hence results in a spectral flatness measure approaching 0, the less entropy the signal exhibits, the larger the delay will be, and vice versa. (13:50 - 15.00).

Granulation

A granulation algorithm controlled by neural networks responds to high- or low-frequency states by adjusting its grain density and size, effectively creating filtering effects that push the spectrum in the opposite direction of its current state (between 06:11 and 8.50 in the video). The higher the frequency, the shorter and sparser the grains will be, while lower pitches will favour a denser grain texture with larger individual grains. In the latter case, the effect is that of a phasor or comb filter, due to the interference between phases of individual grains. Since the system is more prone to high-frequency feedback, the granulation engine serves two purposes:

1. In high-frequency timbres, the propensity of the granulation to trigger short, discontinuous grains increases the chance of triggering the onset-driven notch filter, allowing the system to explore a greater variety of resonant frequencies.
2. In low-frequency timbres, the increased energy of the system, caused by larger grain sizes and higher density, deepens the basin of attraction in this part of the system's phase space, effectively increasing the possibility for exploring low-frequency feedback. As such, the granulation engine, contrary to some of the other processes described, constitutes a positive feedback loop when the system enters low-frequency states.

The algorithms described above constituted some of my first endeavours into creating feedback systems with semi-autonomous DSP architectures. Being simple and created from intuition and trial-and-error, rather than guided by a clear conceptual idea, the algorithms nonetheless contributed to an understanding of how audio feature descriptors may be used

to drive signal processing variables, resulting in complex and unpredictable, but, ultimately, deterministic behaviours. The implementation of negative and positive control feedback proved useful for an understanding of how the control of processing variables may become decoupled from manual control, instead becoming immanent to the system itself. For a musician used to performing with both hands, this is significant, as it leaves me at liberty to physically engage the instrument body without concerning myself with the continuous modulation of processing parameters.

Machine Learning in feedback systems

Although abandoned and, with one exception (discussed in [Appendix B](#)), not present in later work, machine learning, in the shape of Rebecca Fiebrink's *Wekinator* (Fiebrink n.d), was used in *Frog*. Since a particular challenge emerged in the training on audio feedback, I refer to [Appendix B](#) for a discussion of its implementation.

3.1.6 Double the Frog, triple the fun

In 2019, the trio *Ens Ekt*² created the performance-installation *New Communication* at the former WW2 bunker *Artist Homes* in Berlin. In addition to my own double bass, I was able to secure a second double bass and equip each instrument with a piezo-transducer pair. With each instrument having its own analogue and digital signal chain while sending and receiving audio to and from its sibling, a distributed feedback network across the two instruments was established. Leaving them on their own during extended periods of the 4-hour installation, at various points, I would return to the instruments and play them for a period of time. Footage documenting such an interlude is available at <https://vimeo.com/752080061/d477f46de7>.

When left on their own, the behaviour of the two feedback double basses would rather quickly settle into a stable pattern, exposing the fact that the signal processing, although allowing for some adaptivity, was generally not sophisticated enough to let the systems explore a greater part of their phase space. In a later iteration of the *Frog*, developed for the feedback seminar *The Sound of Feedback, The Idea of Feedback in Sound* (Melbye 2020b), this was partly addressed by the implementation of a variation on a frequency rate-of-change measure. This approach will be discussed in greater detail in section [3.2.2](#).

² With Paul Stapleton on VOLA (Volatile Assemblage) and saxophone player Simon Rose.

Figure 3.4 Playing two *Frogs* at Artist Homes, Berlin (FAAB (see chapter 4) visible in the foreground). Photo: Cristina Marx / Photomusix

3.2 attics for all, floors for none

3.2.1 Control signal feedback and constructivist signal processing

In section 2.3.3 I introduced Agostino Di Scipio's discussion of interaction and his implementation of an audio feedback system that is able to modulate its environment, thereby providing a bidirectional model of interaction. Di Scipio's system implements audio feature analysis at the input stage, the data of which is driving processes further down in the signal chain, in a feed-forward process setting the stage for semi-autonomy.

In many feedback systems, due to the circularity of the feedback loop, it is not trivial to clearly identify input and output: the input (air pressure waves sensed by microphone) x to the system at time n , may as well be conceived of as a function of the environmentally modulated output (air pressure waves produced by the speaker) y at time $n - 1$. As such, the feed-forward DSP architecture, with output $y[n]$ being a function of input $x[n]$, could be conceived of as a feedback architecture of the form

Figure 3.5 Feed-forward DSP topology

$$x[n] = y[n - 1] * \varepsilon \quad (3.1)$$

where ε denotes the environment.

This brings up a number of questions, two of which I would like to focus on here: Firstly, can we conceive of feedback systems, the audio in- and outputs of which are not strongly coupled in a self-resonating audio loop? In other words, can we implement feedback architectures that do not operate in, but still modulate, the audio domain? Secondly, if the environment modulates the system as suggested by equation 3.1, it begs the question of what the role of the environment is to the self-organizing system, and to what extent the environment can be accessed by that system?

In order to answer the second question, we can revisit Francisco Varela's radical constructivist notion of environment and world. If the environment is the stuff in which a system is situated, then the world of that system is a function of the relation between system and environment. As such, the idea that "the environment makes sense to the system", suggests a passivity on the part of the perceiving system, as if it is receiving a fully formed world from its surroundings. Rather, sense-making is not unidirectional. The difference is important: the environment does not present itself to the system; it is enacted as a world through the relationship between the environment and active sense-making of the system itself.

Answering the first question will additionally elucidate what we mean by sense-making in the context of the creative use of feedback: consider a system where input and output are weakly coupled³, such as an acoustic instrument, the output of which fed is to a signal processing algorithm, and finally, a PA system. With a gain below the threshold of causing feedback between input (instrument microphone) and output (PA speaker), a feed-forward

³ As noted by Di Scipio, it is understood, and trivial, that some sense of feedback through input-output coupling is still present, through the performer's response to the state of the system. Additionally, input and output are rarely, if ever, completely decoupled: some audio from speakers will bleed into microphones, even below the threshold of feedback.

DSP architecture is not identical to a delayed feedback loop, as was the case above. In a weakly coupled system the input is not a function of the past time-step of the output, but rather, a function of the environment of the system, for example a performer playing the instrument. As such, input audio descriptors will largely be decoupled from the system's output. As they are not immanent to the system itself, the system's level of interactivity becomes reduced to that of a unidirectional response to its environment. In contrast, the radical constructivist notion of sense-making described above offers a working hypothesis with which to approach signal processing: it allows us to conceive of a system that enacts a world through the system's internal feedback processes operating on the input from the environment. According to the constructivist notion of cognition, organisms do not have access to their environment other than in the shape of a perturbation, suggesting that information does not cross the system-environment boundary (Borgo 2016, p. 11). Rather, access to the environment, and hence information, is provided by the self-organising processes of the organism's cognitive apparatus responding to the perturbation. In order to provide such self-organizing properties, the organism, in addition to sensing its environment, should have access to its own state. Consider substituting an audio system for the organism, with all the reservations discussed in section 2.4.1. By placing audio descriptors at the output stage of the signal processing and feeding their scaled data back into the signal processing algorithm itself, might we be able to generate some sense of response, or even adaption, immanent to the system? In signal processing terms, this would approximate a complex variation of an IIR (Infinite Impulse Response) filter, which, in its most simple case, has the difference equation

$$y[n] = x[n] + \alpha y[n - 1] \quad (3.2)$$

with α being the filter coefficient, determining the amount of feedback in the filter.

In signal processing terms, this essentially amounts to the control feedback discussed in 2.3.3.

Figure 3.6 Feedback DSP topology.

Note that audio feature analysis is now conducted on the *output* of the signal processing

3.2.2 Granular time stretch

Control signal feedback was first methodically explored in the work *attics for all, floors for none* (hereafter *attics*), composed, performed, and submitted as a pre-recorded video for *IF* (Improvisation Festival) in Guelph, Canada, 2020. Video documentation is available from Vimeo (<https://vimeo.com/430341503>). The SuperCollider code for *attics* is available at https://github.com/Adampultz/attics_for_all.

In a previous work, *Tåren*, I had explored temporal stretching through granular synthesis on pre-recorded material⁴. For the IF festival, I decided to explore this technique in real-time, using the input of a double bass as the source audio.

Granular synthesis is by now widely documented in both recordings and writing. I can refer to Roads (2004) and De Campo (2011) for in-depth overviews of its history and techniques. As with any granulation technique, granular time stretching is based on the segmentation of the audio signal into discrete grains. By lowering the playback rate to less than 1/1, the time index of new grains will be slowed down as well. With a small enough grain size, the repetition of individual grains will be perceived as a slowing down of the signal, without a change in pitch. The extent to which this slowing is perceived as retaining the identity of the original signal depends on the relationship between the size of individual grains, grain density, grain envelope, and the stretch factor. Generally, by ensuring that neighbouring grains overlap, the signal will sound continuous. As described in section 3.1.5, a large overlap will create phase asymmetries between individual grains, resembling the classic phasor effect. This can further be exacerbated by a high grain density, while a low density combined with a large overlap will lead to noticeable repetitions. Alternatively, grain size can be calculated as a function of the density, describing the overlap between individual grains⁵. Depending on the grain envelope and overlap, high grain densities may additionally introduce frequency modulation, with sidebands corresponding to the frequency of the grain firing rate. While the dynamic variation of overlap has been implemented in later work (*Echoes of Unspecified Origins* and *Towering Silence*), in *attics*, grain size is calculated as the inverse of the grain firing frequency and extended by 0.1 seconds, a rather significant duration in the granular domain. Even with highly calibrated grain speed and density, the longer the signal is stretched, the more difficult it will be to perceptually retain the impression of the original signal.

⁴ *Tåren* (meaning *the tear* in Danish) is based on an improvised opera of the same name from 1986. Recorded by my father, it features me, age 5, singing and playing the piano. The time-stretched version from 2019 is available at <https://vimeo.com/446383631>.

⁵ For example, a value of 1 means no overlap, while a value of 2 means that each grain is sustained twice as long as the firing rate, giving a 50% overlap with each neighbouring grain.

Buffer size

The temporal stretching of pre-recorded material will simply extend the original recording by a factor inverse to that of the time stretch. In real-time systems, where an audio signal is continuously read into a circular buffer, any stretch rate below 1/1 will cause the read pointer to incrementally lag behind the write pointer, only to eventually become overtaken by the latter. As such, a pragmatic choice will need to be made regarding the size of the buffer being written to and read from: too large a buffer will cause the read pointer to gradually recede into the distant past, while a small buffer size will keep it in closer correspondence to the present moment. However, it will also result in discontinuities in volume and timbre, due to the frequent take-overs by the write pointer. For *attics*, a buffer size of ten seconds was chosen.

DSP architecture

The software for *attics* was written in SuperCollider. It consists of four identical granulation engines (in the current recording panned across the stereo field), all being fed by the mono audio signal from a microphone placed in front of the double bass.

Recording

If all four granulation engines were continuously recording and playing back an identical signal, their output would be indistinguishable. Rather than continuously writing into the buffer, recording for each of the four engines is activated by an amplitude-sensitive trigger. When the input amplitude exceeds a certain threshold⁶, a phasor signal, ramping from 0 to 1 over the course of 50 seconds, is triggered. The output of this signal corresponds to the increasing probability (0 being none and 1 being 100% probable) that the engine will start recording into the buffer. Once the input signal falls below the threshold again, recording is stopped. The record buffer receives the input audio with a delay of 0.2 seconds, to ensure that the entire attack is preserved, should a trigger signal be sent the instant the volume gate is activated.

Due to the likelihood that each recording will start at an arbitrary time, the content of the individual buffers will vary. Additionally, due to the amplitude thresholding mechanism, only audio loud enough to be of “interest” to the system will fill the buffer. Once audio is present in the buffer, it is accessible for playback, without the buffer being immediately overwritten by ambient sound, should the performer stop playing. *attics* was recorded in a fifth-floor attic

⁶ Depending on the sensitivity of the microphone, preamp gain and ambient sound, this threshold must be set manually. Currently, any activation of the double bass will cause the threshold to be crossed.

in Berlin, the sonic environment mainly comprising the low-frequency sound of street traffic. Even though the repetition of individually high-entropic grains in fact reduces the overall entropy of the signal⁷, time-stretching quiet ambient textures tends to generate step-like noise structures that is not of much interest in this specific case. Scenarios where the ambient sound environment could be of musical interest are conceivable, in which case the threshold can simply be adjusted.

Figure 3.7 Recording topology of *attics for all, floors for none*

While this thresholding mechanism works satisfactorily, a few improvements could be considered: instead of a simple threshold, a Schmitt trigger with discrete thresholds for starting and stopping recording could be implemented (the Schmitt trigger will be discussed in section 4.9.2). Furthermore, these thresholds could be made to depend on the system state, coupling input sensitivity to output features. The ramp time of the phasor signal could similarly be made dynamic, for example by coupling it to the length of the previous recording, or to a measure of the system's overall complexity.

The arbitrariness of the record onset additionally entails that only in rare cases will amplitude onsets become recorded, since the probability of a trigger signal is the lowest just after the amplitude threshold has been crossed. As will be discussed later in this and the next chapter, the granulation of onsets yields particularly interesting textures. The algorithm could be improved by using onset analysis to directly trigger recording, should a sufficiently spectrally rich attack occur.

As is visible in the video, I perform wearing headphones. This allows me to monitor the processed signal independently of speakers, and as such, avoiding the processed signal entering the microphone and hence triggering recording, even when I am not playing. In a performance for a live audience, this would of course not be possible, in which case a contact microphone placed on the bass could serve as the triggering signal. Whether it would in fact be a musically viable feature to have the system audio feed back into itself has so far not been explored.

⁷ The repetition raises the redundancy of the signal, which, according to Bateson (2000, p. 421) constitutes information, and as such, negentropy.

Playback

In contrast to recording, playback is continuously granulating the content of the buffer, providing the advantage that, once the buffer is filled, the system can operate on its own, should the performer stop playing.

I will here describe each of four granulation parameters in turn:

Time Stretch

As already noted, time stretch describes how quickly the read pointer moves through the buffer. In the case of *attics*, the speed of the read pointer is coupled to the spectral flatness and centroid of the output of the granulation engine, constituting the first of several control feedback loops. The spectral flatness of the signal is calculated linearly and then integrated with a *leaky integrator*—the simple low-pass filter discussed in (3.2). In the case of *attics*, the filter coefficient α corresponds to the reciprocal of the spectral centroid multiplied by ten (as with many of the mappings discussed here, values are constrained to avoid dividing by zero and other mathematical operations that risk resulting in *NaN* (Not-a-Number) outputs). With larger values of α , the low-pass effect is more pronounced, increasing the overall value of the signal. Consequently, a decrease in spectral centroid will raise the value of the spectral entropy mapped to the granular playback rate.

A few features of the feedback loop between the system's output and the granular time stretch can be observed:

- The noisier the output signal becomes, the closer it will push the read pointer to real-time playback, while a sinusoidal output will cause the playback rate to approach a standstill.
- The more low-frequency content the signal has, the higher the rate of integration of the spectral entropy.
- As noisy signals are often rich in high-frequency content, the interaction between spectral entropy and centroid means that the read pointer will only stop in extreme cases, such as when the output signal approaches white noise—a very unlikely case.

Grain density

The calculation of grain density comprises several steps, here explained in sequence and illustrated with a flow-chart:

1. The estimated fundamental frequency x of the algorithm's output is calculated and subtracted from a low-passed (one-pole filter) copy of itself, the normalised filter cut-off being set to 1 minus the reciprocal of the Nyquist frequency. The square root of the reciprocal of the absolute value of this operation (b) is smoothed with a one pole filter (c). It is then integrated twice (d and e) to give us a measure of the evolution of frequency over time, and will be designated $f_{0,e}$. In (e), the integration coefficient β is set by the performer.

$$(a) \ y[n] = \alpha x[n] + (1 - \alpha)y[n - 1]$$

$$\text{where } \alpha = 1/Nyquist$$

$$(b) \ k[n] = \sqrt{1/(|y[n] - x[n]|)}$$

$$(c) \ y[n] = \alpha k[n] + (1 - \alpha)y[n - 1]$$

$$(d) \ z[n] = y[n] + y[n - 1] * 0.8$$

$$(e) \ f_{0,e}[n] = z[n] + \beta z[n - 1]$$

2. The spectral centroid x is smoothed, again with a one-pole filter, this time with a cut-off of $1 - (5/Nyquist)$ (f). The squared spectral centroid deviation $SpecCent_{Dev}[n]$ describes the mean centroid of all four granulators, divided by the spectral centroid $y[n]$.

$$(f) \ y[n] = \alpha x[n] + (1 - \alpha)y[n - 1]$$

$$\text{where } \alpha = 5/Nyquist$$

$$(g) \ SpecCent_{Dev}[n] = \left(\frac{\frac{1}{4} \sum_{k=0}^3 y[n]_k}{y[n]} \right)^2$$

3. $SpecCent_{Dev}[n]$ is multiplied by $f_{0,e}[n]$ (h), the result of which is smoothed with a one-pole filter (i). The coefficient of the filter equals $1 - (5 * 1/Nyquist)$. The result is mapped to the grain density.

$$(h) \ x = SpecCent[n] * f_{0,e}[n]$$

$$(i) \ y[n] = \alpha x[n] + (1 - \alpha)y[n - 1]$$

$$\text{where } \alpha = 1 - (5 * 1/Nyquist)$$

Figure 3.8 Grain density calculation.

The output (grain density) of the flow chart represents granulator k

As can be seen, the grain density depends on two higher-order audio descriptors (frequency-acceleration and spectral centroid deviation), both of which describe heuristic approaches to measuring dynamism in the system:

- Firstly, by measuring the absolute development of pitch over time, we get a value independent of the sign of the signal's change, instead describing the range and speed of the signal's dynamics, not unlike a rate-of-change measurement⁸. In the case of *attics*, with the value being mapped to grain density, the more the signal output varies, the higher the triggering frequency of new grains will be. Accordingly, with grain duration being calculated as the reciprocal of the grain triggering rate, the former will decrease.
- Secondly, by comparing spectral centroid across the four individual granulation engines, a door to cross-adaption is opened, although in this work the opposite is explored: the higher the deviation from the mean, the higher the density of the individual granulator will become, possibly further introducing artefacts.

These features imply that greater variation will lead to higher density and possibly less stable behaviour, while the opposite is the case for slower-evolving signals that are more

⁸ Actual rate-of-change was not used as I, at the time of writing the code, was not familiar with this operation. Additionally, SuperCollider does not allow easy access to individual samples, from which rate-of-change would be derived. I have since stayed with the mechanism described here, simply because it, for my own purposes, gives a good enough approximation of a signal's temporal development. More importantly, I find that it results in causal and musically pleasing behaviour.

uniform across the four granulators. In both cases, the mapping will favour positive feedback processes reinforcing the state of the system. While adaption often relies on negative feedback loops to counterbalance run-away processes, similarly to the other works discussed in this study, feedback is used, not as a proof-of-concept for the musical viability of adaptive systems in general, but as a tool to generate complex and interesting musical behaviour. As such, adaptive DSP architectures are applied where musically feasible. In the present case, with the control feedback favouring positive feedback, adaption is not a strong feature of the digital system itself. Rather, adaption happens at the discretion of the performer, who is left to decide to which extent their interaction with the system should try to accommodate to—or counterbalance—the latter’s immanent processes. However, because the DSP architecture of the system is operationally closed, mainly perceiving and responding to its own output, rather than the state of its environment, the DSP taken in isolation favours immanent over situated behaviour. Consequently, the level of control available to the performer is to a significant extent defined by the system itself.

3.2.3 Comb filtering

In my acoustic arco double bass playing, the combination of steel strings and high action affords the production of timbres with significant high-frequency content. With one of the objectives of this study being the exploration of how such salient features of acoustic performance can be extended into the electro-acoustic domain, the introduction of a comb filter affords such extension. Comb filtering, in this case being applied to the output of the granulation, introduces evenly spaced resonant peaks to the signal, that result in focused higher-frequency spectra.

In contrast to the positive feedback introduced by the time stretch algorithm discussed above, negative feedback is employed in the application of the comb filter, by letting the blend of the filter (in relation to the clean signal), become a function of the inverse of the square root of the spectral centroid deviation. The result is that high-frequency attenuation is introduced with the increase of spectral complexity between individual granulators. In section 4.9.2 I will discuss comb filters and their dynamic and adaptive applications in more detail.

3.2.4 Performing attics for all, floors for none

The version of *attics* documented here constitutes one of a handful of takes recorded over four hours in June 2020. The duration of the performance was at the request of the IF festival. Being limited to 10 minutes, it falls short of letting the performance develop at a pace slow

enough to fully appreciate the emergent timbres and behaviours that could be generated by a less time-sensitive iteration. The piece was performed this one time only, although parts of the software have been re-appropriated for other purposes (see section 4.12).

The bass playing on *attics* was improvised, except for the opening section, which is based on a spiccato technique I have been developing since 2014. As such, improvisation is taking place within a space aesthetically delineated by my preference for bowed and plucked open strings and harmonics, as well as clearly defined sonic gestures. The tuning of the double bass is based on integer ratio multiples of a fundamental A of 440Hz (see [Appendix C](#) for a description of tuning), that has been my main tuning since 2017. This tuning introduces a diverse range of difference tones and beat frequencies between harmonic dyads, and generally creates an unstable timbre without any clearly defined tonal centre.

In what follows, I will conduct an analysis of the performance of *attics*. The evaluation is heuristic—and at times speculative—in that it is not always clear to me which processes engender certain phenomena. To execute this analysis in a fashion that elucidates and criticises the interactive qualities of the performance, at times I will resort to the establishment of boundaries between double bass, performer, and the digital signal processing stage. As agential cuts, and following the neocybernetic and enactivist tradition, such demarcations do not imply that these are hermetically sealed domains. Rather, they should be appreciated as entangled phenomena, the discrete identities of which only emerge through their situatedness and reciprocal relations (Barad 2007; Borgo 2016; Foerster 2003b).

Analysis of attics

At 00:00, as I start playing, the granulation buffers are empty and, as such, only start outputting audio once recording becomes activated, clearly making audible the different recording onsets produced by the probabilistic phasor ramp. Incidentally, once the granulators do start operating, the grain triggering frequency approximates the frequency of the spiccato bow strokes, creating a shadowing effect that, although being based on sampling the double bass, is a property immanent to the signal processing.

At 00:30 a frequency oscillating around 942 Hz emerges. Due to the timbral complexity of the signal, it is difficult to determine exactly what produces this behaviour. One explanation may be the positive control feedback mechanism of the frequency detector mapped to grain triggering frequency. Once a high frequency has been detected, it will reinforce itself by triggering faster grains, the frequency of which are additionally modulated by the spectral centroid deviation value. Since this causes the spectral centroid of the granulator in question to diverge even further from the mean, it will introduce yet another positive control feedback loop, reinforcing the high pitch, while causing subtle variations in its precise frequency.

At 00:39 the signal processing produces a slowly pulsating output, likely to be a result of a low frequency value mapped to the triggering frequency of the grains. As above, this is a positive control feedback loop, causing the triggering rate to further contribute to the detection of a low frequency and thereby reinforcing the current state of the system. However, with the decrease of the spectral centroid value for this granulator, its spectral centroid deviation factor will increase, causing the audible modulation of the low triggering frequency heard from 00:39 to 00:54, and similarly identifiable throughout the piece.

Up until now, I have primarily been bowing two discrete harmonics of ratios 23/16 and 16/23 on the 3rd and 4th string. At 01:19, I actuate the 2nd string, which shows the difference in how the algorithm responds to the timbre of a bowed open string as opposed to that of a harmonic: the open 2nd string, having more low-frequency content as well as a more complex spectrum than bowed harmonics, stands out against the somewhat “softer” texture of the granulation of the latter.

At 01:30, a stark discontinuity in the buffer waveform is revealed, either resulting from the playback read pointer being taken over by the write pointer, or the recording having stopped while overwriting an earlier, more quiet recording. While I appreciate the sudden shifts in dynamics, the digital artefacts accompanying this instance could be avoided by triggering a recording fade-in and fade-out—a feature implemented in the later work *Towering Silence* (4.12.2).

When I stop playing at 02:35, the ability of the algorithm to develop on its own becomes more apparent. However, my entrance at 03:09 is premature, and the performance would have benefitted from a longer rest from my side, giving the system the possibility of exploring new territory to a greater extent.

Between 04:02 and 04:13 one of the granulators settles in to what appears to be a metastable rhythmical structure brought about by variations in grain triggering frequency. The emergence of such repetitive, yet rhythmically intricate patterns suggest an attractor in the system’s phase space, toward which the system will tend under the right circumstances. Unfortunately, the buffer is overwritten with new material (a single left-handed pizzicato attack on the 1st string) already at 04:14, one of the rare instances in which recording is almost instantly triggered by the volume gate⁹.

Between 04:15 and 04:57, my own playing and the behaviour of the system converges around stable and continuous bowed harmonics and smoothly overlapping grains, respectively. This section, as most sections in the present performance, would have benefitted from being longer. However, at 04:57, a digital glitch appears, in the shape of what seems to be a

⁹ The actual attack of the pizzicato note is either not registered in the recording, or is not played back due to the read pointer moving slowly through a part of the buffer not associated with the attack.

sampling error or stark volume discrepancy between two waveforms written into the buffer at discrete moments in time. While this glitch is sonically alien to the general texture of *attics*, here I manage to recontextualize the “error”¹⁰ by increasing activity and engaging in bowed harmonics with pronounced attacks yielding acoustic spectra of greater complexity than those preceding the glitch. Even with the operationally closed control signal loop of the DSP, feeding the system such timbres alters its behaviour significantly toward becoming more pronouncedly pulsating. This culminates at 05:15, where one of the granulators produces a peculiar ticking sound, probably due to its record mechanism having successfully caught the attack of a bowed harmonic.

I find the time span between 04:57 and 06:40 to be a high point of the performance. The interaction between myself, the double bass, and the signal processing here increases in activity, converging on mutually enabling explorations of discrete timbral structures in the acoustic as well as the digital domain. One example is the overtly dramatic build-up emerging in the digital domain at 06:20. Here, a repetitive and pulsating pattern, increasing in volume and at 06:34 suddenly changing pace, is followed by the bowing of two upper-harmonic dyads. This acoustic event is immediately followed by another increase in pace on the part of the algorithm, signalling the culmination of this section. During the almost two minutes this section lasts, it becomes increasingly clear how the signal processing, through the operationally closed and deterministic processes of control signal feedback, is able to generate semi-autonomous and musically viable responses to events in its acoustic environment.

With the culmination of the previous section, the bass playing reverts to the spiccato technique of the beginning of the piece, this time applied to upper harmonics of the 1st, 2nd and 3rd string. With the cessation of the bass playing between 07:42 and 08:19, one is better able to appreciate the development of the signal processing across all four granulators, once again suggesting that, had the performance been longer, much more patience could have been exhibited on the part of the performer in letting the algorithm run its course.

From 07:42, the 4 read pointers’ slow advances through their respective buffers become more pronounced, as do some of the artefacts introduced by the processing. One such example is the emergence at 07:58 and 08:11 of a 700 Hz frequency that, although approximately available as a harmonic with the ratio of 7/4 relative to the open 1st string (77/96 relative to the fundamental A=440Hz), does not appear to have been played in the time leading up to its manifestation. This suggests that the frequency is a product of the granulation itself, possibly a compound artefact of the playback speed and grain triggering frequency. Lacking a strong

¹⁰ I will discuss anthropocentric notions of error and failure in chapter 5.

sensation of relative pitch, I am therefore pleasantly surprised that I do manage to target the frequency by playing the 7/4 harmonic on the 1st string at 08:19.

Another emergent artefact occurs at 08:54, as one of the granulators produces a sudden downward frequency ramp, sounding as if the grain triggering rate is being strongly modulated—a phenomenon reoccurring to a less pronounced extent at 09:24.

Whether this last change of pace is caused by my preceding bowing action, or is an emergent property of the algorithmic design, is difficult to tell. Rather than suggesting that this makes it difficult to gauge whether the machine can improvise or not, it is worth pointing out, that the same uncertainty as to cause and effect applies to many human actions. The two dyads I am bowing just before the culmination are equally difficult to assign to any preceding cause, even if there is a certain temporal proximity to the algorithmic change of pace at 06:34. As I have suggested earlier, improvisation, rather than being an immanent property of any given system or organism, is a relational and emergent phenomenon. As such, it is tempting to revise our understanding of the notion of "improvising machines", and even improvisation as a human capability, and instead focus on ecologies that afford improvisation, whether those ecologies comprise humans or not. Additionally, I want to question whether the notion of cause and effect, or call and response, is the most valuable tool for understanding improvisation as it manifests in a performance such as *attics*, where it is the long-term development of timbre that defines the work.

3.3 Conclusion

I have here described two performances, both of which utilise feedback mechanisms in conjunction with a double bass. While the feedback manifests in different domains (mechanical and control signals, respectively), the tactile interface of *Frog*, along with its (albeit limited) semi-autonomous behaviour, and the control feedback of *attics*, shows how the emergence of feedback in mediums beyond air has the potential to alter, augment, extend, and fundamentally change the way we interact with an acoustic instrument such as the double bass.

Significantly, the works described here in various ways retain what I, coming from a background in acoustic performance, perceive as salient qualities pertaining to playing the double bass. On a sonic level, the emergence of complex, ambiguous, and sometimes morphologically nonlinear timbres invite extended exploration, not dissimilar to how I approach acoustic bass playing. On the level of execution, the diminished sense of control I experience with these systems—in particular in *attics*—similarly affords an approach of listening and improvising with which I am familiar from playing a resistant double bass.

However, with *Frog* and *attics*, this resistance has been partially decoupled from my own agency as a performer actuating and sustaining the output of an instrument. The varying degrees of autonomy of these two systems offer new modes of interaction, where causal and nonlinear digital and mechanical feedback processes assume partial control over the creation of the work. What becomes apparent is, that with these new modes of interaction, the performer needs to relinquish certain ambitions that will likely have built up over their training and career.

Chapter 4

The FAAB

4.1 Introduction

In 2018, I met Halldór Úlfarsson—the inventor of the halldorophone mentioned in [2.5.1](#). Having already collaborated with Alice Eldridge and Chris Kiefer (2017) on the creation of two feedback cellos, Halldór suggested that we build a feedback bass by applying the principle of electro-mechanical string actuation.

Funded by an *Opstart* grant from the Nordic Culture Fund (2019), we met in Halldór’s workspace in Athens in April and June 2019. Here, we fitted a 600 Euro plywood bass with electromagnetic pickups, a Bela microprocessor, amplifier, and inserted an eight-inch speaker in the lower back of the instrument.

Figure 4.1 Halldór Úlfarsson preparing installation of the FAAB’s speaker, April 2019

In January 2020, after playing the instrument for 6 months, I decided to name it *FAAB*—an abbreviation of *feedback-actuated augmented bass*. As discussed in 2.6.1, augmentation is a redundant term. Yet, at the expense of rigour I chose a name, the abbreviation of which suggests that the instrument is fabulous, which, to me, it indeed is.

While I have developed the FAAB on my own since it left Halldór’s workshop in the summer of 2019, his influence on the instrument is defining and continues through occasional meetings and inspiring email conversations.

Figure 4.2 Installing electronics on the FAAB, April 2019

4.2 Technical Setup of the FAAB

The current second-generation FAAB is a carved German double bass from the 1970s and acoustically an upgrade from the earlier plywood instrument¹.

A Bela (2022c) microprocessor is suspended from the back of the fingerboard with Velcro (image 4.3). The pickup-brace, as well as the control panel hosting sliders and knobs used for interfacing with the Bela are designed and 3D-printed by Halldór (image 4.4).

4.2.1 Pickups

The FAAB sports four electromagnetic *Nu* pickups from Cycfi Research (2022). The pickup brace described above is placed underneath the strings at the bottom end of the fingerboard.

¹ Double bassist and luthier Derek Shirley cut the speaker hole for the current FAAB.

While the Nu pickups are fairly quiet, the high gain structure of the amplification does introduce some noise. I am using a digital adaptive moving average filter² designed by the creator of the Nu pickups, Joel de Guzman (2021). Placed at the input of the DSP chain, the filter only takes effect when the string amplitude drops below -37 dB, significantly reducing the audible presence of noise at lower amplitude levels.

Figure 4.3 Bela and pickups

4.2.2 Strings

The strings of the FAAB need to be ferromagnetic for their vibrations to become detected by the electromagnetic pickups.

Having previously used Thomastik Spirocore (n.d.) medium tension strings, I initially found that they were too stiff for affording fast build-up of string oscillations. Between the autumn of 2020 and March 2023 I used Pirastro Flexocore Deluxe (2022), which are designed mainly for arco playing and are softer and thinner than the Spirocores. However, in March 2023 I switched back to the Spirocores and currently feel more comfortable playing these, as they seem to start self-oscillation at lower volumes and are generally acoustically louder. While the physical constitution of strings is a determining factor in how the FAAB

² See <https://github.com/Adampultz/pultzLib/blob/main/Demos/Full%20render.cpp>.

operates, the findings here are inconclusive and suffer from the fact that the initial change from Spirocore to Flexocore Deluxe coincided with a change in amplifier and speaker. Additionally, as any string player will know, the choice of strings to an extent depends on the particular physical constitution and setup of the instrument being played.

4.2.3 Microprocessor

Latency

The pickup signal is sent to a Bela microprocessor sporting a CTAG FACE cape (2022a) that expands the Bela's audio inputs and outputs to 4 and 8, respectively. The CTAG affords a sample rate of 48000 and a bit-depth of 16. Specifically designed for audio purposes, the Bela board, in comparison to a laptop with an audio interface, has a very low hardware latency of about 58 samples, or 1.2 milliseconds (ms)³. To this latency, we need to add a latency of twice the software buffer size. At 16 samples, this gives us a round-trip of 90 samples or 1.875 ms, which falls to 74 samples, or 1.154 ms, if buffer size is lowered to 8 samples. The algorithms described below will operate synchronously at a buffer size of 8, although a size of 16 seems to afford a little more stability in terms of avoiding audio dropouts. McPherson et al. (2016) note that latencies in digital instruments above 10 ms are perceived to compromise the "feel" of the instrument (p. 20). While this property may be less critical in drone musics or other types of music not relying on immediate haptic or auditory responses, low latency is essential to my own practice, coming from a background in acoustic instrument performance. Additionally, a digital feedback system coupled with an acoustic instrument technically constitutes a comb filter. The latency of the system defines the delay time, which, in combination with the feedback, introduces a resonant frequency equal to the reciprocal of the delay. As such, by decreasing latency, the resonant frequency gets pushed higher and—in the case of the FAAB—further away from the domain of interaction. With these two considerations in mind, in addition to constituting a low-power and visually unobtrusive source of DSP, for performance with a feedback string instrument such as the FAAB, the Bela represents a highly suited alternative to a laptop.

Audio outputs

Currently, only five of the CTAG's eight audio outputs are used. A mono signal consisting of the summed processed output of all four strings is sent to the amplifier. The processed

³ See McPherson (2020b) for a tutorial on latency on the Bela. For CTAG FACE-specific measurements, see apeiro (2022).

output of the four strings is accessible by two stereo mini jack plugs, used for spatialisation and additional signal processing on a laptop.

Control panel

The Bela has eight analogue inputs, of which four are currently reserved for individual string gain control (sliders). The latter four (dials) control the balance between each algorithm and the dry signal (as only three algorithms are currently in use, the eighth input is unused).

Gain sliders are generally set at maximum, but are useful for adjusting gain relationships, for example when aiming for creating beat-frequencies between individual strings. The dials used for wet/dry mix of algorithms are usually left in place once a balance has been found.

Figure 4.4 Control panel

4.2.4 Volume Pedal

Before routing the mono output of the Bela to the amplifier, it is routed through a volume pedal. I am currently using a Lehle (2022) Mono volume pedal. This pedal operates silently and affords a gain boost of up to 10 dB, which can be useful for raising the signal volume before sending it to the amplifier.

While I infrequently adjust the gain controls for individual strings, being able to dynamically control master volume is essential in performing with the FAAB.

4.2.5 Amplifier

An S.M.S.L SA-98E amplifier (n.d[b]) receives the signal from the volume pedal. This is a stereo amplifier with 160 watts per channel, providing the necessary power and headroom for causing string self-oscillation. On newer feedback basses from Úlfarsson's workshop, bespoke preamps, amplifier, and power supply designed by Orfeas Moraitis have contributed to a better signal-to-noise ratio than what is currently possible on the FAAB.

4.2.6 Speaker

Adding weight to the instrument not only compromises its acoustic integrity by dampening vibrations, but also makes travelling more problematic. Neodymium-magnet speakers are therefore preferred. I am currently using an Eighteensound 8NMB420 8-inch speaker (2022), chosen for its weight of 1.7 Kilo and frequency range of 60-5500 Hz. The speaker is fitted on a plywood ring glued to the perimeter of the hole cut in the lower right corner of the back of the instrument.

Figure 4.5 Speaker placement

4.3 Software

During initial work with the FAAB I ran SuperCollider on the Bela. Since March 2021, I have used C++, which is the native programming environment on the board. While somewhat more complex than SuperCollider and other high-level languages, C++ gives easy access to the sample domain, and additionally affords the use of fast, approximated mathematical operations (Bela 2022b).

4.3.1 *pultzLib*: A C++ library for signal processing on the FAAB

The creative and theoretical work undertaken for this thesis is accompanied by the creation of *pultzLib*—a C++ library of CPU-efficient algorithms optimised for the Bela and the FAAB. Of these algorithms, some, such as filters and mathematical operators, are trivial, while others are specifically customised to run on the FAAB. Others still consist of novel signal processing operations developed specifically for this instrument, three of which will be discussed shortly. Of the latter, most would require some parameter customisation to be useful on other instruments. The current study is concerned with the development of personal, and sometimes idiosyncratic, approaches, and therefore not intended to evaluate individual algorithms through their general applicability. *pultzLib* is available at <https://github.com/Adampultz/pultzLib> and <https://zenodo.org/record/7924995#.ZFz7t3ZBzRI>.

4.4 Feedback on the FAAB and transduction in self-resonating vibrotactile feedback instruments

The FAAB is part of the family of SRIs (self-resonating vibrotactile feedback instruments) described by Eldridge, Overholt and Kiefer and mentioned in 2.5.1. Eldridge et al.'s (2021) definition of an SRI is quoted in full:

1. A feedback loop is created between a pick-up and an electro-mechanical actuator via resonant material(s) (e.g. strings, membranes etc.) causing self-resonation. This is the primary sound producing mechanism; the properties of the resonant materials colour the vibrations, influencing the resultant acoustic properties of the instrument.
2. The self-resonating system is intimately sensitive to physical interaction by the player, creating the potential for vibrotactile interfaces through which the musician can influence the behaviour of the instrument. (pp. 6–7)

The subset of SRIs that are of particular interest to this study, and of which the FAAB is one, number the halldorophone, Eldridge and Kiefer's (2017) feedback cellos, as well as the feedback basses currently coming out of Úlfarsson's workshop. All of these employ mechanical couplings between speakers, solids, and transducers, but embody transduction through other mediums as well. Since the transduction of SRIs is essential to a proper understanding of these instruments, it is worthwhile to proceed by tracing out the minimal conditions for their operation. The halldorophone, being an acoustically fairly inert example of an SRI and often featuring an entirely analogue signal chain, constitutes a good case-study for exploring such conditions: like the FAAB, the halldorophone comprises a speaker inserted into the lower back of the instrument body. The speaker vibrates the body, which in turn actuates the bridge and hence the strings. In contrast to the largely electro-mechanical loop of Brandtsegg's instrument or the *Frog*, the oscillations of the halldorophone strings are not mechanically transferred to a piezo pickup. Rather, they are registered by electromagnetic pickups, the signals of which are turned into an electric current sent to an amplifier feeding the speaker (for in-depth discussions of the halldorophone, see Úlfarsson (2018, 2019)). In addition to the mechanical transduction of the body, in Eldridge and Kiefer's cellos, in the FAAB, and to some extent in the halldorophone, the vibration of the back plate of the instrument produces air-pressure waves inside the instrument body, actuating the top plate, which in turn produces air pressure waves travelling in the opposite direction. As such, open-air feedback does play a role in these instruments, although to a lesser extent than feedback systems such as those employed in Nicolas Collins' *Pea Soup* or Agostino Di Scipio's (2011) *Background Noise Study*.

By applying the system-environment cut enacted by Di Scipio and Sanfilippo to the FAAB, (that is, by defining the environment as situated between microphone and speaker), we encounter that the environment of the FAAB corresponds to the acoustic double bass itself. However, while the open-air feedback architecture is defined by a signal propagating through an environment of direct, reflected, diffracted, and dampened air pressure waves, as discussed above, the environment of the FAAB comprises heterogeneous materials and shapes, each of which transduces the audio signal in a particular fashion. Significantly, while input and output in the open-air architecture share air as the transductive medium, in the case of the FAAB, the output corresponds to the mechanical vibration of the speaker and the wooden back plate, while the input comprises the vibrations of ferro-magnetic steel strings.

Figures 4.6 and 4.7 illustrate the differences in transduction between a generic open-air system and, representing an SRI, the FAAB. In order to focus on acoustic transduction, specifics pertaining to signal processing architectures and hardware have been omitted (a

diagram of the FAAB including both of these is available in figure 4.8). Arrows representing different kinds of transduction are colour-coded as follows:

- Red = mechanical vibration
- Yellow = air pressure
- Orange = electromagnetism
- Cyan = voltage
- Black = digital signals

Figure 4.6 Transduction in open-air feedback systems

Figure 4.7 Transduction on the FAAB

In conclusion, mechanical and to a lesser extent air pressure feedback characterises the operation of the FAAB, while electromagnetic transduction plays a part in the feedback loop. The acknowledgement that no single process governs the operation of this SRI will have an impact on the discussion of its design and performance.

4.5 Digital signal processing on the FAAB

In initial conversations around the design of the FAAB, Úlfarsson and I agreed that a particularly interesting avenue of exploration would be the implementation of signal processing. Having already been explored and described by a number of feedback artists working in the open-air domain, notably Di Scipio and Sanfilippo, signal processing on instruments such as the SRIs developing around Úlfarsson's work has mainly been implemented and discussed by Eldridge and Kiefer (2017). Their research is substantiated by an extended performance practice. In addition to exploring the implementation of both adaptive algorithms (Kiefer 2017) and machine learning (Eldridge and Kiefer 2021), their work has accentuated the new possibilities emerging from the difference in both design and performance practice between SRIs and other feedback instruments and systems. While suggesting the existence of several yet under- and un-explored avenues of research and creative practices pertaining to the digital processing of string feedback signals, a particularly interesting aspect of these explorations is the fashion in which the digital and material domains integrate with, and modulate, each other.

An additional concern applies to the aesthetics of the performance situation: in section 2.3.6 I discussed mapping as a valuable term for describing the relationship between, say, the double bass bow, the string, and the production of sound. Discussing the work of Tom Mudd, the nonlinearity of such relationships emerged as valuable models for creating mappings in digital instrument design, for example by applying complex transfer functions to the values mapped between a MIDI controller and a synthesis engine. In the case of the FAAB, comprising both physical-acoustic and digital domains, physics do not require modelling, as they are available through my interaction with the acoustic instrument itself (although a particular interesting area of exploration is the integration of acoustic instruments with digital physical modelling conducted at SARC, Queen's University Belfast (Stapleton et al. 2018)). Here, I will draw upon Impett's discussion of environmentally and performatively situated processes (2.9.1), Di Scipio's Audible Ecosystemics model in which, with Di Scipio's own words, *sound is the interface* (Di Scipio 2003), and expand upon my own works, such as *Frog* and *attics*. My thesis is that complex DSP behaviour can be derived from, on the one hand, interactions between performer and instrument, and on the other, processes immanent to the DSP domain itself. This would set the performer free to engage with the instrument according to an already established performance practice, while deriving a diversity of control signals that do not directly correspond to the gesture of the performer, but rather to the sounds produced through the interaction with the instrument. As such, not only sound, but the instrument itself, becomes an interface. This is not an alien concept to a musician playing an acoustic instrument. Yet, in contrast to most MIDI controllers it offers an expanded

domain of gestural interaction, that, while possibly being less predictable in control, affords new modes of interaction. This, then, would require the establishment of new skill sets and approaches to performance that respond to the altered relationship between performer, acoustic instrument, and digital processes that are immanent as well as situated.

4.5.1 Time-domain signal processing

Like the approaches discussed in *Frog* and *attics*, for the generation of control signals for DSP variables on the FAAB, I rely on audio feature descriptors. With the two previous works having been realised using a laptop computer, CPU usage have posed little consideration, even when running several FFT-based audio descriptors at once. This is not the case with four-channel processing on the Bela board. Consequently, I rely exclusively on time-domain processes for audio feature analysis and signal processing. As demonstrated by Di Scipio (2022), even mappings exclusively relying on a descriptor as simple as RMS can yield highly complex and emergent behaviours within a feedback system. Additionally, Sanfilippo (2019, p. 74) has convincingly demonstrated how computationally cheap time-domain alternatives to frequency-domain analysis can yield reliable higher-order audio descriptors.

4.5.2 Overview of signal transmission and transduction on the FAAB

To conclude this overview of the design architecture of the FAAB, figure 4.8 expands on figure 4.7 by including the DSP architecture of the Bela (represented by the grey box), the amplifier, as well as the control panel and volume pedal. Additionally introducing the performer necessitates the addition of a fuchsia-coloured arrow to represent the manual operation of control panel and volume pedal. The player has been placed within the environment according to the definition in section 4.4 of the environment as sitting between speaker and pickups. While the figure goes to some length to trace the increasing complexity of signal transduction, an increase in granularity would reveal new details, such as if one were to examine the relationship of the speaker to the back plate or the subtleties of the signal processing architecture (which will feature in the following sections).

Figure 4.8 Comprehensive overview of signal transmission and transduction on the FAAB

4.6 Three performances

Below follows a discussion of three performances. Each performance evolved in conjunction with the development of a FAAB-specific DSP algorithm. Consequently, a detailed description of each of the latter is followed by an analysis and discussion of its operation in the context of the former. These algorithms are not to be seen as general-purpose tools, or substrate-independent entities that can be realised with any given input or material configuration (although, with modifications, they may be applicable to other material ecologies). Even considering them as fulfilling specific purposes is compromised by the fact that they evolved in a reciprocal relationship with an often daily instrumental practice, combined

with several performances. In this sense, the development of algorithms and performance practices follows a nonlinear trajectory of, what Lucy Suchman (2006) describes as, *situated actions*: in contrast to predefined plans, the term situated action ‘underscores the view that every course of action depends in essential ways on its material and social circumstances’ (p. 70). In the same sense that situated actions may provide the basis for formulating plans (ibid., p. 184), the DSP objectives on the FAAB have been generally underspecified in the early stages of design. Although achieving a certain sense of design stability as they mature, like the processual nature of instruments discussed in section 2.6.1, these algorithms are in a state of continuous evaluation and development through their intimate relation to an ongoing performance practice. As such, the design of each algorithm was initially triggered by intuition, either led by a conceptual idea or an accidental timbral discovery which, when implemented as a working prototype, would often generate unexpected behaviour that became the guiding principle for further explorations. I will propose that the algorithms, embedded as they are in a material and performative ecology, are to be understood in terms of a leaky and fuzzy logic that cause them to transcend their digital realm. On a temporally finite and local basis, algorithmic design, the materiality of the microprocessor, the acoustic instrument, and performance all become boundary-making practices that enact and become enacted through agential cuts. As such, when I talk about how an algorithm behaves, I am observing a global systemic behaviour informed, but not determined, by that algorithm. For a more detailed discussion of the entanglement of performance, materiality, and algorithms in post-digital ecologies, I will refer to Stapleton et al. (2022) and Stapleton and Bowers (2022).

The current digital infrastructure of the FAAB includes all three algorithms and is available as part of pultzLib here: <https://github.com/Adampultz/pultzLib/tree/main/Demos/Full%20>.

4.7 Amplitude Sync

An initial version of this algorithm was described in Úlfarsson and Melbye (2020, p. 224), yet the following description presents a complete rework of the algorithm, featuring significant improvements. The C++ code for the Sync algorithm is part of pultzLib and available here: <https://github.com/Adampultz/pultzLib/tree/main/Amplitude%20Sync>. A render.cpp file for running the Sync algorithm on its own on the Bela is available here: <https://github.com/Adampultz/pultzLib/tree/main/Demos/Amplitude%20Sync>.

In his book *Sync: The Emerging Science of Spontaneous Order*, the mathematician Steven Strogatz (2003) explores the phenomenon of synchronisation, that ‘pervades nature at every

scale from the nucleus to the cosmos' (p. 1). The in-step flickering of fireflies, synchronised firing of neurons in the brain, or the phase-locking of two grandfather clock pendulums may appear difficult to imagine without a centralised control mechanism. Yet, as Strogatz explains, these phenomena are self-organizing properties of nature, the behaviours of which can often be mathematically modelled as oscillators. These oscillators, rather than responding to a central master oscillator, or clock, are coupled; that is, their phase, amplitude, or both, tend to synchronise to each other. In most cases this coupling is local, with each individual in an array of oscillators synchronising to its immediate neighbours, while some systems exhibit couplings across all oscillators (*ibid.*, p. 171).

While reading Strogatz' book, I was grappling with the problem of single-string feedback dominance on the FAAB. As discussed in section 3.1.2 audio feedback tends toward strong attractors. On the FAAB, these attractors are often defined by the dominance of one string over the others, to the extent that feedback build-up on any given string tends to exclude the self-oscillation of the three other strings. In an attempt to address this phenomenon, I conceived of a simple system consisting of an oscillator A_k , with $k(mod4)$ corresponding to the string index. The frequency f_k of A_k is equal to the difference between the amplitude of string x_k and the mean amplitude of its two neighbouring strings, x_{k-1} and x_{k+1} .

$$f_k = \frac{1}{2}(x_{k-1} + x_{k+1}) - x_k \quad (4.1)$$

As such, x_0 will be considered a neighbour of x_3 (this definition will be applied throughout the section). While this is not spatially the case, frequency-wise, if we observe octave-equivalency, for open strings, the proximity of the 1st to the 4th string (61/276) will be greater than the proximity of the 1st to the 2nd string (154/552).

For amplitude detection, both RMS and envelope following have been tried, with the choice falling on the latter. With attack and release times decoupled, the envelope follower, through an attack time of 0.01 second, affords the quick tracking of—and hence adaption to—amplitude increases. A slower release of 0.15 results in a musically pleasing tapering off of string gain.

Before measuring the amplitude differences, the amplitude of individual strings is scaled to the decibel range and linearly scaled back into the range of 0 – 1. This serves the purpose of creating a greater sensitivity to small amplitude differences through a logarithmic distribution. Additionally, by restraining the decibel values to between -45 or -50 (depending on the string) to -5 it allows for the omission of extreme amplitude values rarely occurring in the signal, affording the full use of the range of 0 – 1. In order to avoid the computational load imposed

by the decibel calculation, a linearly interpolated lookup-table from Joel de Guzman's (2022) Q library is used.

With equation 4.1 we get a positive value if the mean amplitude of x_{k-1} and x_{k+1} is larger than x_k , and a negative value in the opposite case. This value can be used to index a wavetable oscillator w , the speed and direction of the indexing corresponding to the magnitude, and the sign, respectively, of the amplitude difference. Amplitude differences, only in the most extreme cases, tend toward values of -1 or 1. Consequently, in most cases, the indexing of w will be slow. Different waveforms have been tried, with the choice falling on a sinusoid.

To avoid the oscillator outputting negative amplitude values (which would amount to a polarity shift of the modulated signal), its output is scaled within the range of 0 - 1.

$$A[n] = \frac{1}{2}w[n * f * w_{size} * f_s] + 0.5 \quad (4.2)$$

where n corresponds to the sample index, f to equation 4.1, w_{size} the size of the wavetable, and f_s the sampling frequency.

For any string k , this gives us an output z_k defined as

$$z_k = s_k * A_k \quad (4.3)$$

with s being the sampled input of the string, and A corresponding to equation 4.2.

With the previous description, we can see how the oscillator A is able to accelerate or decelerate its search through the space of possibilities for attenuation or amplification of the input, depending on the level of amplitude discrepancy between string k and its neighbours. This feature constitutes a simple adaptive mechanism that is consistent with the notion that a larger discrepancy between goal-state (amplitude equivalence across strings) and actual state, requires an active search for a solution, while smaller discrepancies are better addressed by a slow adjustment.

Indexing into a continuous waveform, such as a sinusoid, however, poses a problem when relying on both positive and negative indexing values. We have already discussed that

$$sgn(f_k) = \begin{cases} -1, & \text{if } x_k > \frac{1}{2}(x_{k-1} + x_{k+1}) \\ 1, & \text{if } x_k < \frac{1}{2}(x_{k-1} + x_{k+1}) \end{cases} \quad (4.4)$$

That is, if string k is louder than the mean amplitude of its neighbours, the frequency value assigned to A will be negative, and vice versa. This, however, only applies in the first

and third quadrant of the sinusoid's unit circle. In the second and third quadrant, applying a negative index value will cause an *increase* in the output of A .

A solution is to continuously check the sign of the oscillator output against the oscillator frequency to obtain a sign-corrected frequency f_{corr} , here expressed as a conditional statement:

$$f_{corr}[n] = \begin{cases} -f[n], & \text{if } \text{sgn}(A_k[n] - A_k[n-1]) \neq \text{sgn}(f[n]) \\ f[n], & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4.5)$$

Figure 4.9 Sync algorithm: Amplitude difference oscilloscope visualisation.

Brown = 1st string, blue = 2nd string, green = 3rd string, red = 4th string.

Screenshot from video available at <https://vimeo.com/752672047/88cf23818e>

4.7.1 Complex behaviour

Real physical systems rarely obey the simplified models we construct in order to understand the world. The complexity of dynamical systems in general makes it difficult to project their long-term evolution. In the case of the FAAB, even though string k could theoretically end up synchronising its gain to match the amplitude of its two neighbours, $k-1$ and $k+1$, the fact that each of these attempt to synchronise *their* own gain to the mean amplitude of k and $k+2$, and k and $k-2$, respectively, means that any long-term stability is difficult to achieve. On the level of the individual strings, the high energy driving the feedback creates a phase-space

with a large amplitudal axis along which the behaviour of the instrument, rather than scaling linearly, may be drawn to a number of resonant attractors. By stopping the string at various points along the fingerboard, the string's vibrating length and angle is changed, which, in combination with the body's resonant frequencies, even in the absence of amplification, has significant impact. However, the Sync algorithm is only concerned with differences between very specific nodes in the system, that is, disturbances in the electromagnetic fields created by the ferromagnetic strings oscillating near the pickups. As such, only by proxy does the algorithm consider other important physical properties, such as the vibration of the back plate or the position of the left hand on the fingerboard. Consequently, George Lewis' call for the improvising machine to have a sufficient representation of its environment is not satisfied at this stage of development.

4.7.2 Long, and short-term behaviours

From a performative point of view, an even more important question is the extent to which long-term synchronisation should be our primary concern. In section 3.1.3 I discussed the criticism of Ross Ashby's Homeostat, the behaviour of which, although a landmark cybernetic engineering feat, could suggest that the goal of adaptive systems is homeostasis. Rather, I will argue that in complex systems, parts of the system may be required to retain homeostasis in order that other parts can do interesting stuff. The reason we have thermostats on heaters is not to keep our houses warm in the absence of dwellers. Rather, I need to keep warm so that I can play the FAAB, meditate, write my PhD thesis, and all sorts of other fun and engaging things. At the same time, it is important to acknowledge that the FAAB is not a thermostat designed to supply the optimal playing conditions for the player, but rather a system that can potentially do interesting stuff on its own, as well as in collaboration with a performer. In other words, it should fulfil the conditions for interactive behaviour outlined by Di Scipio. While counteracting the somewhat tedious sound of single-string feedback, through the development of, and performance with, the Sync algorithm, it becomes clear that amplitude homeostasis may be but one of several goals of the algorithm.

4.7.3 Listening bias

The above discussion suggests that the algorithm could be improved by mechanisms that account for the nonlinearity of the amplitude response as well as the material idiosyncrasies of the instrument. Furthermore, it suggests that the initial goal of amplitude synchronisation need not lie in the long-term domain exclusively. Rather, we can conceive of synchronisation as being a dynamical and metastable property of the system, responding to the performer,

as well as suggesting its own behaviour. Consequently, I have chosen to raise the bar for the system's short-term behaviour and long-term adaptability by applying a set of evolving biases to the amplitudes against which each string measures itself. In this case, equation 4.1 becomes

$$y_k = \frac{1}{2}((x_{k-1} * \alpha[k * 2]) + (x_{k+1} * \alpha[k * 2 + 1])) - x_k \quad (4.6)$$

where α is an array of 8 values, currently limited to the range between 0.2 and 1.2. These values are effectively listening biases, scaling the amplitude at which any given string perceives its neighbouring strings. While it may at first seem counterproductive to compromise the conditions for amplitude synchronisation and adaption, a discussion of how such biases may evolve during performance presents a case for increasing behavioural variety, and consequently, long-term adaption.

4.7.4 Evolution and adaption

If, for a given period, we calculate the mean amplitude of each string, we can proceed with measuring the absolute amplitude deviation l , of a given string from each of its neighbours,

$$l = (|x_{k-1} - x_k|) + (|x_{k+1} - x_k|) \quad (4.7)$$

in addition to the absolute deviation e of a single string from the mean amplitude of all four strings:

$$e = \left| \frac{\sum_{k=0}^3 x_k}{4} - x_k \right| \quad (4.8)$$

Equations 4.7 and 4.8 can be conceived of as *fitness functions*, describing the successes l and e by which a single string is able to adapt to its closest neighbours and its environment, respectively. By summing l and e , we get a value weighted toward l by a factor of 2/3, since it represents a summation of two values. This bias seems reasonable, considering that l also represents the main objective of the Sync algorithm, with synchronisation across all four strings being an implied objective.

A fitness function describes the evolutionary success of an individual relative to a population. It is a fundamental feature of *Evolutionary Algorithms* (EA)—an evolutionary approach to algorithmic design first explored by John H. Holland in the 1960s (Holland 2014, 1992), and further developed in the 1980s and 90s by Christopher Langton (1997) and others working in the field of Artificial Life. EAs are often used to evolve systems or parts of systems, by iterating through numerous generations of ideally increasingly efficient designs.

Evolutionary algorithms are closely related to *ALife* practices. A discussion of some of the many approaches to *ALife* in the arts is found in Eldridge and Bown (2018), with the work of Jon McCormack (2009) being of particular interest in the context of this study. Similar to McCormack's (2001) multimedia installation *Eden*, the evolutionary process taking place in the Sync algorithm happens during performance run-time, in contrast to *MutaSynth* and *Synthbot*, two EAs discussed by Eldridge and Bown (2018, p. 10), that are primarily used for pre-performance processes.

Before proceeding, it may be useful to quote Holland's (2014) succinct definition of the process :

1. Start with a population of N individual strings of alleles (perhaps generated at random).
2. Select two individuals at random from the current population, biasing toward individuals with higher fitness.
3. Use genetic operators (such as mutation and crossover described below) to produce two new individuals, which are assigned to the next generation.
4. Repeat steps 1 and 2 $N/2$ times to produce a new generation of N individuals.
5. Return to steps 1 to produce the next generation. (p. 68)

EAs operate on a population of individual strings of bits, and sometimes, symbols. In the case of the Sync algorithm, since each individual bias (eight in total, two per bass string⁴) is a floating-point number, it can be expressed as a binary string of 32 bits, comprising a population of eight individual chromosomes, each with 32 alleles, upon which the rules of manipulations stipulated by Holland can be applied.

In the present case—evolving biases for a synchronisation algorithm—the fitness function has already been defined as a function of measuring the amplitude difference between strings.

4.7.5 Generation lifespan

As the evolution of the listening biases is occurring as the performance proceeds, and with recombination and mutation happening once every generation, we have left to determine what the life span of each generation can be. Two concerns emerge here:

1. In order for the algorithm to generate enough data for its fitness function to be properly evaluated, a generation cannot be too short.

⁴ In order to avoid confusion, in the following I will differentiate between bass string and binary string.

2. The algorithm will need to iterate over a minimum number of generations to properly evolve its listening biases.

In early stages of development, the lifespan of a generation was fixed at 30 seconds. To introduce some variation between the lifespan of individual generations, a third fitness function has been introduced, using a variance measure to determine the overall synchronisation of all four strings over the course of a generation:

$$v = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^3 \left(x_k - \frac{\sum_{n=0}^3 x_n}{4} \right)^2 \quad (4.9)$$

where x_k and x_n represent the amplitude of individual strings.

Since what we are really doing when trying to synchronise string amplitude is to minimise amplitude differences, equations such as 4.9 are convenient for getting an impression of how close to the target the system is overall.

For every new generation, the variance of the past generation is mapped inversely to a life span of 10 to 30 seconds, effectively meaning that the more heterogeneous the amplitude of one generation is, the quicker new generations will be spawned, accelerating the search for more optimal conditions through genetic recombination and mutation. In real life, of course, rather than creating homogeneity, evolution results in diversity, with heterogeneity being a precondition of health on both a biological, ecosystemic, societal, and interpersonal level.

In the original SuperCollider code, a mechanism was introduced to confer some agency unto the current generation: upon reaching the last tenth of a lifespan, the variance of the current generation was monitored, and, if crossing a certain threshold, would trigger the immediate creation of a new generation. This mechanism has yet to be implemented in the current C++ code.

The remaining part of the EA is known territory: binary strings are chosen from a random search biased towards those individuals with a higher fitness, while crossover is used to divide and recombine strings. Mutation happens with a probability of one over the number of genes, that is, statistically once for every genesis.

4.7.6 We're running out of Sand — A case-study in performance with the Sync algorithm

The development of the Sync algorithm was begun in December 2019 and is still ongoing, although the major features had been settled and implemented by November 2021.

While the algorithm was initially intended to produce stable feedback across all strings, its current main application is to create self-organizing, yet metastable behaviour, able to operate and evolve autonomously, as well as through interaction with a performer.

In contrast to the C++ algorithm discussed above, early versions of the algorithm were implemented in SuperCollider and contained two programming flaws, in addition to a modified triangular, rather than sinusoidal oscillator. Since the current study is concerned with the development of—in addition to performance with—the FAAB, the fact that the behaviour of the current algorithm is not fundamentally different from the one used in the performance discussed here, and that I perceive the music realised with this early algorithm appealing, I will refer to [Appendix D](#) for an overview and discussion of the difference between the two.

We're running out of Sand (henceforth *Sand*)—is a pre-recorded performance submitted for *Sonic Practice Now*—a festival organized by the Irish Sound, Science, and Technology Association (ISSTA)—and streamed on August 14th, 2020. The audio of the performance was later released online by the *Stolen Mirror* label as part of a compilation celebrating the festival (Melbye 2021b). A video of the performance is available from <https://vimeo.com/447257162>.

Figure 4.10 *We're running out of Sand*, screenshot

Sand begins with the slow, repeated bowing of a dyad—the 2nd harmonic on the 3rd string ($23/16$, an E-flat 28 cent sharp) and the third harmonic on the 2nd string ($2/3$, a D 2 cent flat), respectively (see [Appendix C](#) for a discussion of tuning). I then introduce a plucked open 1st string ($11/12$, a G about 50 cent sharp), and shortly thereafter, the bowed 4th harmonic on the 3rd string ($115/96$, a detuned C#). With the volume pedal initially all the way down, I slowly increase the amplification of the system. At low to medium amplification levels, the behaviour of the Sync algorithm manifests as an undulating ghostly resonance, with individual strings fading in and out without ever reaching feedback saturation. Significantly, the tendency of the algorithm is to suppress amplification of any string being activated by the player, instead raising the amplitude of any neighbouring strings currently not being played. This behaviour becomes increasingly apparent from [04:20](#) and onwards, at which point I have introduced the remaining two pitches comprising the main 5-note pitch set of the composition: the bowed 1st harmonic of the 3rd strings ($23/24$, roughly an A-flat) and a stopped detuned B-flat on the 3rd string (approximately $37/42$, not visible on the tuning chart in [Appendix C](#)).

From approximately [05:05](#), the level of amplification is sufficiently high to allow noticeable feedback on open, as well as stopped strings, the latter often requiring more energy for feedback to build up. Additionally, with increased activity from my side, the algorithm's attempts at synchronisation become more apparent. Since synchronisation in the digital domain is not immediate, but rather mediated by the smoothing window of the envelope follower and the modulating oscillator, the frequency of which is in the sub-second range, the algorithm's response to my interference is that of a gradual adjustment with a soft envelope. At higher amplification levels this causes instances of gain overshoot—a feature I find musically pleasing, as it introduces a level of behavioural idiosyncrasy that allows unforeseen events to occur. One such event takes place between [05:10](#) and [5:20](#), where the 1st string seems to get stuck at a high gain level, causing the other strings to follow suit, resulting in overall gain saturation. A perhaps counterintuitive feature of the system is, that should one string drive itself to saturation for extended periods of time, or become uncomfortably loud⁵, one of the most effective countermeasures available to the player is to transfer even more energy into the string by bowing it at its fundamental frequency, causing the increased low-end information of the signal to be tracked as an increase in volume.

The algorithm not only lowers the gain of a string exceeding the mean amplitude of its neighbours, but also increases its gain, should it be softer than its neighbours. One can use this feature creatively to make the system coax the amplification of, say, a stopped pitch, by

⁵ With the term uncomfortable, rather than merely signalling loud audio volume, I am referring to the—after 3 years—still unnerving feeling of the bass entering into a feedback coupling so powerful that I fear for the structural integrity of the instrument itself.

activating its neighbouring strings. An example is found at [04:29](#), where, following a bowing of a dyad, I pluck the 1st string immediately followed by the depression of the 4th string, the gain of which increases as a function of the amplitude increase of the 1st string.

At [05:52](#), as I briefly cease playing, the algorithm adapts by lowering the gain of all four strings, effectively synchronising to silence. Once the algorithm reaches this state, it will have achieved complete synchronisation and has no reason to adjust the gain of any string further. Despite it being a computationally solid and the arguably most stable long-term solution to the task presented to the algorithm, silence is of course not what I intended when conceiving of the code. The sudden amplitude drop provides an interruption to the performative flow, and triggers the creation of a voluminous coda quite different to the initial six minutes of the performance. As brief as this phenomenon is, it constitutes a significant musical as well as conceptual event: firstly, with the sudden interruption of the flow and direction of the performance, the situation becomes precarious, as I am coaxed away from the stable state in which interaction with the FAAB has taken place. However, as uncomfortable as the situation was to me—the performer, when listening back in the role of the perceiver, what ensues is a musically valid turn that seems unlikely to have occurred in the absence of the synchronisation to silence. From [08:28](#), it is clear how the algorithm attempts to sync volume between strings, an undertaking further compromised by the fact that I use both left and right hand to stop a variety of notes across the fingerboard. As discussed in [4.7.1](#), the gain required to make stopped notes at different positions feed back varies, consequently complicating the task of the algorithm, with over, and undershoot as obvious results.

With the acknowledgement of gain over, and undershoot, we may observe an additional reason for the use of an EA to evolve a listening aid for the amplitude tracker: it is now apparent that the environment in which the Sync algorithm is situated is not only comprised of complex and nonlinear string behaviour; the environment changes over time through the interaction of the player. Accordingly, by being able to evaluate and evolve the conditions for its operation, the algorithm becomes able to respond to the changing environment, not only through short-term synchronisation, but also longer-term adaption. This, of course, requires that the environment stays stable for several generations and must be taken into consideration when sculpting a performance, be it composed or freely improvised.

4.7.7 Additional performances using the Sync algorithm and concluding remarks

While Sand was the first work realised from an exploration of the Sync algorithm, the subsequent implementation in C++ described above has formed the basis of extended use in solo performances.

As discussed above, a stable, or slowly evolving environment is a condition for the evolution of listening biases, suggesting the exercise of constrained behaviour on the part of myself. During performance, one such approach has been explored through the initial establishment of four-note pitch sets, the individual pitches of which are slowly changed one by one. Through its volume swells, the algorithm cycles through these pitches in various permutations, “exploring” durations and amplitudes for each pitch. Also previously discussed, the tendency of the algorithm to sync itself to silence affords a certain drama in live performance. When the FAAB suddenly falls quiet, often within the first 3 minutes of a concert due to low master volume, I attempt to retain my posture and not provoke further action from the instrument. Through the vibrations of the instrument body against my own body, I am sometimes able to feel feedback build up before it manifests in the audio domain. Accordingly, I can play on the suspense of nothing audibly happening, while feeling the faint build-up of feedback, the result of which may eventually become audible (see also Melbye (2021a, p. 25)). Yet, at other times, I can only guess as to when, and if, the instrument will start sounding again. The amplitude differences between strings, and hence the frequency of the four oscillators, are rarely zero. As such, one string will often eventually build up enough energy to self-oscillate, a phenomenon which can additionally be encouraged by the left hand through increasing pressure on the string, or even transferring small amounts of energy by instantiating a vibrato. At other times, if the silence persists and I feel the drama of suspense being replaced by tedium, I choose to stimulate a response by gently plucking a harmonic with my right hand. Due to the low overall amplitude of the system, this will often lead to a volume swell on a neighbouring string, at times triggering the other strings to start oscillating.

Once a pitch set has been established and a certain stable synchronisation behaviour has emerged, it often only takes the change of a single pitch to trigger a new state: by changing the vibrating length of any given string, its oscillation—and consequently its amplitudal relationship to its neighbouring strings—is altered. As such, the amplitude oscillation patterns brought about by the Sync algorithm are prone to change in frequency and amplitude across all four strings, even with minute changes in the behaviour of a single string. This allows for the creation of sequences of pitch sets whose internal relationships are reconfigured one pitch at a time, with individual pitches swelling and subsiding in metastable patterns.

A concert from the NRW Forum in Düsseldorf on October 14th, 2021, illustrates some of the behaviours mentioned above. The video is available from: <https://vimeo.com/727162855/0beaedbe28>.

The first four minutes of the performance demonstrate the sensitivity of the system to changes in finger placement, even when operating at a low general volume. A left-hand hammer-on at 02:36 causes the frequency of the oscillator to increase, in turn provoking a general increase in amplitude oscillations across all four strings. Here, we can witness how a single action may cause the system to enter a new and more active state, in which it persists until 3:07. With the introduction of the bow at 03:54, more external energy is supplied to the system, in turn causing the algorithm to raise the frequency of the oscillators to adapt to the amplitude fluctuations caused by my playing.

In addition to the increased responsiveness of the improved algorithm, revisiting this performance, it is clear to me that my familiarity with the FAAB in general, and the Sync algorithm in particular, has developed: although I can not predict the behaviour of the instrument, let alone determine the evolution of the performance, I am able to interact with the amplitude swells through both adaption and coaxing.

The Sync algorithm has been under development longer than any other algorithm designed for the FAAB. Numerous waveforms, amplitude analysis designs, and parameter settings have been explored in order to come up with what feels like a sensitive and semi-autonomous algorithm that affords continuous exploration. It is also in this algorithm, specifically in the EA, that most of the instances of randomisation across the entire FAAB code base are found, namely in the calculation of crossover, selection of individuals (weighted probability), and chance of mutation. With something as simple as slow amplitude modulation, the algorithm exhibits complex emergent behaviour far beyond my initial expectations.

4.8 Waveset time expansion

In section 3.2, I discussed granular time stretch in the context of the piece *attics for all, floors for none*. In this work, I used overlapping grains to ensure signal continuity, with each discrete grain windowed with an amplitude envelope to avoid clicks from the sudden instantiation of high-amplitude waveform discontinuities. Another approach to granulation in general, and time-stretch in particular, is discussed by Trevor Wishart (1994) in his book *Audible Design*. Here, Wishart describes *waveset operations*—a technique by which the period between negative-to-positive zero-crossings in an audio signal are identified and used as the fundamental building blocks for resynthesis.

4.8.1 Zero-crossing analysis

Waveset operations can be approached as a subset of zero-crossing analysis. Where zero-crossing analysis registers both negative-to-positive and positive-to-negative zero-crossings, a waveset corresponds to the full wave cycle between negative-to-positive crossings. Wishart (1994, p. 88) develops a rigorous and fascinating approach to granulation through the description of several waveset transposition techniques, and introduces a method for time-stretching that relies on multiple repetitions of individual wavesets. Writing in 1994, the computational power required by real-time signal processing, such as waveset analysis and playback, was still largely unfeasible on desktop computers. Wishart (*ibid.*, p. 2) explicitly states his purpose to be the discussion of compositional techniques.

Figure 4.11 Waveset analysis of a brief (0.02 seconds) audio sample. Each x identifies the beginning of a waveset, with some being slightly offset from the waveform due to lack of interpolation in the analysis (see discussion of interpolation below in section 4.8.2)

More recently, Dario Sanfilippo has developed real-time zero-crossing techniques, allowing both negative-to-positive transitions and vice versa. Contrary to Wishart's approach that always retains cycles between positive and negative values, Sanfilippo (2019, p. 86) monitors the output of the resynthesis engine to match the next zero-crossing to the transition direction of the former.

Zero-crossing granulation differs from traditional granulation in important ways: firstly, Wishart introduces a differentiation between wavesets and grains by identifying a waveset

as the smallest individual sound particle, while a grain is made up of multiple wavesets. Secondly, the necessity for windowing has been made redundant, since all wavesets begin and end close to zero amplitude, meaning that amplitude discontinuities in the resynthesized waveform are avoided, at least at high sample rates. Apart from preserving the amplitudal integrity of individual wavesets, a per-sample multiplication is saved, contributing to a reduced CPU load. Thirdly, grain overlaps become less essential, again due to the waveform continuity. Again, this contributes to a reduced CPU load by omitting the need for generating multiple grains at once. Lastly, zero-crossing granulation addresses the spectral properties of its source material as a defining factor in the analysis, significantly contributing to the sonic identity of the resynthesized signal. The integration of signal analysis with the resynthesis process contributes to situating DSP operations in their environment, through a direct coupling to the waveform identity.

The original impetus to exploring waveset operations partly derived from working with *attics*. Throughout the preparation for this piece, it became clear to me that the temporal stretching of the double bass' timbre offered an exciting approach to the generation of novel textures and new musical material. Whereas *attics* relied on the quadraphonic processing of a mono signal, the four discrete inputs to the Bela allow me to rethink time-stretching as a per-string operation, offering a new set of creative possibilities.

4.8.2 Implementation of waveset operations

My own early experiments followed Wishart's approach and were implemented in SuperCollider using Alberto De Campo's (2011) *Waveset* UGen. Both de Campo's and my own initial implementation was non-real-time (offline) in the sense that it relied on analysing a pre-recorded audio file. For my initial use, offline analysis was sufficient for use in creating material for the work *Baigup Learning*—an online commission by Tura New Music, Australia, created in collaboration with Josten Myburgh (Myburgh and Melbye 2020). My appreciation of the resulting textures created a wish to be able to perform real-time analysis and synthesis, considering that computationally, this would be a trivial feat for most modern processors.

In a recent paper, Martins and Padovani (2021) present an overview of waveset synthesis software libraries, two of which—an updated version of Di Campo's original SuperCollider UGen, and one by Fabian Seidl (2015)—operate in real time. Seidl's work offers a thorough description of the creation of a real-time waveset algorithm along with a discussion of the signal processing possibilities introduced by the technique, yet does not feature much discussion of the application of the technique to a musical practice.

In the following, I will discuss the creation of my own waveset algorithm, designed especially for use with the FAAB. While many features will be identical to the algorithms mentioned above, some considerations apply when working with an instrument such as the FAAB. While the algorithm is programmed in C++ and designed to run on the Bela, I have aimed at reducing CPU usage by avoiding some of the costlier operations described by Wishart, Seidl, and Martins and Padovani. In line with the DSP philosophy of my current work, variety and complexity are instead pursued through the coupling of audio feature descriptors to processing variables.

The C++ code for the waveset algorithm is available here: <https://github.com/Adampultz/pultzLib/tree/main/Wavesets>, while the render.cpp file for running wavesets on the Bela can be found here: <https://github.com/Adampultz/pultzLib/tree/main/Demos/Wavesets>.

Analysis

In this analysis, wavesets are indexed according to start and end position in the sample buffer. Figure 4.12 provides an example of the C++ code implementing this analysis in real-time (the full code is available at <https://github.com/Adampultz/pultzLib/blob/main/Wavesets/WavesetsRT.cpp>):

Here we index the beginning of the current waveset, expressed as integers along the x-axis of the signal. Its amplitude at any given index, that is, the y-value, will be either 0, which is unlikely, or very close to 0. Each waveset index is inserted in an array that additionally contains information about the amplitude of the current and previous samples, the fractional crossing, fractional length, mean amplitude, and peak amplitude. The latter three values express information about the entire waveset, and as such, are only possible to compute upon detection of the next waveset. While mean and peak amplitude are used for filtering out unwanted noise, fractional crossing and length can be applied to the interpolation between discontinuous wavesets. From an aesthetical point of view, I have come to appreciate the somewhat gritty sound of non-fractional zero crossings, and have therefore postponed any further work on their smoothing.

```

void zx_detect(float x, int index){
    index_ = index;
    float x = sample;

    float absAmp = fabsf(x);

    if (x_m1 < 0.0 && x >= 0.0){
        if (localPeakAmp_ > (lastMeanAmp_ * ampThreshold_)){
            gAmpAccum_ /= gPeriodCounter_;

            if (zcIndex_ > 0){
                wavesetInfo_[zcIndex_ - 1][5] = localPeakAmp_;
                wavesetInfo_[zcIndex_ - 1][6] = gAmpAccum_;

                wavesetInfo_[zcIndex_] =
                {(float) index_, 0.0f, x, x_m1, 0.0f, 0.0f, 0.0f};

                meanAmp_ += gAmpAccum_;

                if (localPeakAmp_ > peakAmp_)
                    peakAmp_ = localPeakAmp_;

                lastMeanAmp_ = gAmpAccum_;
                gPeriodCounter_ = 0;
                localPeakAmp_ = 0;
                gAmpAccum_ = 0;
                zcIndex_++;
            }
        }

        x_m1 = x;
        return 0;
    }

    return 0;
}

```

Figure 4.12 C++ code for waveset detection and analysis

Playback

After the analysis is complete, playback is initiated. This consists of a resynthesis algorithm applying different operations to one or several wavesets (GitHub link: https://github.com/Adampultz/pultzLib/blob/main/Wavesets/Wavesets_RT_Shell.cpp).

For granulation purposes, the algorithm has three main variables:

- Block size, expressed as the number of consecutive wavesets per playback iteration.

- Block repetitions: How many times a block will be repeated before triggering a new block.
- Buffer size: The length of the audio to be analysed and resynthesised.

Grain size, then, is a function of block size and block repetitions. A fourth variable, waveset increment—that is, the number of wavesets the read pointer will skip forward after having completed its repetitions—is generally set to 1.

For illustration purposes: In order to recreate the original signal, repeats must be set to 0. With a block size of 10 and repeats of 1, the playback will move at one-tenth the speed of the original signal. A different texture with a similar time expansion factor would be achieved by setting block size to 1 and repeats to 10.

Noise management and playback artefacts

The zero-crossing analysis will mercilessly identify any electromagnetic interference, crosstalk between pickups and—in the realm of human agency—imprecise bowing techniques. This is particularly true in the environment of real-time DSP, where only limited possibilities exist for treating the source audio before exposing it to analysis and resynthesis. While microscopic fluctuations and noise are usually only marginally perceptible in an unprocessed signal, through time-expansion they may become perceptual entities in themselves. A noisy signal will yield many zero-crossings and, hence, wavesets of very short durations, giving a noisy playback due to the repetition of low-amplitude grains of high spectral entropy. In de Campo's Waveset UGen, this problem is addressed by setting a lower threshold for the number of samples each wavelet may contain. However, this solution is not sample rate-independent, as higher sample rates would lead to lower tolerances and temporally shorter wavesets (20 samples at 96 kHz equals 10 samples at 48 kHz). Additionally, it is agnostic concerning overall signal amplitude. Instead, I have opted for a solution adapted from Joel de Guzman's (2020) *Bit-stream Autocorrelation* algorithm. While Guzman's algorithm is concerned with pitch detection, it relies on zero-crossing analysis and, as such, face the same challenges as waveset analysis. In de Guzman's solution, only zero-crossing windows with a peak amplitude in excess of the mean amplitude of the entire analysis window, scaled by a coefficient of less than 1.0, are registered. In my implementation, I compare the peak amplitude of any waveset against that of the mean amplitude of the previous waveset. A possible improvement would be to use a running mean or median filter on several previous mean amplitudes. The coefficient value in my current setup is set to 0.01 and has been chosen based on a heuristic auditory analysis and musical taste: too low a value increases the presence of noise in the signal, while a value too high will mean that short, but valid

wavesets would be ignored. This would result in a resynthesis favouring longer periods, the repetition of which leads to a perceived roughness in the output.

It is worth noting that a DC blocker filter (O. Smith III n.d) is essential for the waveset analysis, without which the algorithm would be at risk of tracking false zero crossings or failing to register valid ones.

Spectral ambiguity

Above, I have referred to waveform continuity as a salient property of the waveset approach. While this affords the retention of some sense of signal preservation in the face of temporal stretching, due to the possible timbral complexity of an oscillating string, the waveset analysis also introduces a new set of complexities in the signal. A sinusoidal signal will yield wavesets identical to its period. In contrast, for complex signals with a low-frequency fundamental having lower energy than its partials, any zero-crossing analysis may segment the signal into partials rather than the fundamental frequency, meaning that even a single waveset may not represent a fundamental (see also Wishart (1994, p. 88)). This is especially true of the complex string behaviour of multiphonics and other spectrally rich playing styles that are common features of my playing. Since my ambition is not to faithfully reproduce the signal according to perceived fundamentals, such ambiguity does not pose an obstacle, but rather affords the exploration of timbral variation on the level of microsound.

However, this uncertainty leads to the question of how to define block, or—in Wishart’s terminology—grain size. From Wishart’s writing (*ibid.*, p. 88), it appears that he exclusively relies on single wavesets. Sanfilippo (2019, p. 86) allows for a tentative predefined window size, the first zero-crossing after which determines the actual window size (which, if using wavesets, would be the initial negative-to-positive zero-crossing). For the double bass, predefining a block size to be, say, 20 ms, is acceptable for the resynthesis of a frequency of 440 Hz with a cycle of approximately 2.27 ms. Yet, for a frequency of less than 50 Hz, this poses a problem, as the original waveform will be longer than the specified block size. This would result in a further attenuation of the fundamental frequency by the playback developing a preference for upper partials, complicating the already precarious resynthesis of low-frequency signals.

These findings are specific to the frequency range and timbre of the double bass, and may not be of a concern in every situation. The current range of the FAAB, stretching over approximately six octaves when considering extended tuning and harmonics, yields fundamental frequencies in the range of approximately 38 to 2000 Hz, equivalent to waveset durations between 26.3 and 0.5 ms. Rather than predefining block length in the time domain, I have chosen to define it as an integer multiple of wavesets. Consequently, we leave the

domain of waveform agnosticism and enter one where the sound morphology is, at least partly, determined by the source material.

Offline analysis and playback

The initial offline analysis tests were promising and have evolved into an algorithm on their own. Contrary to the real-time implementation, the offline algorithm does not require a tightly coupled relationship between analysis and playback. Accordingly, it operates in two stages, the first analysing the entire audio file, while the second stage is responsible for the amplitude-dependent selection of wavesets through the thresholding discussed above. Here, it is important to stress that the original audio file is not altered in the analysis process; only vectors containing waveset information are updated.

Figure 4.13 Offline waveset analysis and playback

Although real-time analysis and playback was the original goal, the offline analysis became almost instantly useful in the fixed-media piece *Diffractions*—a commission by Murray Art Museum and Bogong Centre for Sound Culture in Australia (<https://field-not.es/>). While not being part of the portfolio, the audio file is accessible at <https://adampultz.bandcamp.com/album/diffractions>. Since the waveset analyses and synthesis relies on the analysis of a mono signal, for stereo signals, two instances of the algorithm are required. A stereo signal rarely, if ever, has a matching number of zero crossings between channels, meaning that the application of discrete waveset synthesis to each channel will result in a fascinating phenomenon of the signals straying apart. Depending on the source material, the result may be anything from a subtly oscillating delay effect between channels, to the impression of two distinct signals. Where the source is a stereo recording of a double bass solo performed in a natural environment, such as my solo album *Dam* (Melbye 2020a), material from which was used for *Diffraction*, the experience is that of a warping of the stereo image (examples of which occur between 01:39 and 03:40 and, even more obviously from 18:49 and until 25:26). In the case of a non-repeating longer source file, one channel may start significantly lagging behind the other, to slowly catch up and overtake it. As such, the performer and composer may relieve themselves of probability distributions or manual panning and instead let the source signal modulate higher-order processing features such as the deconstruction of the spatial sonic image.

Real-time analysis and playback

The real-time waveset approach poses unique challenges not encountered with offline analysis and playback. For time-stretching purposes, we will need to run our waveset analyses and transpositions on buffers of a limited duration, to avoid the resynthesised signal receding further and further into the past. When time-stretched playback in one buffer has finished, this buffer will then need to be filled with new audio closer to the present. Obviously, then, real-time waveset time stretch will discard audio at a ratio inverse to the stretch itself (if the stretch is a factor of 1/10, 9/10 of the incoming audio will be discarded by the resynthesis). Therefore, a strict separation between the write and read position needs to be established to ensure that the read section is not overwritten while playing back. This would be disastrous, as the waveset operations depend on a complete knowledge of the entire waveset or wavesets currently being played back. At the same time, as will be discussed shortly, since the time it will take for the read pointer to complete reading the playback buffer is unknown, there is no way to pre-compute when a transition from analysis to playback in any given buffer will happen. One solution would be to have discrete read and write buffers and copy samples between these, which, however, is a computationally costly operation. My alternative solution has been to implement three buffers, each of which at any given time may be used for writing or reading.

To avoid writing into a buffer currently reserved for reading, we need to make sure that the read buffer index is always one ahead of the write index, the one exception being in the transition phase between one read buffer to the next. As such, the write pointer, always writing at a speed of 1, will loop through buffer n until it receives notification that the read pointer has reached the end of its current buffer $n + 1$ and has proceeded into buffer $n + 2$, which is the buffer immediately preceding the write buffer. At this point, the write pointer, upon reaching the end of buffer n , will proceed to write into buffer $n + 1$.

Illustrated in figure 4.14, this temporal discontinuity between three buffers is necessary in order to preserve continuity within the buffers themselves.

Figure 4.14 Real-time waveset analysis and playback

Variables

In a system relying on fixed values for grain size, uncertainties pertaining to write and playback buffer transitions would not be a concern, since playback speed could be pre-computed during analysis. However, as with traditional granulation, the textural variety of waveset synthesis benefits greatly from dynamical control over variables.

While being mainly concerned with the repetitions of single wavesets, Wishart (1994, p. 17) observes that repeating every waveset only once or twice merely leads to a perceived deconstruction of the signal that doesn't allow for an experience of expansion to occur. Signal stability is achieved from around five or six repetitions and beyond, at which point time expansion becomes noticeable. In my own work, by allowing for more than one discrete waveset per grain, lower block repetitions may be allowed, while retaining a sense of expansion and adding new spectral features to the resynthesised signal. Importantly, repetition may be entirely omitted by increasing block size to about 10 and more, in which case block and grain size become identical. With a waveset increment of one, this amounts to expanding by a factor equal to the block size, with each grain differing from the previous by one waveset.

Block size

In contrast to traditional granulation techniques, the waveset analysis itself introduces a variable, namely the coupling of waveset size to the input audio waveform. Even with block size and repetitions set to fixed values, the playback length is inversely related to

frequency, with lower-frequency waveforms tending to produce longer wavesets than higher ones. Here we again need to remember that wavesets derived from complex waveforms do not necessarily correspond to the perceived fundamental, but can also represent partials. Since low frequencies are perceived as softer than—and generally don't feed back as easily as—their high frequency siblings, I have chosen to reinforce the playback length of low-frequency waveforms by inversely mapping the spectral tendency of each string to the block size of its resynthesis. Here, spectral tendency is a CPU-efficient time-domain analysis algorithm, developed by Dario Sanfillippo (Sanfilippo 2019, p. 52). It is remarkably precise⁶ and I have found that it gives a good fundamental frequency estimate for signals such as a self-oscillating double bass string. The inverse mapping of frequency to block size additionally has the benefit of avoiding the resynthesis applying a long time stretch to quiet, but noisy signals, that may cause the spectral tendency algorithm to output a high pitch estimate. Accordingly, a frequency range of 30 to 1500 Hz is mapped to block sizes of between 8 and 1. The frequency estimate is generally between 80 and 800, meaning that only in rare cases will the values at either limit be generated. To avoid sudden value fluctuations, the frequency estimate is smoothed by a one-pole low-pass filter with a cut-off at 0.2 Hz.

Block repetitions

Block repetitions are determined through mapping of an RMS amplitude range of 0.0 to 0.3 to repetition values of 1 to 10. Like the spectral tendency estimate, this mapping attenuates the extension of soft signals, with the drawback being the linear relationship between amplitude and repetition. Further work may implement thresholding, nonlinear or tanh-function mappings to explore a more complex application of block repetition.

Buffer size

Buffer size has proven to be of critical significance in real-time implementation. For continuous and frequency-invariant feedback exhibiting periodic waveforms with few harmonics, buffer sizes below 0.4 seconds work well, since the resynthesized audio will resemble the source material by simply repeating the periodic input. For non-periodic waveforms such as multiphonics, or those produced by *sul ponticello arco*, buffer sizes shorter than 0.4 seconds will compromise the experience of discrete sonic events, leading to an output of high variance. On the other hand, buffer sizes larger than 1.5 seconds will make the system

⁶ I have implemented Sanfillippo's suggestion for a computationally cheap version, that omits a number of stabilising features in the pitch calculation. Due to an overshoot of the cheap version, I have found it necessary to multiply the algorithm's estimate by a factor of 0.66333. The code, adapted to C++ from Sanfilippo's original code in the Faust language, is available as a part of pultzLib: <https://github.com/Adampultz/pultzLib/tree/main/Analysis>.

feel slow and unresponsive, and additionally emphasise the delay introduced by the analysis window. Relying purely on heuristics, an initial buffer size of between 0.5 and 0.7 seconds has proven to be a good compromise, by allowing for a sense of continuity between input and playback.

In a more recent development, buffer size has been rendered dynamic. In 3.2.2, I discussed the application of an audio feature rate-of-change. Applied to amplitude, this algorithm gives a very rough measure of the amplitudal novelty of the signal. By mapping RMS rate-of-change to buffer size, we can make the latter increase and decrease with the amplitude novelty of the signal. As such, the waveset algorithm is conditioned to exploring states with a higher novelty in greater detail, while giving less attention to static textures. While this constitutes a fairly primitive representation of what could be considered novel and interesting to the improvising machine, it counterbalances the resynthesis of steady-state feedback, the time-stretch of which tends to introduce timbral redundancy. In contrast, amplitude discrepancies, whether in loud or soft signals, will cause the buffer to expand, thereby increasing the possibility of generating novel resynthesized textures.

4.8.3 Temporally extended and displaced harmonics

Compared to its smaller siblings in the violin family, plucked, struck, or bowed harmonics on the double bass have significant sustain to the extent that chordal structures may be explored, for example in Luciano Berio's *Sequenza XIVb* (2004), arranged and performed by the late double bassist Steffano Scodanibbio. On the acoustic double bass, I have used bowed harmonics extensively, for example with the trio Flamingo (n.d) and on the track *Boolean* from the solo album *Measures* (Melbye 2017a). As already mentioned in 4.7.6, bowed harmonics constitute the first half of *We're running out of Sand*.

I commenced work with the FAAB supposing that the sustain of harmonics would be extended through the self-oscillation of the strings. This has proven to be only partly true: as discussed in 4.7.6, at low-to-moderate volume, the feedback does tend to cause harmonics to ring a little longer, creating what I referred to as ghostly resonance. However, due to the tendency of the feedback to seek attractors of low-integer multiples of the fundamentals of the string, in the absence of continuous bowing, an upper partial will tend toward such attractors. In some edge cases, it is possible to sustain both the initially activated harmonic and the emerging fundamental by carefully managing master volume, although this is by no means a reliable phenomenon.

The tendency to accentuate fundamentals is no surprise, given that the vibrational length of the string is not changed when playing harmonics. Alternatively, we may consider a

stopped note: in this case, the finger depressing the string acts as a moving nut and causes an actual shortening of the string's vibrational length.

The waveset algorithm disrupts the dominance of low-integer harmonics. By allowing for the retention of energy at higher harmonics after their acoustic actuation, thereby increasing their chance of self-oscillation, the algorithm increases the number of attractors and hence, the variety of the system. Essentially, it introduces a new feedback cycle through a temporal displacement—as well as extension—of the signal: as the algorithm excites the string at its upper partial this excitation gets amplified through the system in a fashion similar to the unprocessed feedback, the only difference being the resynthesized nature of the signal being fed back into the system in the waveset case. The temporal displacement is a difference in degree, not kind, to the unprocessed feedback that is also defined by a time shift, albeit magnitudes shorter than the delay introduced by the resynthesis. However, it is not a given that by simply playing a harmonic, the waveset algorithm will cause the system to enter a feedback cycle at that very frequency. For this to happen, several factors need to coincide. Most importantly, the string needs to be actuated long enough that the playback will have sufficient time to cause the system to enter the new attractor.

This brings us back to my occupation with bowed harmonics and how this practice becomes transformed and extended through the operations of the waveset algorithm: through the time-stretch, harmonics (or any sound for that matter) may sustain beyond their natural decay in a way that is significantly different to how a string decays acoustically. Instead of the natural decay of the latter, which is an irreversible process obeying the laws of thermodynamics, the waveset stretch will modulate its decay time as a function of its own output⁷. Accordingly, while I do have some control over the behaviour of the playback by adjusting bow attack, pressure, and release, the way these changes map to buffer size, block size, and block repetition are governed by complex internal dynamics, making it difficult for me to expect exactly how the algorithm will respond to my playing. Finally, this predicament is only exacerbated by the fact that I do not know whether what I am currently playing will make it into the playback at all. While the waveset synthesis is a promise of extended sustain, it may also abruptly cut off a sustaining pitch when entering a new buffer containing new material or silence.

4.8.4 Findings and explorations

Through the development of the waveset algorithm, it has become clear that rather than creating a smooth, temporally stretched version of the original signal, it may introduce

⁷ For a more detailed discussing of immanent signal processing, see 4.10.

significant artefacts, ranging from a perceived increase in the roughness of the signal to a stuttering playback, especially in the lower frequencies. This is no doubt because the temporally longer wavesets of low-frequency signals will map to larger playback grains. Additionally, as mentioned previously, low-frequency signals on the FAAB often contain partials of higher amplitude than the fundamental. The playback expresses this ambiguity through discontinuous stuttering, literally shuffling back and forth between fundamental and integer-multiple periods. While these phenomena are much less pronounced when the source signal is pure string feedback, bowed pitches yield very diverse behaviours. Here, the spectral complexity of the signal is expressed full force, with the transients caused by a change in bowing direction (an operation notoriously difficult even at a 1/1 time-ratio) manifesting as an extended buildup and decay of a high-entropic, high-frequency sonic event (audio example: <https://on.soundcloud.com/oTjdY>). Similarly, bowed multiphonics and sul ponticello techniques come to sound like strange, bit-reduced and staircase-like signals with discernible pitch-fluctuations (audio example: <https://on.soundcloud.com/RXZ2y>). While these artefacts are the result of transitions between heterogeneous wavesets, because of the zero-crossing transitions, they do not exhibit the clicks associated with non-overlapping and un-windowed granulation. Rather, what we may experience as artefacts could just as well be understood as discrete immanent potentials of the signal. While these potentials are usually integrated over milliseconds and accordingly perceived as continuous, through repetition, and hence expansion, they come to occupy their own discrete space.

In recent explorations of waveset time-expansion, I have come to appreciate a number of phenomena:

- Onsets and attacks achieve a character of sonic “beads”, often losing their percussiveness, instead achieving an almost bubbly sound ([Link](#)).
- Repetitive bowing patterns across strings generate a slowed-down rhythmic meta-pattern ([Link](#)).
- Bowing on dampened strings and exploring lower-amplitude noise textures yield quite mystic and sometimes rather bizarre responses. They somehow often still manage to blend in with the acoustic texture, creating an ambiguous sonic space, ripe for exploration. Playing around the threshold between un-pitched and pitched sounds yields fascinating results, with the resynthesis alternating between muffled textures and high-frequency bursts ([Link](#)).
- While difference tones have been a focus of my musical practice for many years (Melbye 2017b), the sinusoidal qualities of a self-oscillating string and its playback

allows for very particular textures not possible on an acoustic instrument. By slightly adjusting left-hand position and hence the frequency of pure string-feedback, it is possible to play pitches back against delayed and subtly detuned versions of themselves. In this case, since the playback is often smooth, the resulting difference tones are remarkably consistent ([Link](#)).

- Due to the discontinuity in playback when the read pointer enters a new buffer, the material of which is more recent in time (5 – 20 seconds or more) than the previous one, even when operating in a static sonic environment, amplitude discontinuities between buffers can be significant.
- The deconstructive stereo effect, as a function of different zero-crossings between channels described in 4.8.2, has a counterpart in the current real-time version: applying a repetition factor of, say 5, to a waveset of a low A at 55 Hz will result in a playback lasting 90 milliseconds, while applying the same factor to A at 440 Hz will give a playback time of 11 milliseconds. With the signal of every string being analysed and processed individually, an interesting asynchronicity emerges: playback will no longer retain the temporal relationships between strings, meaning that bowing two pitches on different strings synchronously may manifest as discrete events having different start and end-times in the resulting playback. Additionally, the algorithm is selective and will only play back those parts of the signal happening to be in the write buffer when a buffer transition happens. Consequently, while discarding everything else up until the next buffer transition, parts of a signal appearing as a single sonic entity in the acoustic domain may become omitted in the playback. While this is already a significant feature of the summed signal being played back over the FAAB's single speaker, distributing the discrete outputs across four speakers has been implemented in the recent performances *Echoes of unspecified Origins* and *Towering Silence* (both discussed below).

4.8.5 Performance: Answer use replace, insert, append

The performance is available from <https://vimeo.com/747567186/6e82778283>.

The waveset time-stretch causes texturally and spectrally rich, as well as surprising, and sometimes unpredictable, results. While the algorithm will support and expand the delicate textures of bowed single pitches, it will also introduce upper harmonics and brutally expose any bowing discontinuities. Accordingly, I have found myself adapting my playing to explore the extremes of bowing, either paying great attention to the preservation of continuity

and pureness of timbre or aiming for extracting a high degree of spectral ambiguity from the string. Due to the time expansion, even the trivial gesture of bowing a single pitch may result in an informationally saturated output and, as such, affords a reconsideration of structure and temporality, in improvisation as well as composition. In my recent work, this is best exemplified in *Answer use replace, insert, append*—a piece recorded for the online inauguration of the Feedback Musicianship Network on June 4th, 2021. While several of the techniques and timbres explored in this piece have been covered in section 4.8.4, I would like to specifically focus on the beginning of the piece. Here, I activate the waveset algorithm and start out by bowing a single pitch—a harmonic node on the 1st string corresponding to the ratio of $3/2$ relative to the string. As the playback enters, it introduces a harmonic at a $3/2$ ratio above the bowed frequency (the fifth above the octave, a ratio of $9/2$ relative to the string or $33/8$ relative to the fundamental). While bowing is still taking place, the resynthesis is not strongly perceived, but blends with the bowed pitch, a phenomenon that changes the moment the bow is decoupled from the string. At this point, two things are prone to happen: either the resynthesized pitch is strong enough to lock the string oscillations at the $3/2$ harmonic, or feedback will build up around the fundamental of the string. In the case of the former, by carefully adjusting the master volume, the string may remain stable in this state, while other strings are bowed. In the latter case, the fundamental of the string will gradually come to dominate. In the present case, during the process of transition between harmonic and fundamental, the waveset resynthesis skips between the two wave periods, causing significant modulation artefacts, not unlike the previously described response to multiphonics. Sonically disruptive as it is, it is also an emergent, deterministic, and, to me, musically pleasing property of the entanglement of performance, matter and software. It is decidedly novel and acoustically alien, yet reproducible and structurally implicit. What is critical, though, is to give such phenomena time to become perceptually established. Possessing an acoustically alien nature as they do, they carry a risk of becoming freakish artefacts unrelated to the ongoing flow and structure-building of the performance. Accordingly, the insistence on their place in the performative process will determine whether such sonic artefacts become musically meaningful. As I am becoming increasingly convinced, in performing with the waveset algorithm, my response to such phenomena must often entail patience and refraining from playing. In other words, creating a space for events with sonically distant relationships to the source material entails exposing them in their unmitigated otherness for extended periods of time.

4.9 DisCo nT – A case study in adaptive comb filtering

Above, I discussed how waveset time expansion may assist in disrupting the tendency of the FAAB to stabilise on low-integer multiples of the fundamental frequency of the string. In another endeavour directed at coaxing the feedback away from this tendency, early programming work focused on the implementation of bandpass and comb filters (Úlfarsson and Melbye 2020, p. 224). This was guided by the assumption that, by focusing the energy of the amplified signal on specific frequencies, I could force the strings into self-oscillation around these very frequencies. Below I will discuss the implementation of an adaptive comb filter, that, in addition to increasing the number of resonant attractors, has effectuated the emergence of a number of unforeseen musical potentials.

The C++ code for the adaptive comb filter is available here: <https://github.com/Adampultz/pultzLib/tree/main/Filters>, while the render.cpp file used for running the filter on the Bela is found here: <https://github.com/Adampultz/pultzLib/tree/main/Demos/Adaptive%20Comb%20filter>.

4.9.1 Basics of comb filtering

While a comb filter can be implemented with both a feed-forward, and a feedback architecture, it is the latter I will focus on here. Being a special-case Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) filter with one addition, one subtraction, and one multiplication, in addition to being identical to a delay line with feedback, it is a computationally cheap filter ideal for quadrophonic processing on the Bela. It is defined by the difference equation

$$y[n] = x[n] + gy[n - M] \quad (4.10)$$

where M is the delay in samples and g the feedback coefficient. Since we are discussing the filter in the context of a feedback instrument, in the following, it is important to differ between the acoustic feedback of the FAAB and the filter's internal feedback, the latter which is exclusively present in the filter's delay line. The delay line itself has been implemented as a circular buffer with linear interpolation.

True to its name, the filter's frequency response resembles a comb, caused by the introduction of a sequence of resonant peaks and valleys in the signal, the resonant fundamental of which corresponds to the inverse of the delay time. With a positive feedback coefficient, the resonant peaks are situated at the even-numbered harmonics (figure 4.15), whereas a negative feedback coefficient shifts the peaks to the odd harmonics (figure 4.16).

Figure 4.15 Feedback magnitude response for various positive feedback values (α). Delay time equals 2 samples.

By Krishnavedala - Own work, CC BY-SA 3.0,
<https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=15298010>

Figure 4.16 Feedback magnitude response for various negative feedback values (α). Delay time equals 2 samples.

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<https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=15298032>

Inverting the sign of the feedback amounts to a polarity switch, which, in turn, affects the phase of the signal. Probably because polarity and phase are somewhat related, they are often used interchangeably in audio production and signal processing. Yet, in digital signal processing they are discrete operations relating to the sign of the signal and its time-domain representation, respectively. In an ideal repeating waveform, such as an infinite sine-wave, a 180-degree phase shift would be identical to a polarity switch. In contrast, the partials of timbrally complex signals, in the case of a polarity switch, are asymmetrically phase-shifted⁸.

4.9.2 An adaptive comb filter

Through the tuning of three filter variables—frequency, feedback coefficient, and feedback sign—the comb filter affords the attenuation of particularly strong acoustic attractors, in addition to the amplification of weak resonances, ultimately increasing the number of attractors in the FAAB's phase space. In line with the hypothesis of this study, namely that situated and immanent processes afford adaption, interaction and improvisation, the variables discussed here are all coupled to data generated from audio feature analysis, in this case extracted from the output of the algorithm itself.

Below, I will describe the implementation of three adaptive structures before discussing their contribution to the behaviour of the comb filter, and the FAAB in general, within the context of a performance.

Adaptive filter frequency

By applying a comb filter to an audio source such as an oscillating double bass string, the filter output will consist of the source audio modified to exhibit resonant peaks corresponding to the fundamental and harmonics of the filter frequency. If we apply a frequency detection algorithm to the *output* of the filter, it is likely to return a frequency estimate corresponding to either the strongest harmonic of the string, or, alternatively, the strongest resonant peak of the filter. By feeding this value back into its frequency variable, the filter may start self-oscillating around its strongest resonances. If the resonance corresponds to the dominant harmonic of the string, the filter will contribute to the deepening of this particular basin of attraction, effectively assisting the FAAB in establishing resonant attractors already present in its phase space. However, since the onset of a string vibration is often spectrally more complex than its ensuing decay or stable oscillation, a chance exists that the frequency tracker and comb-filter coupling may cause self-oscillation around frequencies other than the frequency acoustically dominant in the absence of any filtering. This probability is further

⁸ I am grateful to Chris Pitsiokos for pointing the difference between polarity and phase out to me.

increased by the frequency tracker listening at the filtered output of the algorithm rather than the acoustic input of the string oscillations.

The short time instability of onset frequency detection can lead to an increased diversity in long-term behaviour. Yet, a continuous spectrally complex input, such as bowed string or a multiphonic, may result in the frequency estimate—and consequently the filter resonances—continuously fluctuating. To my ears, this is not musically ideal and additionally compromises adaption, as the filter rarely stabilises long enough to establish any internal self-oscillation between frequency estimate and filter resonance. Before gently smoothing the pitch estimate with a one-pole low-pass filter, we can apply a sample-and-hold (SAH) operation, the triggering of which, in line with the aim of behaviour immanent to the system, could derive from the system state itself.

In 4.8.2, I discussed the use of an amplitude acceleration approximation. By integrating and thresholding this value, we can generate a trigger signal for the SAH. Effectively, every time the amplitude deviation over a given time window increases past a certain threshold, whichever frequency is currently estimated is mapped to the filter frequency. Given that the time window of the fast RMS tracker is high enough, the SAH will catch any transients in the onset, raising the chance of triggering frequencies other than the fundamental of the string oscillation.

Figure 4.17 Comb filter frequency

Of musical and performative interest is the fact that the change in filter resonances is triggered by both amplitude decreases *and* increases. I shall discuss this phenomenon further below.

Illustrated in figure 4.18, to further push the filtered string signal away from deep attractors, we can raise the tracked frequency by an integer ratio corresponding to the low-integer harmonics of $3/2$, $5/4$, $7/4$, $9/8$, and $11/8$. This ratio is currently chosen at random.

Figure 4.18 Filter frequency multiplied by randomly selected ratios

Filter feedback coefficient

The familiar “ringing” sound of a comb filter is largely due to the output signal being fed back into the delay line, creating a sequence of evenly spaced echoes. With the increase of the filter delay time, a high feedback coefficient will cause the filter to ring with a metallic sound, considered unwanted when using the comb filter as the basis of reverberation algorithms (Reiss and McPherson 2019, p. 260; Pirkle 2019, p. 466). In my case, a high feedback coefficient increases the chance of the filter shifting the string resonance away from acoustically deep attractors. Yet, the metallic ringing becomes apparent during onsets due to acoustic transients, in addition to filter frequency jumps caused by the adaptive frequency control. To counteract this artefact, I again make use of the integrated amplitude acceleration, this time by subtracting its squared, continuous value from a feedback coefficient of 0.95. Consequently, when amplitude rises or falls, the feedback, and hence the resonance of the filter, will decrease, whereas it will begin rising again once amplitude stability is regained, regardless of whether amplitude is high or low.

Figure 4.19 Filter feedback coefficient

Filter feedback sign

As mentioned in 4.9.1, while shifting the polarity of the signal does not constitute an actual phase shift, the polarity shift described below was inspired by Nic Collins’ (2020a) use of phase shifting in *Pea Soup*. In Collins’ work, originally implemented in the analogue domain, an envelope follower was used as a control signal for a phase shift, emulating the continuous spatial displacement of the microphone (*ibid.*, p. 3). In the digital implementation of *Pea Soup* the phase shift was created through the Hilbert Transform, which, even if digitally implemented in the time domain, is a taxing CPU operation. In the present case, rather than operating directly on the main acoustic feedback signal, the polarity switch is implemented in the feedback chain of the comb filter’s delay line.

Simply changing the sign of the filter feedback is computationally cheap and brutally effective. In order to smooth out the resulting sudden amplitude jumps, I have applied a one-pole low-pass filter, creating a soft amplitude envelope.

The triggering in this case is implemented through a *Schmitt trigger*—a simple digital emulation of an analogue signal comparator with hysteresis. A Schmitt trigger has two thresholds; one upper and one lower. In this case, once the amplitude has crossed the upper threshold, a value of negative 1 is output, while a positive 1 is output when the amplitude falls below the lower threshold. As such, for amplitude values between the two thresholds, the Schmitt trigger keeps outputting its last value. Figure 4.20 provides the code for the C++ `Schmitt_Trigger` class found in `pultzLib`. Separate amplitude thresholds can be set for each of the four Schmitt triggers to account for the variation in behaviour across the four strings.

```

class Schmitt_Trigger
{
public:
    Schmitt_Trigger(){};

    void init(float lowerThresh, float upperThresh){
        upperThresh_ = upperThresh;
        lowerThresh_ = lowerThresh;
    };

    float process(float s){
        if (s >= upperThresh_ && state_ == 1) {
            state_ = -1;
        } else if (s < lowerThresh_ && state_ == -1) {
            state_ = 1;
        }
        return state_;
    }

private:
    float upperThresh_;
    float lowerThresh_;
    float state_ = 1;
};

```

Figure 4.20 Schmitt trigger, C++ code

Figure 4.21 Filter feedback coefficient and sign

Applying the output of the Schmitt Trigger to the feedback coefficient of the comb filter introduces a nonlinear phase response to amplitude fluctuations. Importantly, should the amplitude increase, the comb filter shifts its resonant peaks, possibly counterbalancing the feedback build-up of the FAAB.

Figure 4.22 Comb filter feedback coefficient. Brown = 1st string, red = 4th string. Screenshot from video available at <https://vimeo.com/749885276/344b15ecee>

4.9.3 Performance with the comb filter

The performance is available from <https://vimeo.com/666244503>. The C++ code for the adaptive comb filter is available here: <https://github.com/Adampultz/pultzLib/tree/main/Filters>. The render.cpp file for running the comb filter on the Bela can be found here: <https://github.com/Adampultz/pultzLib/tree/main/Demos/Adaptive%20Comb%20filter>.

The three augmentations of the standard comb filter described above; adaptive filter frequency, feedback coefficient, and feedback sign, produce a nonlinear and metastable filter very sensitive to input, while introducing its own emergent and immanent behaviour through the operationally closed structure of its signal processing loop.

On November 30th, 2021, I performed the work *Dis Co nT* at a meeting of the Feedback Musicianship Network in Copenhagen, for the first time using the comb algorithm exclusively for all but the last three minutes of the performance. While the video of the concert is grainy to the point of it seeming intentional (it isn't), the audio gives a good impression of the fashion in which the comb filter co-determines the behaviour of the FAAB, establishing a new context within which interaction may take place.

A defining feature of the performance is the throbbing of the strings, clearly present from the very beginning of the performance (00:00 – 01:00), and reappearing throughout (02:25 – 2:40, 04:10 – 4:45, and 06:30 – 7:00). This metastable phenomenon tends to oscillate around

irregular patterns repeating at fixed intervals and is caused by the Schmitt trigger introducing amplitude modulation in the feedback chain of the delay line, through the low pass-filtered polarity shifts.

When observing such self-organizing behaviour, we need to keep acknowledging that, while partly enacted by the hysteresis of the digital Schmitt trigger, its causality is distributed and fundamentally entangled with the material properties of the instrument. When the polarity-switched feedback of the comb filter prevents the feedback of the FAAB from entering a resonant attractor, the nonlinear relationships between speaker, back and front plate, bridge, and strings (to list a few of the parts involved) are allowed to persist as metastable undulations (as opposed to becoming saturated by feedback), in turn feeding the RMS detectors with a complex amplitude envelope.

This intimate coupling of polarity to amplitude is essential to the performance. If a positive-to-negative polarity shift fails to attenuate the amplitude of the mechanical feedback enough to fall below the lower threshold of the Schmitt trigger, feedback may proceed to build up and stabilise above the higher threshold. This stability is attained with the signal being polarity-inverted—and hence asymmetrically phase-shifted—and suggests an expansion of the phase space of the FAAB⁹. As such, at low-to-moderate volumes, the filter will exhibit negative feedback control, whereas high amplitudes will cause its polarity to remain stable, allowing feedback to grow. Additionally, recall that the amount of filter feedback is inversely proportional to amplitude acceleration. When audio feedback stabilises, even at high volumes, amplitude acceleration falls, pushing the feedback of the filter up, thereby amplifying the comb resonances. If the filter frequency at this point is identical to the current fundamental frequency of the string, the filter will effectively contribute to positive feedback (00:28 – 0:31, 1:35 – 1:45, and 2:06 – 2:08).

The amplitude throbbing is a surprising and slightly funky result of the development of the comb filter. In contrast, the high-frequency feedback caused by the filter resonances was intended from the initial design stage. Meant to introduce a greater diversity of pitch material, the filter resonances sometimes produce clearly defined pitches (02:55 – 3:50), while at other times, like the throbbing phenomenon, they enable the alternation between two or more resonant attractors. An example can be found between 01:25 and 1:35, where two frequencies with a 7/4 relationship compete for dominance.

⁹ The assumption here is that the entire digital signal is passing through the comb filter, and therefore exposed to any polarity shift and phase modulation. As such, polarity inversions in the digital domain will only be noticeable at the very moment of the shift, while they may persist in the relation between the digital and acoustic signal. However, because of the hard and software latency of the Bela, phase inversions between the digital and acoustic signal are already present in the absence of the comb filter. It therefore becomes difficult to predict, and beyond the scope of this text, to which extent new polarity shifts may amplify or attenuate additional phase cancellations.

Performance techniques

Arco playing has significant impact on the filter resonance, as becomes clear when bowing is introduced at 05:10. Sul ponticello is a traditional arco technique of bowing the string close to the bridge and amplifies the high frequency spectrum of the string. When combined with the comb filter, not only do novel timbres emerge; the filter causes individual partials to resonate longer, in addition to introducing spectral content harmonically related to, but not necessarily present in, the audio signal (possibly due to the randomly selected ratio multiplier). As is audible in the video, while I am bowing the 1st string, the comb filter introduces a sequence of harmonics in a step-like manner, vaguely resembling a multiphonic, yet with discrete pitch-relationships increasingly pronounced.

In addition to amplitude sensitivity, with the introduction of the comb filter, the FAAB becomes increasingly sensitive to left-hand finger position and pressure. Moving my left-hand-finger a millimetre or two, or slightly increasing or relieving pressure on the string, will change the oscillation pattern and amplitude response of the latter, and ultimately, the response of the algorithm. While it is not visually obvious from the video, much of the performance consists in my subtle manipulation of left-hand position and pressure, not unlike the bass “Reiki” discussed in section 3.1.4. A variation of the double-handed stopping of strings discussed in the section on the [Sync algorithm](#) is applied here, allowing me to keep one hand still, while using the other to actuate or change the pitch on a neighbouring string. This technique assists me in the production of both harmonic and rhythmic polyphony, where some pitches will continuously feed back, while others find themselves in metastable throbbing (02:25 – 4:20).

4.9.4 Adaptive comb filter — Concluding remarks

The adaptive comb filter proposes a solution to the tendency, discussed at various points throughout this text, of feedback to enter a single strong attractor, effectively challenging interaction and improvisation. Due to the polarity-dependent self-cancellation of amplitude at low-to-moderate volume levels, the attractors visited by the FAAB become metastable rhythmical and timbral structures highly sensitive to any change in the system and its environment. In the submitted video, the improvisation that emerges from the establishment of this precarious domain of interaction is one of long-term adaption and response, rather than split-second decision-making. This is no doubt due to my own affinity for exploring this kind of music-making, but is additionally defined through the affordances of the instrument. I find that polarity-shifts, phase-shifts and resonance modulation on a large, low-frequency instrument are conducive to slow and reflective musicking. However, the sometimes static

bodily postures required by such music infer a high level of mental and physical focus on the miniscule changes that *do* occur, in the bodily, as well as in the instrumental domain.

4.10 Discussion of adaptive DSP processes

Evaluated through performances and demo examples, each of the three algorithms discussed above contribute to an expansion of the timbral, spectral, and dynamical space in which the FAAB operates. Although the algorithms engender different behaviours, through an understanding of the similarities in their internal configurations, I will here discuss the ways in which these structures impact performance. Firstly, though, we need to keep in mind the analysis of differences between feedback modalities undertaken in section 4.4. Here, I concluded that, to a greater extent than open-air feedback systems that share air as the medium in which both input and output are situated, with an SRI such as the FAAB, transduction occurs in an assemblage of heterogeneous materials. Consequently, if we listen directly to the pickup input we will hear an oscillating string, even if the speaker outputs a heavily processed signal. This input-output asymmetry on the FAAB is important for an understanding of the choice of listening position: placing the algorithm's listening position at its output gives it direct access to its own internal state, that is, the processed signal itself, rather than the materially transduced signal of its input. Significantly, it suggests that different feedback configurations afford individual DSP architectures, expanding the horizon for continued research far beyond the scope of this thesis.

4.10.1 Situatedness and immanence

We are now in a position to expand on our understanding of how situatedness and immanence may apply to the DSP structure of the FAAB:

Situatedness: as their sensory apparatus is confined to the mediation of the electromagnetic pickups, in a limited sense, the algorithms described above are all situated in their environment. While the audio feature descriptors are only able to perceive one environmental variable (string vibration), that variable contains information about the material configuration and dynamical state and history of the instrument. From this single environmental coupling, two features have been extracted: waveset information and amplitude envelope. To this we may add that the audio signal itself, on a sample-by-sample basis, is a vital source of information impacting any processing happening further down the signal chain, although this is not a unique feature of the FAAB, but applies to any DSP architecture.

Immanence: where waveset information and amplitude envelope are extracted directly from the string signal, four additional features describe the output of the signal processing: slow and fast RMS amplitude, amplitude acceleration, and spectral tendency, the latter additionally serving as a fundamental frequency estimate in the case of periodic or semi-periodic waveforms. As such, rather than relying on a direct extraction of environmental features for modulating DSP variables, in this case, the algorithm uses information about its internal state to drive its own processing variables.

The immanence of the audio feature analysis and signal processing was even more pronounced in the previously discussed work *attics*, where the circularity between acoustic input and DSP output was decoupled through the use of headphones. Yet, in the case of the FAAB, the internal feedback operation instantiated by the coupling of processing variables to audio features derived from the algorithm's own state contributes to the emergence of a simple world in the constructivist sense discussed in 2.10.2. In addition to perception of the environment, the FAAB is now able to directly perceive and act on its own response, effectively increasing its autonomy in interactions with its environment. These immanent control feedback loops are an essential property of the DSP space, allowing the FAAB to regulate its coupling to its environment. This, as we have seen, is a precondition for interactional asymmetry.

My distinction between situatedness and immanence is not meant to suggest that environmental situatedness presents unmediated access to a supposed reality¹⁰. Nor does the term immanence mean that the algorithm is listening to an output entirely decoupled from its environment. Firstly, as already discussed, the algorithm's access to its environment is mediated, on the one hand through the material nature of its couplings, and on the other, via the (humanly curated) choice of features used to describe the signal. Secondly, the algorithm's output is a function of its situated input (and accordingly, its environment), modulated by its own internal processing. Importantly, like the distinctions made between structural coupling/-operational closure and material/digital domains, respectively, the separation of situatedness and immanence constitutes an agential cut. It is locally valid, but ontologically leaky with regard to how situatedness and immanence are enacted in the ecology of performance, in which exteriority and interiority temporally emerge through ongoing processes of reconfiguring mutable boundaries.

¹⁰ A discussion, epistemological or ontological, of the nature of—or validity of positing—a fixed external reality is beyond the scope of this text. My own perspective, rooted in theories of embodied and enactivist cognition, is that any organism's perception of its environment is a world-building, which, on the social level, corresponds to participatory sense-making (De Jaegher and Di Paolo 2007).

4.11 Performing and improvising with the FAAB

In section 2.8.2 I discussed the challenge facing the solo improviser, of establishing a precarious relationship to their instrument, from which improvisation may take place (see also (Melbye 2021a, p. 20)). In 2.8.1 I additionally argued that group improvisation relies on resistance to establish the metastable and precarious situations in which response, adaption, or non-adaption, may occur (ibid., p. 20). In chapter 1 I described how my own response to the absence of the other improviser in solo performance has been to explore a resistant acoustic instrument and a metastable and ambiguous sonic environment (ibid., p. 22).

In analysing and discussing the above three performances and their related algorithms, the metastable and sometimes unpredictable behaviour of the instrument has been a recurring feature. In *Sand*, I discussed how the Sync algorithm established complex oscillating amplitude relationships between the FAAB's four strings, whereas the waveset algorithm used in *Answer use, insert replace, append* exhibited a range of resynthesized timbres, from the non-destructive time expansion of string feedback, to alien high-entropic textures. Finally, in *Di s Co nT*, an adaptive comb filter created irregularly pulsating and throbbing low, as well as high-pitch, resonance.

Due to the situated and immanent adaptive signal processing coupled to the nonlinear performance of a self-oscillating double bass, the emergence of an increased dynamical and timbral space becomes a feature of the instrument's semi-autonomy. More to the point, we can identify a sense of interactional asymmetry emerging through the instrument's property of being able to dynamically regulate interactions with its environment. Having delegated control of some processing variables to the instrument itself, I, as a solo performer, find myself in a situation where the constitution, development, and exploration of timbral and dynamical space is a function of my gesture, the input of the FAAB's pickups, various domains of feedback, and the perceptual and computational properties of the algorithms. Navigating this space, then, is a precarious operation, defined by a horizon of uncertain outcomes, the nature of which I am unable to fully predict or direct. This does not mean that I have lost all control, but rather that the interactional asymmetry established by the FAAB requires me to respond and engage, rather than simply dictate. As such, improvisation becomes a core principle in performing with this instrument. It is only through improvisation that I can respond and adapt to the semi-autonomous behaviour of the FAAB, thereby enabling a musically sound environment in both completely open settings, and in performances with predetermined musical material and narratives, two of which will be discussed shortly.

In this way, many of the features I have explored in my acoustic double bass practice become diffracted through the augmented acoustic-digital space of the FAAB. Spectral ambiguity and high pitch modulation emerge through waveset operations expanding the

rapid spectral dynamics of, say, a multiphonic, into a temporal domain in which frequency fluctuations become perceivable as discrete events. Or they may appear through an increase in resonant attractors, in addition to frequency sweeps and Doppler shifts associated with the adaptive comb filter feeding control signals back unto itself. While not discussed in detail in this study, the feedback-induced sustain of unprocessed string signals in combination with bowed tones (stopped as well as harmonics) allows for two- and three-part polyphony across an extended frequency range in comparison to an acoustic double bass. Consequently, the development, practice, and performance of traditional as well as extended bowing techniques now not only need to take into consideration the acoustic timbral possibilities of the double bass itself. With the DSP domain establishing a world immanent to its own architecture, onsets, bow-direction changes, and minor pressure adjustments (in both bowing and stopping hand) become instigators of timbral variation and nonlinear development beyond their initial duration and mechanical actuation. This constitutes a significant difference to the operation of an acoustic string instrument, where physical actuation may instantiate nonlinear feedback, yet does not engender the extended timbral and temporal autonomy eventually becoming physically decoupled from human intervention.

These observations do not imply that technique cannot be trained and improved. Rather, they become intrinsically tied up with what Hubert Dreyfus (2014) has referred to as *skillful coping*. In Melbye (2021a), I proposed that

mastery is dynamic and never complete. It is enacted in the relation between an agent and its environment and, as such, relies on resistance inherent in this relationship. (...) In contrast to the conventional understanding of mastery as an achievable goal, I will propose the term ‘diachronic mastery’ to describe the dynamic mastery enacted in improvisation and the electro-acoustic ecologies discussed later. (p. 21)

While the development of diachronic skill sets are essential in building an ongoing relationship with the FAAB, in light of the above discussion of interactional asymmetry between humans and semi-autonomous improvising machines, the notion of mastery is rendered operationally unsuitable. More importantly, in chapter 5 I will discuss how feminist and queer readings of mastery, virtuosity and failure afford a critical discussion of these concepts in a performance and music context.

4.12 Collaborations involving the FAAB

While most of my practice with the FAAB has so far oriented itself toward solo performance, in 2021, as parts of Europe emerged from an extended COVID-19 lockdown, I had the

opportunity of using the instrument in two collaborative projects, each of which will be discussed briefly below.

4.12.1 Echoes of Unspecified Origins

Link to performance: <https://on.soundcloud.com/8sYH>.

In the summer of 2021 the guitarist and composer Julia Reidy and I developed the project *Echoes of Unspecified Origins* (hereafter *Echoes*), premiered at Studio Borne, Berlin, on September 24th and 25th. *Echoes* is a six-channel work for adjustable fret guitar and FAAB. It relies on the discrete outputs of the Cycfi Nu pickups, installed on both of our instruments, which allow us to process and spatialise our ten strings separately. For this performance, I designed a SuperCollider patch, running on a separate laptop and processing each string individually. The signal from Julia's guitar was received directly from the pickups, while the signal from the FAAB comprised the output of the onboard DSP. The 13-limit justly tuned pitch sets used for the performance were composed by Julia.

Each string had an amplitude dependent six-channel panning algorithm, creating a continuously changing spatial configuration of the ten strings. The six speakers were placed in a circle around the audience, with Julia and I performing in the centre. Before being panned, each string was submitted to one of three granulation-based time stretch and time freeze processes, all of which were the result of extensive developments of the algorithm initially designed for *attics*. Of special interest to this study was an onset-triggered time stretch that would only record a few seconds after triggering and then continue to cycle through the recorded material until being retriggered. With the dense texture of six to ten signals being asynchronously as well as individually granulated at very slow read speeds, this algorithm would introduce new material only when individual strings were activated, creating a particularly attractive timbre when used in combination with fingerstyle guitar playing (time code 29:05 - 36:40).

10:50 - 17:00 provides the so far only example of unprocessed string feedback from the FAAB. Combined with the spatialisation of the strings, it is apparent how the feedback-induced swell and extended sustain of pizzicato notes allows for a novel approach to creating rich supportive textures to an instrument such as Julia's guitar.

The section between 25:40 and 27:59 showcases both the laptop-based granular processing of the FAAB and the spatially distributed waveset transformation of the Bela. The latter is especially noticeable toward the end of the section, emerging as stuttering extended delays.

The audio recorded from the concert subsequently underwent significant amounts of post-processing (including the development of new SuperCollider algorithms), some overdubs (guitar, acoustic double bass, and sine waves), and mixing.

4.12.2 Towering Silence

Link to video-excerpt of performance: <https://vimeo.com/699466741>.

The full, unedited audio of the concert is available here: <https://on.soundcloud.com/SJN2k>.

In March 2021, Ingrid Schmoliner and I were commissioned by the festival Wien Modern to create a work to be performed in Kasematten—a vast underground medieval munitions chamber in the centre of Vienna. In November that year, we premiered *Towering Silence*—a one-hour performance collaboratively composed and performed by Ingrid on voice and electronics, and me on FAAB and additional signal processing. The performance was preceded by a 40-minute sound installation created by me, using processed field recordings, in addition to samples of Ingrid’s voice and prepared piano playing¹¹. Both performance and installation were distributed across 12 speakers using a SuperCollider patch of my design.

Figure 4.23 *Towering Silence*, Kasematten, Vienna.
View of the entire concert space

¹¹ While not a part of the thesis portfolio, the installation is available at <https://on.soundcloud.com/pWB5y>.

During performance, Ingrid had the option of choosing between four different processing architectures providing processing of her voice, in addition to a sample bank (the contents of which were decided on by her). Two of these architectures provided full control over DSP variables through motion tracking and a manually operated MIDI interface. A third option utilised a control feedback architecture, similar to the ones discussed above, to provide autonomous processing. Lastly, a combination of motion tracking and control feedback provided some, but not complete, control over signal modulation and resynthesis. For much of the performance, Ingrid relied on the latter option, expressing that it provided a dynamic space in which to navigate the performance while still affording the exploration of emergent timbral behaviour (private conversation).

Figure 4.24 Premiere of *Towering Silence*. Photo: Markus Sepperer

In addition to the already discussed algorithms implemented on the FAAB, as with *Echoes*, the output of each string was processed in SuperCollider. An extended solo for the FAAB¹² featured an onset-activated quadraphonic granular time stretch, developed from the algorithms already employed in *Echoes*. Here, the modulation of granulation variables, in line with the application of immanent DSP architectures, were functions of audio features derived from the output of the system itself. As was the case in *attics*, but further developed here, as I stop playing, because the algorithm is responding to its own output, it is able to continue to update its processing parameters in response to its own state (03:32).

¹² <https://on.soundcloud.com/vdyw>.

4.12.3 Discussion of collaborations

Using the FAAB in collaborative works presents both new opportunities and challenges with regard to interaction, improvisation and composition. On the one hand, performing in a group context with a semi-autonomous instrument requires that the other performers accept that I have less control than with a traditional acoustic instrument, not to mention that I have much less experience with performing on the FAAB than I have on the double bass. Consequently, I may sometimes not be able to respond to the musical gesture of my collaborators with the same immediacy that I would on an acoustic instrument. As already mentioned, in solo performances, the volatility of the FAAB is often an instigator of musically exciting situations, while it requires a certain flexibility on the part of my collaborators to accommodate the presence of an additional machinic performer, especially in contexts comprising fixed musical material. On the other hand, the asymmetry inherent to my relationship with the FAAB also establishes a stronger continuum between solo and collaborative performances, since interaction is partly mediated through the FAAB in both cases.

Previous solo performances with the FAAB were largely determined by the current acoustic, haptic, and algorithmic affordances of the instrument, in improvisation as well as composition. In contrast, the creation of *Echoes* and *Towering Silence*, on the one hand, responded to the FAAB as a significant musical component, but, on the other, required that I adapt my performance practice to facilitate shared compositional and performative processes. The slowly evolving dynamics and textures of both works are testament to shared affinities between Julia, Ingrid, and me. However, they also respond to the practice, established through the solo works discussed above, in which subtle changes can be perceived to develop over extended time scales. During the collaborative composition process, I found myself exploring new spectral and dynamic territory, in order to develop a closer musical relationship with Ingrid and Julia. This afforded the development and refinement of techniques such as pizzicato-induced feedback swells, in addition to exploring how pizzicato harmonics and false harmonics¹³ respond to the increased sustain and signal processing of the instrument (see *Towering Silence*, time code [00:00 - 02:30](#)).

Due to space considerations, the discussion of a third important collaboration featuring the FAAB will regrettably need to be largely omitted, apart from a brief mention: The Trio *3BP* (*The Three-Body Problem*) with Paul Stapleton and John Bowers performed several online concerts between December 2020 and June 2021. Improvising together from

¹³ False harmonics are created by pinching the string with the right hand at an integer ratio (often octave, fifth, or third) above where it was stopped by the left (See also Dresser (2010)).

our respective homes in Belfast (Paul), Newcastle (John) and Berlin (myself), this group developed an infrastructure in which each routed the audio from the other two through their instrument, effectively turning the internet into a feedback comb filter, the resonant frequency of which equalled the reciprocal of the fluctuating delay time of the network. While performances with *3BP* are not part of the portfolio, I can guide the interested reader to <https://www.adampultz.com/3bp> and refer to Stapleton et al. (2022).

4.13 Conclusion

In this chapter, I have shown how situated and immanent signal processing architectures, when embedded in an electro-acoustic feedback instrument, can afford the emergence of asymmetrical relationship between machine and the performer, establishing improvisation as a relational property. How, not only this asymmetry, but also the timbral and dynamical variation emerging through the signal processing, find their application in creative processes has been exemplified through three solo performances, and two collaborative works, each of which have undergone a written analysis.

As such, the question formulated at the outset in chapter 1, which asked, in which ways the timbral and resistant properties of an acoustic instrument practice may be extended into an electro-acoustic space, have found tentative answers. Yet, unsurprisingly, the horizon of inquiry has expanded with each new discovery, providing a host of new questions, some of which will be discussed in the conclusion.

This study, being concerned with instruments, code, algorithms, wood, ferromagnetic strings, cybernetic notions of feedback, interactional asymmetry, and more, is diffracted through a personal creative practice. Whether one ascribes to social constructivism, dynamical systems theory, non-dual notions of identity in contemplative traditions, or actor-network theory, this diffraction occurs through that agential cut called a *Self*. As such, it is clear that the present work has become, and always was, a study of an emergent self-identification as a maker, performer and thinker, as much as anything else. I have cautiously celebrated the various ways in which salient timbral and resistant properties found in my acoustic practice are transduced through work with the FAAB. However, there are other and more far-reaching consequences of the diversification of the asymmetrical relationships that concern, not only how I begin to approach performance, but how I understand human-machine relationships. These I will discuss in the next chapter.

Chapter 5

When things slip

It is September 18th, 2020, and I am playing my first live concert in seven months, the longest I have gone without performing in front of people in more than 20 years. Apart from a demo presentation in Athens a year earlier, this concert also happens to be the live solo debut of the FAAB. The venue is KM28 in Berlin—a well-known place for experimental and new music. The 20-people audience, though small, numbers at least eight brilliant musicians, including Laurel Pardue, who is closely affiliated with the development of the Bela microprocessor, and Sukandar Kartadinata—the instrument builder mentioned in section 2.5.

Performing a 30-minute solo set on the FAAB, then—as well as now—is a challenge, and I have spent the past month preparing a set, that although featuring much improvisation, is divided into three sections of approximately ten minutes each (the last section being a rework of *We're running out of Sand*). Due to COVID-19, the original FAAB became stranded in Belfast in March 2020, and I have had to build a new instrument from a bass purchased in Berlin in June of that year. With a few exceptions, I have only played this instrument in my living room and as such, do not have a good idea of how it performs in various acoustic environments. Additionally, while the instrument is in an acceptable structural state, it is far from achieving the robust roadworthiness that characterises instruments in the wild. Taking them on busses, trains, and planes, having them accidentally shoved by strangers, brutalised by airport luggage crew, and dragging them over cobblestones late at night in sub-zero temperatures or heatwaves, teaches you a lot about the structural bottlenecks of your tools, something which is difficult to achieve in the controlled settings of a domestic space.

I have arrived at the venue early and have had a good sound check, cherishing the lively acoustics of the larger room and the possibility of pushing the gain more than I dare in my flat (incidentally, the next day, I am approached by my neighbour politely asking me if we can sort out a schedule for my practising, as she is studying statistics in the room sharing a wall with my practice room). Although against my ethos of avoiding programming in the

week before a live performance, I have changed a minor detail in the code on the morning of the performance, which has not caused any noticeable issues.

After Bex Burch has played a solo set, I set up during the intermission and test if everything is running. When the audience has settled in their seats, I begin the performance with a composition where the careful manual management of amplitude causes two or more strings to self-oscillate at the same time, producing beat frequencies, the speed of which I can control by the subtle calibration of left-hand position. While it is difficult to perceive the resulting miniscule change of frequency on the string being manipulated, the frequency of the beating—that is, the difference between the frequencies of the two sounding strings—is noticeably altered. Due to the absence of strong harmonics on strings set in motion through self-oscillation, the resulting spectrum is bordering on the sinusoidal, with clearly audible beat frequencies and difference tones. However, unexpectedly punctuating the serene and minimal bliss of the feedback performance is a persistent digital glitch. While I have experienced similar glitches when lowering the buffer size beyond the computational headroom of the Bela's processor, I am surprised to experience it at this stage of software development, especially as it wasn't present during sound check and should not have been caused by my minor programming change earlier. While the miniscule change in code may in fact have been the proverbial nail that lost the war, when I resume playing the instrument a week after the concert, the glitches no longer appear, only deepening the mystery of their origin.

A compilation of every glitch taking place during the first ten minutes of the concert is available from <https://vimeo.com/747395676/5fce29d8ea>. The entire concert is available online here: <https://vimeo.com/747391355/7df9c9d8ba>.

5.1 When things break

In my acoustic performance practice, I am no stranger to things breaking. Due to the unusually high action of my acoustic double bass, discussed in chapter 1, the stiff steel strings occasionally break due to pizzicato playing and the application of preparations, both of which stress the strings at the point where they meet the bridge. In 2016, during a concert in which I performed with the legendary improviser Evan Parker for the first time, the two bottom strings of my instrument collapsed during the first ten minutes. Prior to that, around 2011, I completed a concert with a New Orleans-style jazz band on a borrowed bass, soloing on the encore, *Down by the Riverside*, with one string left.

I perceive such events as part of the resistance of the acoustic instrument, and have developed tactics for dealing with string collapse, including turning string replacement into a carefully choreographed part of the performance. Yet, the digital glitches imposing themselves on the live concert world premiere of the FAAB present a challenge I (at that point) am unable to meet. Hoping that they will go away, I at first try ignoring them. However, unbeknownst to myself, they cause me to assume a facial expression of annoyance roughly synchronised to the frequency with which they occur. After about 20 minutes I interrupt the concert to reboot the system and, while waiting for it to restart, make a joke (edited out in the concert video) referring to the shutdown of Hal 9000—the supposedly malfunctioning AI in Arthur C. Clarke’s novel *2001: A Space Odyssey*, adapted to screen by Stanley Kubrick¹.

Speaking to people in the audience after the concert, I realise that several audience members either have not noticed the glitches or simply thought they were part of the composition, at least until my body language suggested otherwise. As such, my inability to, firstly, produce a musical response to the glitches, and secondly, to deal with the situation in a way that does not compromise the experience of the audience, constitutes a failure to meet the challenge of performing with a new technology. It suggests a performative immaturity but also points to the fact that instrumental resistance comes in many shapes and sizes, some of which are easier to deal with, and more welcome, than others. With the acoustic double bass, a string breakage reconfigures physical affordances but does not, as such, cause a change in the instrument’s sonic output. The algorithms discussed in the past two chapters do significantly change the output of the instrument, but are designed to respond to perturbations at the input stage, while also observing, and adapting to, their own behaviour. Consequently, the autonomy and resistance engendered by the implementation of these algorithms are negotiable, even when not controllable. In contrast, the digital glitches, while surely being a function of *something*, compromise negotiation by not responding dynamically to mine, nor their own, behaviour. They simply seem to start when an audio signal is present in the system and cease when the signal stops. They represent, in the words of Legacy Russel (2020), “‘the failure to perform”, an outright refusal, a “nope” in its own right, expertly executed by the machine’ (p. 29). Rather than dynamically changing in response to their environment, the glitches persistently and predictably occur with little noticeable difference in timbre, their density increasing as the concert progresses. This, however, does not mean that there is no way of integrating the glitches into the performance, or at least attempt negotiation. In retrospect, I could have used each glitch as a trigger for changing acoustic variables, such as pitch or timbre, or for introducing short bow actuations or accents. Alternatively, I could have changed the sonic

¹ As it turns out, Hal’s malfunctioning is a response to a conflict between the objectives given to the machine, and as such, algorithmically sound.

texture of the performance to become noisier, approaching the timbral identity of the glitch itself, and thus spectrally integrating it with the output of the FAAB². Instead of doing any of these things, I persist with a plan that becomes marred by digital error.

5.2 Resistance and asymmetry

In previous chapters, I have discussed how feedback, in combination with adaptive signal processing, can produce a form of interactional asymmetry that affords exploration and improvisation. Although previously referring to the FAAB as embodying a sense of resistance similar to my experience with acoustic bass performance, I have come to prefer the term *interactional asymmetry* discussed in section 2.8.1. In my view, interactional asymmetry suggests a process of interaction between heterogeneous agents without ascribing a possible negative property, such as resistance, to either. The term resistance seems to suggest that something is actively resisting what is, in this case, human intention. In addition to situating the performative event in a nexus of humanist understanding, resistance problematically ascribes agency to an individual object (for a discussion of agency, see Melbye (2022, p. 25)). The place of the human as both performer and observer is naturally indisputable in the current context. Yet, contextualising the event within an anthropocentric framework, through the use of terms such as resistance, poses the risk of confining materials and algorithms to a negative space that is evaluated through its human use-value, even if this value is conferred through relationships that ultimately compromise human intent³.

This does not mean that the perceived resistance of my acoustic double bass is identical to the algorithmically produced asymmetry of the FAAB, although there are similarities. In both cases, the materiality of the instrument plays a significant part in creating a precarious environment ripe for interaction. On the acoustic double bass, the nonlinear *acoustic* feedback, the tautness of the strings, and their pull on the instrument body, obfuscate the straightforward execution of musical ideas. Similarly, the physical response of the FAAB's strings and body to both audio feedback and signal processing is nonlinear, topologically diverse, and unpredictable. Yet, where the acoustic bass is dependent on continuous manual excitation as the precondition for the establishment of asymmetrical relationships, it is the electrically induced amplification that sustains the instrumental autonomy of the FAAB. Hence, in the immediate temporal domain of—and the agential cuts enacted through—performance, the establishment of interactional asymmetry is not necessarily dependent on the performer.

² While the middle of the performance features noisier textures, this was a predetermined part of the structure, rather than a response to the glitch: <https://vimeo.com/747391355/7df9c9d8ba?ts=844000>.

³ Admittedly, in other contexts, such as in fighting oppression and ecological and societal exploitation, to name a few global injustices to be countered, resistance as a human capacity cannot be underappreciated.

Rather, at the time of writing, ancient sunlight stored in depletable fossil fuels and nuclear energy will be the most likely sources of autonomy in Germany⁴.

We are now in a position to expand on the discussion in section 2.6.1 of Thor Magnusson's (2019) observation, that the electronic and digital counterparts of acoustic instruments 'are imbued with an increased level of epistemic dependencies' (p. 57). As the epistemic dependencies increase, so the way in which instruments may enter into asymmetrical relations with performers also change according to *material* dependencies, for example in the shape of access to electricity for amplification and processing. Where string breakage on the acoustic bass is tied to my performative agency, the digital glitches of the FAAB rely on electronic amplification for their realisation. This difference does not excuse my inability to respond to the glitches. Nor is the example meant to suggest that, by introducing amplification, the performance ecology is fundamentally altered⁵. Instead, it shows that things go wrong in different ways depending on their material constitution. As such, an attitude to performance that may benefit from, but cannot primarily be grounded in, technical virtuosity, is required. The traditional notion of virtuosity in musical performance is tied to the execution of technically demanding musical material, whether that be the execution of a Rachmaninoff piano concerto or improvising a jazz solo on John Coltrane's Giant Steps. In contrast, when negotiating interactional asymmetry in performing with the FAAB, the musical objective is a moving target co-constituted by the real-time configuration of semi-autonomous algorithms entangled with the materiality of feedback. Consequently, the stakes are different. In multiple solo performances following my fateful debut, I did not experience any severe technical difficulties. In the later performances, the unexpected happened within the confines of the algorithmic-material design space, which, although affording complex and asymmetrical behaviours, had their origins in my own algorithmic design. The skills needed to adapt and respond to these behaviours are necessarily improvisational. They require an openness to the situation, and the willingness to revisit, or abandon, preconceived plans in the face of a dynamically evolving musical situation.

⁴ I am writing this in the autumn of 2022, with much of Europe trying to wean itself of its energy-dependency on Russia. In light of this, it is not difficult to see the irony in the discrepancy between the carbon-fuelled autonomy granted to the FAAB and the relationship between fossil fuels, colonialism, and dictatorships studied by Mitchell (2011).

⁵ Although, with Luciana Parisi's (2013) discussion of the incomputability sitting at the core of algorithmic architectures, a shift in ontology due to the powered digital processing of the FAAB may in fact be the case.

5.3 Mastery

Elsewhere, I have suggested the term *diachronic mastery* to describe the development of expertise in navigating precarious sensorimotor schemes in improvising with the FAAB (Melbye 2021a, p. 25). However, a critical reading of the notion of mastery—even one that acknowledges the dynamic and precarious nature of human-instrument relations—suggests that the concept of mastery itself may be an impediment to fully exploring and realising the potential of asymmetry in these relations. Mastery suggests a binary in which someone (presumably a human) accomplishes something through the exercise of control or authority over something else⁶. Importantly, opposed to the master in this binary, we find the slave. As such, it is difficult to imagine musical mastery in the Global North⁷ being disengaged from a colonial, capitalist, patriarchal, and heteronormative past and present, obliging us to enquire which societal and cultural norms may be perpetuated through practices of instrumental mastery and virtuosity. In her book *Unthinking Mastery: Dehumanism and Decolonial Entanglements*, Julietta Singh (2017) discusses the acquisition of English as a second language. Here, she questions the very notion of skill, maintaining that it is intrinsically linked to the ‘relations of power that make it possible’:

The demonstration of our skill and power, our “mastery” of texts and languages, should not be thought outside its referential connection to the “dominion,” “superiority,” and “control” that both the term and the practice also entail. (p. 92)

I want to avoid conflating music-making and language. Instead, I will conjure up Simondon’s call for ‘identities of rapports rather than rapports of identity’ discussed in section 2.4.1. In doing so, I acknowledge that, similar to language, the practice and tools of music are deeply entangled with socio-economic relations; from the power structures of the nation-state mirrored in the symphony orchestra, to the herdsman playing his flute (Small 1998, p. 201). If the material is social, as is suggested in material culture studies in anthropology (Bredenbröker forthcoming; Carroll et al. 2017b, p. 5), then instrumental mastery will always diffract the social life of its subject. Additionally, by pertaining to, not just an idea of pure matter, but a node in a social nexus, instrumental command becomes an ethical question.

This is not to say that we shouldn’t get good at playing instruments or that we cannot develop as performers. Rather, I argue that practising and performing with an instrument such as the FAAB, while depending to some extent on the acquisition and honing of technical

⁶ According to the Merriam-Webster online dictionary (n.d.), mastery first appears in English in the 13th century in the meaning of the authority of a master.

⁷ I am not equipped to discuss the notion of mastery in cultures other than my own, and will here concern myself exclusively with the socio-cultural sphere of the Global North.

skills, requires a practising for failure. As previously discussed, playing the FAAB requires an improvisatory mindset to accommodate to the interactional asymmetry emerging in the relationship between performer and instrument. This is not all, however: in the worst case (or best, depending on the point of view) an instrument can cause a disruption to the performative flow to the extent that I, the performer, fail to make musical sense of the situation. Yet, even in the absence of technical glitches, the semi-autonomy of the instrument disrupts by compromising human intent, ultimately introducing the risk of failure.

5.4 Failure

Failing is inscribed into the very relationship I have developed with the FAAB. The nonlinear transduction of feedback through heterogeneous materials, in addition to semi-autonomous signal processing, establishes an asymmetry that compromises my intentions, conscious as well as pre-reflective. When the Sync algorithm causes a surge of high-amplitude feedback to rip through the instrument, or alternatively, suddenly attenuates the gain of all four strings, I am left to negotiate these sudden and unexpected amplitude extremes. Similarly, the minor adjustment of a fatigued left-hand finger may cause the comb filter to explode in a shimmering rainbow of loud upper harmonics or, alternatively, a gut-shaking sub-harmonic rumble. On the temporal plane, the waveset time stretch occasionally and excruciatingly sustains dubious pitch choices far beyond their aesthetical lifetime, while unexplainably censoring well-crafted musical gestures.

Classical notions of virtuosity and mastery often confine failure to a negative space to be avoided. In contrast, I want to discuss how my continuous failure to exercise the kind of instrumental control that was a cornerstone of my formal musical training, may be understood as a process in which new creative horizons become established.

In discussing the Bush-era phenomenon in which a Google search for "failure" returned the "Biography of George W. Bush", Jack Halberstam (2011) argues that:

failure is a lofty word for Bush, since it implies that he had a plan and then failed to execute it. (...). Failure (...) connotes a certain dignity in the pursuit of greatness, and so while miserable might be a good word for the Bush-Cheney era, they were actually horribly successful in terms of dominant understandings of success. (p. 94)

Failure, Halberstam argues, is an art in itself, posited against normative narratives of success driving capitalist society and aesthetics. It is a rejection, but also an invitation to

remain in states of apparent discomfort, in those liminal spaces where things don't fall into place: 'alternatives dwell in the murky waters of a counterintuitive, often impossibly dark and negative realm of critique and refusal.' (Halberstam 2011, p. 2). Yet, this negativity contains a seed of something else, a possibility of becoming: 'Under certain circumstances failing, losing, forgetting, unmaking, undoing, unbecoming, not knowing may in fact offer more creative, more cooperative, more surprising ways of being in the world.' (ibid.).

In Halberstam's writing, there's a profound discrepancy between the celebration of, on the one hand, low theory and negativity as conditions that should not be resolved into a state of normative success, and, on the other, the notion that failure possesses a creative potential and offers alternative ways of being. Carroll et al. (2017a) takes issue with this celebration of failure, asking that 'If you want to fail, is it failure if achieved?' (p. 9). To my eyes, rather than presenting a conundrum or exposing a logical fault in Halberstam's argument, the question addresses two aspects of failure—one intentional and one temporal—both of which warrant a closer look. No doubt failure can be intentional, and Halberstam's allusion to more creative, more cooperative, more surprising ways of being in the world suggests that there's an incentive for practising failure. Yet, arguably, failure is more often associated with unintentional misfires, the outcomes of which are anything but expected. By understanding failure as a queer art, Halberstam situates failure on the background of a queerness that is not able to choose the societal norms in and against which it is situated. Yet, it can still choose the conditions for its refusal and critique of those very norms. Rather than suggesting an intention to fail, Halberstam's analysis discusses the art of responding to the apparent failure to fit in, while allowing for the possibility of authoring the conditions for this response. This, then, could pave the way for choosing, or, in the words of Carroll et al., wanting to fail, thereby creating the conditions for one's own failure. Which brings us from the intentional to the temporal aspect of failure: I will argue, that instead of failure being something that can be achieved, it is a process in which an asymmetry is sustained, rather than resolved. Rather than the end-state suggested by failure-achieved-once-and-for-all, the infinite form taken by the verbs in Halberstam's listing of 'failing, losing, forgetting, unmaking, undoing, unbecoming, not knowing' suggests that failure is an active process. Rather than simply suffered by the subject, as observed by Muñoz (2019), it is also associated with a 'kernel of potentiality' (p. 173) and can be practised with 'a certain mode of virtuosity' (ibid.) (see also Whale (2022) for a discussion of queer failure in the context of feedback musicking). Drawing upon Merleau Ponty's analysis of what happens when things 'become distant, oblique, and "slip away"' (Ahmed 2006, p. 171), Sara Ahmed discusses the notion of a queer orientation, specifically 'how we are orientated toward queer moments when objects slip' (ibid.). The temporal horizon of failing in Halberstam's writing is here echoed in a phenomenology that

‘might involve an orientation toward what slips, which allows what slips to pass through, in the unknowable length of its duration’ (Ahmed 2006, p. 172). Even more clearly aligned with the infinite verbal form of Halberstam’s failing, in discussing how queer does not exclusively refer to sexual orientation, Ahmed notes that ‘Queer would become a matter of how one approaches the object that slips away—as a way of inhabiting the world at the point in which things fleet’ (ibid.).

5.5 The Disorientation Device

The fleeting things, the objects that slip away—if we allow events, sounds and haptics to be objects—constitute the reality of performing with an instrument that disrupts. In Ahmed’s terminology, when the lines of socially constructed norms of accomplishment and performative success bend, and our orientations become compromised, rather than a queer phenomenology overcoming such “disalignment” of the horizontal and vertical axes’ (ibid., p. 172), it becomes a ‘disorientation device (. . .), allowing the oblique to open up another angle on the world’ (ibid., p. 172). In performing with instruments such as the FAAB, the nurture of skill, then, may consist in developing abilities to sustain and remain in these modes of disalignment, in order to open up new angles. The instrument, or perhaps more precisely, the relationship between performer and instrument, is then allowed to become a disorientation device, the disalignment and asymmetry of which come to inhabit the performance ecology as a fundamental condition, rather than as something to be overcome. The improvisational mindset, rather than serving to disentangle situations of asymmetry and disorientation, must be augmented by an attitude that can let us remain in the domain of failure and misfires, keeping the door open to new angles and possibilities. In this context, technical and performative mastery resonate weakly with the development of a metastable ecology rich in heterogeneous futures. Returning to Julietta Singh (2017):

We must abandon mastery in order to give ourselves up to wider and less hostile horizons. It should be clear that I am not insisting that we all avoid a skilled relationship to our intellectual fields. Rather, I am advancing a practice of vulnerable engagement, a practice of opening ourselves up to our dependence on other discourses, peoples, beings, languages (that we know and do not yet know), and things that give rise to the ways that we think and the claims that we make. (p. 91)

Applying such unmastery and vulnerable engagement to instrumental performance is no easy task. Trained on an instrument with which I have proceeded to build a 25-year

career, I know first-hand that some horizons and angles only open up once I have put in the technical and intellectual work required for developing a skilled relationship to that instrument. As Ahmed (2006, p. 55) notes, our world is shaped by what is within reach and sometimes technical skills need to be meticulously refined in order to make your arms longer (figuratively speaking). Yet, these horizons can also become hostile and remain out of reach through the very fear of failing, no matter how long one's arms may be. The paradox of my real failure to embrace the digital glitches in my FAAB debut performance was perhaps due to my fear of imagined failure in abandoning a given course, the existence of which was similarly a product of my imagination. By disregarding the new horizon established through the disruption of the glitch, a discrepancy between real and imagined horizons was established, the grinding clash of which—to several audience members—occluded the actual sonic event of the glitch itself.

I have described how the algorithms developed for the FAAB afford interaction and improvisation. Although designed by me, they illustrate a pursuit of instrumental autonomy. Through their establishments of interactional asymmetry, the instrument slips, fleets, and retreats from my control. In contrast to the glitch discussed above which was most likely a design flaw, the fact that these slips will happen is a function of an intentional algorithmic architecture, although I cannot predict the exact detail of their nature. In other words, I choose the condition for my own failure. This failure is sustained through the asymmetrical relationship between performer and an instrument, the latter exhibiting nonlinear tendencies engendered by its physio-mechanical constitution and algorithmic design. Where traditional notions of skill-building and mastery can seem to attempt a reduction of asymmetry between intent and outcome, in continuing to develop my relationship with the FAAB, skill-building will need to nurture and sustain this asymmetry. Only then can I fully accommodate and explore the metastability that is the condition for this very relationship. Paradoxically, this may entail taking a closer look at our perceived superiority and instead align ourselves more closely with the ecology in which we are situated. While discussing the power structures already embedded in notions of mastery, Julietta Singh's (2017) decolonial and dehumanist project of unthinking mastery, by engaging in 'active, unmasterful forms of self-dispossession' (p. 126), additionally seeks to decentre the human subject by pleading for 'transspecies identification and cross-species solidarities and [the] queer collectivities' (ibid., p. 126). I argue that we can apply this transspecies identification to trans-human-machine relationships as well. Here, identification does not imply the conflation of human and machinic identities. Rather, it acknowledges that taking the step of engaging with improvising machines poses an implicit challenge to the notion that they should be fashioned in our image, or that interactional hierarchies need be hardwired into the structure of performance. I have

already discussed the possibility of non-human perception in machine listening in section 2.10.1, and discussed critiques of unidirectional notions of interaction in 2.3.3. However, by framing these in the context of my discussion of failure and unmastery, we can see how their implementation need not be evaluated through normative notions of performative success, but rather through their participation in the emergence of a disorientation device.

Here, it is critical to recognise that embracing failure and unmastery does not compromise the development of dynamic relationships and meaningful interaction. It simply acknowledges that the thwarting of intentions, interactional asymmetry, failure, meta-, and even in-stability are aspects of the precariousness that suffuses lived reality. In the case of human-machine improvisation, the challenge, then, is how to develop modes of interaction that take seriously the potential of failure. As discussed above, this has been, and is, a personal challenge in moving from an acoustic to an electro-acoustic performance practice. In order to develop a close relationship to the acoustic propagation of my acoustic bass, years ago I removed the pickup from the instrument. By taking the term acoustic literal, any amplification became a compromise. As I started developing the FAAB with Halldór Úlfarsson, this appreciation of acoustic projection carried over into an ill-defined concept of retaining some sense of acoustic "feel" in the FAAB's signal chain (Úlfarsson and Melbye 2020, p. 223). I still aspire to integrate personal ideals concerning acoustic double bass timbre with amplification and signal processing. However, I am becoming increasingly aware that those ideals are historically and socially constructed and do not always hold up to the messy entanglement and agential cuts of acoustic, electronic, and digital domains. Rather, the timbral and aesthetic horizons emerging from such materially heterogeneous ecologies can, and should, be explored, both with regard to how they at times seamlessly integrate, in addition to their often upfront timbral alterity. Here, I again turn to how the waveset synthesis described in section 4.8.4 produces bit-crushed, distorted, and choppy deconstructions of the audio signal, in addition to smooth acoustically sounding time stretch, or how the comb filter, through the low-pass filtered changes in delay time cause an acoustically alien Doppler shift to appear. Some of these digitally induced textures can sound awkward against the periodically stable string feedback of the FAAB, especially when they disrupt an otherwise homogenous timbre. The paradox of making a hybrid and post-digital instrument while heralding interactional asymmetry, and then being taken aback by its timbral weirdness, is not lost on me. However, I am increasingly coming to terms with not trying to resolve this conflict between acoustic sound and digital naughtiness. Rather, it is at these moments of rupture that the FAAB asserts its identity, putting the onus on me to engage on a level of mutual music-making that acknowledges and sustains, rather than resolves, the disalignments of the disorientation device. While improvisation is essential in this context, so is the long-term exploration of,

on the one hand, possibilities for interaction, and on the other, the algorithmic design space. In the case of interaction, Halberstam's infinite verbal form of failing can demonstrate how practising with the FAAB (and possibly, any other instrument) can become a process of exploring the sustained disequilibrium and metastability as a source for the discovery of new musical material. Yet, it can also offer a useful lesson in sustaining uncertainty in the face of precarious situations, teaching us about 'staying with the trouble' (Haraway 2016, p. 1) to apply Donna Haraway's terminology. Haraway's concern—ecological destruction—is of course far graver than the perils of augmented instrumental practices. Yet, I suggest that the cognitive-embodied demands that apply in both cases require radical acceptance coupled with a stubborn determinacy to navigate a precarious and unforeseen situation. Haraway (*ibid.*) writes:

staying with the trouble requires learning to be truly present, not as a vanishing point between awful or edenic pasts and apocalyptic or salvific futures, but as mortal critters entwined in myriad unfinished configurations of places, times, matters, meanings (p. 1).

Haraway's dismissal of a vanishing point and her celebration of unfinished configurations, in agreement with Halberstam, again suggest a dynamical approach to being and interaction. This applies to my second point of exploration—the algorithmic design space. I have already discussed how algorithms implemented on the FAAB are often intentionally underdetermined in the early stages of design, to allow for the emergence of unexpected behaviour. With the previous discussion of failure, unmastery, and trouble, we begin to see an argument for how the code base, throughout its lifetime, can remain an unfinished configuration as well. Through the development of a relationship to the FAAB, not only does the domain of interaction change. The discovery of new modes of interaction expands the algorithmic horizon by allowing for the imagining of new asymmetries. These asymmetries may emerge through the creation of new algorithms, but importantly also through the continuous development of old ones. This puts what I have referred to as "programming errors" in a different light. Since the instrument is a dynamically evolving entity—an unfinished configuration and socially constructed in its materiality, it becomes difficult talking about algorithmic optimization in precise terms beyond the level of CPU-usage. In fact, error can constitute the necessary perturbation that disturbs the complacency of well-written and well-meaning code. This does not mean that the level of detail applied to the previous discussion of algorithmic design is rendered superfluous. Rather, it suggests that the accountability and reproducibility gained by precise descriptions of algorithmic processes do not always extend to the qualitative evaluation of the performance ecology of which they are a part. In other words, algorithmic optimisation is not identical with musical achievements.

Having little to no formal training in mathematics and programming, my occasional failure at writing solid code combines with the underdetermination of algorithmic goals to create a dynamic relationship between performance and programming. Code is evaluated through the “feel” of the instrument in performance, yet the evaluation of the feel itself changes as the code develops. Playing techniques are discovered and developed from interacting with algorithmic processes, thereby creating new horizons within which code can be reconfigured. This algorithmic development then again triggers the need to develop technical and performative responses, constituting a (non-audio) feedback loop between development and performance. While it is impossible to precisely identify the locus of evaluation in this loop, Lucy Suchman’s (2006) use of the term ‘effective encounters’ (p. 245) particularly resonates with my experience of this ongoing process. In the words of Suchman, effective encounters constitute ‘those moments of moving complicity between persons and things achieved through particular, dynamic materialities and extended socialities’ (ibid.). The aesthetics used to evaluate such encounters are a product of the moving complicity established between myself and the FAAB. It is a trans-machine-human aesthetic, comprising the extended social value systems pertaining to the evaluation of acoustic sound production. Furthermore, it involves a semi-autonomous digital morphology of timbre, that, at times, moves beyond my own conceptual grasp, thereby pushing the horizon of possibilities even further.

The iterative mechanisms of design, performance, and aesthetics, described above, are feedback processes in their own right, continuously reshaping the domains in which they take place. They are reflected in the title of this thesis, again a reference to Lucy Suchman’s (ibid.) profound and brilliant work:

what was talked about itself extended what was talked about, providing a continually receding horizon of understanding to be accounted for. (p. 66)

Chapter 6

Conclusion: Approaching the Horizon

6.1 Résumé and contributions

In this thesis, I have described how the establishment of asymmetrical relations between performer and semi-autonomous instrument has fundamental consequences for the way in which we understand and approach performance and making. To an even greater extent than the nonlinear and complex interaction afforded by acoustic instruments, the semi-autonomous feedback instruments described in this thesis establish a space for interaction in which the agency of the performer, to some extent, becomes compromised. The making of such instruments, manifesting as an intimate exchange and feedback loop between design and performance, establishes a horizon, the continual receding of which modulates, not just performance and design, but the performer-maker themselves.

This study was initiated by the question of *how and to what extent, a technically and timbrally extended instrumental practice can be expanded beyond the acoustic domain and into an electro-acoustic space*. In chapter 2, I discussed how the complex timbre and instrumental behaviour that I associate with my own, as well as other's, instrumental practice, share similarities with certain digital and electroacoustic practices, for example those of Tom Mudd (2017, 2019), Agostino DiScipio (2003, 2011, 2022), and Dario Sanfilippo (2019, 2022). In order to understand how such practices may relate to an extended instrumental practice, I proceeded to discuss the prefixes and adjectives (hyper-, meta-, hybrid, etc.) often employed to describe the perceived extended electro-mechanical-digital spaces occupied through the modification of already existing—or invention of new—instruments. Rather than being fundamentally distinct from the material, technological, and social factors constituting traditional instrument design and performance, I argued that these instruments and their relationships to music-making are subject to similar boundary-making practices and agential

cuts that have defined their acoustic predecessors. Identifying human-machine interaction and improvisation as being frequent drivers of new instrument designs, I discussed how the enactivist concept of *interactional asymmetry* provides a means for understanding improvisation as a relational and metastable process. This discussion produced a key concern of the thesis, namely the second research question of *how resistant and precarious performer-instrument relationships may express themselves in an extended electroacoustic instrumental practice*. Critiquing the use of randomness as the sole, or even most significant, source of asymmetry, and following Jonathan Impett (2001) and Tom Mudd (Mudd 2017), I identified *situatedness* and *immanence* as useful concepts for understanding how a system can monitor its environment, while establishing its own sense of a world. By virtue of its potential for nonlinearity and metastability, feedback emerged as a candidate for driving the behaviour of interactive systems, in turn generating the third and final research question that asks: *How may feedback be used to generate asymmetrical relationships affording interaction and improvisation?* Additionally being a cause of timbral complexity in many acoustic instruments, feedback, in the audio as well as in the control signal domain, came to serve as the guiding principle of this thesis.

Audio and control signal feedback were creatively explored in chapter 3, where I described the development of the works *What the Frog's Eye tells the Frog's Brain* and *attics for all, floors for none*. Similar to the other portfolio works discussed in this thesis (except for the four waveset demos), *Frogs* and *attics* have been performed in concert contexts (in person and online). They are artistic contributions in the fields of feedback musicianship and sonic HCI in particular, as well as good old music-making in general. In addition, *Frogs* and *attics* assisted me in discussing how the improvising machine, through situated and immanent signal processing architectures, can respond to its environment and create its own sense of a world. In particular with regard to *attics*, it was investigated how such immanence, in the shape of control signal feedback, can afford dynamic timbral complexity that does not necessarily correspond to the real-time decisions of a performer.

Chapter 4 constitutes the main part of this thesis through the discussion of the development of, and performances with, the FAAB. This is true for the artistic output, but additionally applies to the theoretical arguments of the thesis: compared to the two performances discussed in chapter 3, the FAAB more fully embodies the principles pertaining to the generation of complex timbral behaviour and the establishment of conditions for human-machine improvisation developed in the previous chapters. Each of the three signal processing algorithms discussed in chapter 4 exemplifies a distinct approach to establishing timbral and amplitudal complex behaviour. The algorithms were discussed within the context of performances in which improvisation played a key role, and as such, addressed asymmetrical relations

between machine and human. Additionally, I discussed two collaborative performances in which the FAAB was a part of an ecology comprising other human performers, fixed compositional structures, and additional multichannel signal processing.

The DSP architectures embedded on the FAAB are indebted to the conceptual and practical work of, amongst others, Nicolas Collins (2020a), Alice Eldridge (2008, 2022), Chris Kiefer (Kiefer 2017; Kiefer et al. 2020), Agostino Di Scipio (Di Scipio 2003, 2011, 2022), and Dario Sanfilippo (Sanfilippo 2019, 2022; Sanfilippo and Di Scipio 2017). I have demonstrated how the principles developed by these artists can be applied in the specific case of a self-resonating vibrotactile feedback double bass. Through this work, I have underlined the creative potential for exploring how signal processing and performance are intimately related to transduction in the heterogeneous material configurations of feedback instruments.

It is my hope that the three algorithms discussed in this chapter and submitted as part of the *pultzLib* C++-library may be used by, or serve as inspiration for, other musicians working with feedback and semi-autonomous systems.

Asymmetry saturates the initial narrative of a "failed" performance in chapter 5. Here, I argued that we need to embrace the uncertainty and possible failure that accompanies asymmetrical relationships. With the help of, amongst others, Jack Halberstam (2011) and Julietta Singh (2017), I critiqued the notion of mastery and how its undoing can be central to the 'human-machine reconfigurations' (Suchman 2006) studied throughout this thesis. Significantly, I argued that, by cultivating the asymmetries between the augmented instruments and ourselves, we may develop new and more profound ways of human-machine interaction. Obviously, machine may here be taken to mean any instrument or musical interface; digital, electronic or acoustic. As I will discuss below, I believe this applies to any interaction, irrespective of the ontological status of its participants.

To sum up, the contributions of this thesis are:

- An audiovisual portfolio of nine works with three different double bass feedback instruments
- A description and discussion of the design of the FAAB with a focus on performance practices
- A discussion and critique of interaction and improvisation with Digital Musical Instruments
- A discussion of feedback architectures and modes of transduction in feedback practices in general, and self-resonating vibrotactile string feedback instruments in particular

- The development of a C++ signal processing library, with applications to feedback instruments in particular
- A critique of the notion of instrumental and musical mastery and a discussion of failure and glitch in musical performance, with possible applications to the design of Digital Musical Instruments

6.2 Discussion and further work

It is not only in performance that a vibrotactile self-resonating instrument such as the FAAB embodies and instigates nonlinear and complex processes. While the Larsen effect constitutes a significant part of the present study, the research has moved beyond the domain of audio feedback. The countless hours spent modifying—and being modified by—a feedback-actuated augmented bass have significantly changed how I perceive performance, music, machines, listening, cognition, agency, ecologies, failure, mastery, virtuosity, identity, and much more. With a nod to the Lucy Suchman quote at the end of chapter 5, what has been talked about—in the shape of my dialogue with the instrument, my internal monologue, and my conversations with collaborators and those close to me—has certainly extended what was talked about. In effect, the "talking of the talking about" is continually extending the horizon within which I am able to understand and appreciate the work, the music, and the thinking emerging.

6.2.1 First-person experience, coupling, and sympoiesis

This thesis has seen little discussion of the actual first-person phenomenology of performance. This is not to say that a phenomenological account is not of interest to the study, but rather an acknowledgement that an in-depth discussion of first-person experience requires an epistemological scaffolding beyond the scope of this thesis. The emergence of a self is but one agential cut out of many, and for my purposes in the present text, I have often refrained from qualifying the portfolio choices with language pertaining to the emotional content of first-person experience. While chapter 1 described the background of the thesis as originating in my own personal experience and aesthetics, in the description of the works themselves I have focused on their emergence through making and doing, even if these processes are of course also tied to the experience of a subjective self. Ahmed (2006) discusses the neglect of the perceiver's orientation in much classical (white, cis male, heterosexual) phenomenology. For example, she notes that for Husserl to have been able to conduct a bracketing of the experience of his writing table, someone had to look after his children and attend to other

domestic work (p. 31). Rather than describing *the feeling of what happens* (Damasio 1999), in focussing on process, I want to acknowledge that the listener's orientation is different from mine and that their experience may elicit emotional and aesthetical responses distinct from my own. That being said, on occasions throughout the text (specifically in chapter 3 and 4), I use the term *musically pleasing* with little qualification. It is my hope that the reader on these occasions can accept my use of a simplistic terminology underwritten by a socially constructed value system that causes me to perceive certain sonic behaviours as simply "sounding good".

Obviously, I do not find my emotional response to the works in the portfolio, or the thesis itself, irrelevant. On the contrary, I am thrilled by all of it and I hope that the portfolio communicates artistic contributions beyond my own immediate experience of their performance. Performing *Frog*, *attics*, and with the FAAB triggers all sorts of feelings pertaining to the joy of exploration, musical negotiation and—in the case of the FAAB—being physically rattled by coupling myself to the instrument. Perhaps the closest I can come to qualify and communicate these experiences from a first-person perspective, and on an emotional level, is through the notion of *coupling*. In performing, the experience of being an active part of something that shakes, moves, responds, and makes sound, is an emotion difficult to reduce to any other description. Challenging my own precaution against strong autopoietic language in sonic HCI, it is the feeling of a certain sense of operational closure emerging between myself and a system to which I am structurally coupled. At this stage, the autopoietic language of self-making, having served me on one level of description, may give way to *making-with*, or *sympoiesis*—a term coined by M. Beth Dempster (1998) and adopted by, amongst others, Haraway (2016) and Polimeneas-Liontiris et al. (2018). As Haraway (2016) writes: 'autopoiesis and sympoiesis, foregrounding and backgrounding different aspects of systemic complexity, are in generative friction, or generative enfolding, rather than opposition' (p. 61). In section 5.5 I referred to trans-human-machine relationships. With these relationships playing out in performance, the experience of *making-with* something other than myself establishes a precarious self-individuation, or boundary-making, through the asymmetrical relationships established. Yet, at the same time, I experience how this boundary—the agential membrane of the self—liquifies to merge with the equally precarious boundaries of the instrument. The sympoietic and tactile full-body experience of melting into a large self-resonating instrument is a truly exhilarating experience which I, due to the constraints of the space allotted, am not able to do justice here. Annelie Nederberg's (2020) recent work is one of the few examples I know of an in-depth investigation of feedback and corporeality. Hopefully, as the field of feedback musicianship grows, research in this important area will proliferate.

6.2.2 Algorithmic horizons

The three algorithms discussed in chapter 4 have been developed and used extensively since the FAAB emerged as a playable instrument around mid-2020. In addition to the pure unprocessed string feedback of the instrument, they are central to most of the musical works presented in this thesis, all of which I find to satisfy the desire for a complex interactional and timbral space that I expressed in the introduction. While the documentation of the works to some extent renders them “finished”, the algorithms developed for their realisation have plenty of room for improvement. Except for the evolutionary features of the Sync algorithm, the algorithms do not exhibit long-term adaption or learning, and being able to modify their own behavioural space according to evaluations of performance would be a major improvement¹. Whether this is possible within the computational limitations imposed by the Bela board is an open question. Yet, such ambitions also suggest the attractive option of offloading some computation to a laptop in cases where very low latency and audio-rate synchronisation are not primary concerns. *Echoes of unspecified Origins* and *Towering Silence* both illustrate such computational offloading. This has been explored in the creation of a solo album for FAAB, field recordings, and laptop-implemented sound synthesis and DSP algorithms. While the work on this music only commenced after the completion of the thesis portfolio, the album will be released by Carrier Records and available on their Bandcamp page (www.carrierrecords.bandcamp.com) in the second half of 2023.

Pertaining specifically to embedded DSP and the machine learning processes discussed in Appendix B, recent work by Pelinski et al. (2023) describes a method for running neural networks on the Bela platform. During a post-doc at Intelligent Instruments Lab at Iceland University of the Arts in the fall of 2023, I will further explore the creative applications of machine learning and artificial intelligence to the FAAB, with a particular focus on training neural networks on feedback.

I have argued that interactional asymmetry is a precondition for human-machine improvisation and have explored how this asymmetry may emerge through the instrument’s situatedness in its environment, in addition to its embodiment of immanent control feedback loops. Situatedness and immanence are features inherent to acoustic instruments. Yet, with the digitally augmented and feedback-actuated behaviour of the FAAB, the asymmetry I experienced as a young acoustic double bass player has been transformed into an electro-acoustic semi-autonomy that appears familiar and alien at the same time. Entangled with the instrument’s situatedness—that is, its digital perception of environmental audio features—and immanence—in the shape of its perception of its internal state—the audio and control signal

¹ Such evaluation could conceivably be oriented by Eldridge’s (2022) discussion of ‘synchronic diversity in creative system design’ (p. 8) rather than the classic fitness function.

feedback of the FAAB additionally drives the modulation of its augmented timbral and dynamical space. Approaching audio feature extraction as a potential for other-than-human perception can create novel asymmetries affording other ways of improvising, in addition to lowering CPU cost.

Currently, the algorithm variables are governed by situated and immanent DSP mechanisms, yet the choice of balance between pure and processed feedback is at the discretion of the performer. Adaptive balancing is a very attractive prospect. In order to encourage long-term dynamic behaviour, it would be tied to the establishment of presumably sophisticated machinic capabilities for evaluating and learning from the ongoing performance.

6.3 Learnings, challenges and limits

It was only during the work on this thesis that I became fully aware of the extent to which my own early acoustic practice was informed by a fascination with resistance and asymmetry. This realisation significantly changed, not only the ways in which I have designed and performed with the FAAB, but also how I understand my artistic practice in general. As suggested by Lucy Suchman, letting plans become guided by situated actions rather than vice versa, and, with Halberstam and Singh, understanding failure and unmastery as potentiality, has been artistically as well as personally liberating. In addition to being applicable to performance, I believe that this potentiality has value for other creative practices where the technological and epistemic dependencies of the work transcend the formal abilities of the artist. In addition to performative humility, the work with the FAAB has taught me more about soldering, blown fuses, and low-level programming than I had ever imagined. In particular with regard to programming I want to suggest that my frequent failures and detours, guided as they were by creative necessity rather than mathematical proficiency, may also serve as the noise that affords new forms of self-organization for the metastable system. Metastability has seemed to propagate from the domain of musicking into other areas of life, to an extent unaccounted for in the design specifications of the FAAB. As stressed earlier, embracing failure and unmastery does not mean that one has to give up on the aspiration of making good work. However, the process of creation will have less to do with the romantic ideal of the work as existing before and beyond the sphere of its enactment, and more to do with emergence through making (see also Ingold (2013)). The critiques of notions of mastery and virtuosity raised in chapter 5 apply beyond the domains of sonic HCI and the arts in general. In developing new ways of interacting with machines, we will also need to address deep-seated notions and biases regarding our own place in, and interaction with, the world. As Alice Eldridge (2022) observes:

contemporary computer musicking can play a similarly critical role in supporting us through current existential, ecological, technological and social crises, by providing an embodied, generative space for exploring, recognising and refiguring our relationships with each other, the wider world and the technologies that we make. (p. 1)

While I have proceeded with caution in applying biological terminology to the design of semi-autonomous improvising machines, it is not inconceivable that musicians will one day perform with biological computing systems exhibiting self-individuation and normativity, in addition to interactional asymmetry (see section 2.8.1). If these systems were able to evolve their own wet and hardware, in Di Paolo et al.'s (2017) terminology, they would have satisfied the minimal conditions for agency. Rather than the obvious technological design challenges to this utopia, I would like to point to a much greater challenge to be addressed in my own work, as well as in computer musicking in general: the multiple technological and epistemic dependencies of the augmented nature of the FAAB are enabled by an ecologically unsustainable industry of perishable rare-earth metals, minerals, and fossil fuels (Masu et al. 2021). Relying on cheap labour, the destruction and pollution of habitats, and the installation and support of dictatorial and fascist regimes, the extraction of these resources amounts to nothing less than modern colonialism (Mitchell 2011). While it is still an open question what energy production and consumption will look like in a post-carbon society, it seems uncertain to what extent we can rely on a steady supply of microprocessors, amplifier chips, and related sophisticated technology in the future (Michaux 2021). Energy supply fluctuations are already integrated into instrument designs by, amongst others, the maker Lintang Raditya, whose *Acak Baur* (Chaos Box) is built to, not only accommodate, but creatively explore, an unstable electricity grid (Novak 2022). The *situatedness* of such a design is profound and points to yet another way of creatively engaging with failure, in this case the instability of an entire energy infrastructure. In addition to such resilience-development becoming essential to future creative practices, as with any technologically intensive practice, ecological awareness must be a major concern in future computer musicking (see Heikkilä (n.d) for a recent initiative around developing a “permacomputing” practice).

In a world of increasing resource scarcity, longevity is essential. The FAAB is four years old as I write these words. Its creative potential and the interactional challenges it affords suggests another lifetime of exploration and discovery, in solo as well as in collaborative contexts.

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Appendix A

Additional selected works and performances

2022

May 28th: *Seeds and Shards* Galerie Bernau, Berlin
Performance for FAAB and four resonating boxes

April 9th: *FAAB solo* Sonorities Festival, Belfast

April 9th: *Concert with Laurel Pardue and Kate Smith* Sonorities Festival, Belfast

March 11th: *FAAB solo* TV Control Center, Athens
Feedback-Musicianship Network Meeting

March 11th: *Concert with Alice Eldridge, Chris Kiefer, Thanos Polymeneas-Liontiris, and Daniel Overholt* TV Control Center, Athens

February 23rd: *FAAB solo* Frederikshavn Art Museum, Denmark

February 11th and 12th: *Ouroboros* Tanzhalle Wiesenburg, Berlin
Work for two musicians and four-channel audio feedback
Link: <https://vimeo.com/705038387>

2021

November 30th: *FAAB solo* U-Kirke, Copenhagen
Feedback-Musicianship Network Meeting

November 1st and 2nd: *Towering Silence* Kasematten, Vienna

- October 14th: *FAAB solo* NRW Forum, Düsseldorf
Pre-Conference “AI, Music and Improvisation”
- September 24th and 25th: *Echoses of Unspecified Origins* Studio Boerne, Berlin
- June 16th: *Improvised performance with 3BP* NIME, Shanghai (online)
- June 4th: *FAAB Solo* Online
Feedback Musicianship Network Meeting inauguration
- March 22nd: *Concert and artist talk* Exploratorium, Berlin
Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=l7bPXwVreA4&t=4090s>
- March 19th: *Concert with 3BP* New York Electroacoustic Improvisation Summit (online)
- March 14th: *Presentation* SensiLab, Monash University, Melbourne
- February 28th: *Concert with 3BP* Belfast Science Festival (online)
- February 26th - June 27th: *Diffractions* Modern Art Museum Albury (MOMA), Australia
Fixed-media. Link: <https://adampultz.bandcamp.com/album/diffractions>

2020

- December 12th: *Concert with 3BP* SARC, Queen’s University, Belfast (online)
- September 23rd: *FAAB solo* KM28, Berlin
- August 14th: *FAAB solo* ISSTA festival, Ireland (online)
- July 23rd: *FAAB solo* NIME, Birmingham (online)
- July 17th: *With the Brain Dead Ensemble* (online)
- July 1st: *Baigup Learning* (online)
Fixed-media. Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3iALuxlkXhg>
- February 12th: *Duo with Viola Yip* St. Finian’s Lutheran Church in Ireland, Dublin
- February 11th: *Duo with Viola Yip* The Green Room, Black Box, Belfast

2019

- December 5th: *Artist talk* The Academy of Music (RMC), Copenhagen

-
- October 22nd: *Artist talk* University of California San Diego
During tour with Ens Ekt (with Paul Stapleton and Simon Rose)
- August 31st - September 1st: *Performance Installation with Ens Ekt* Artist Homes, Berlin
Performances with FAAB, Frog, and 6-channel audio feedback
- June 28th: *FAAB solo* Em-Dash, Athens
- April 26th: *Duo with Emilio Gordoa* World in a Room, Berlin
- March 25th: *What the Frog's Eye tells the Frog's Brain* Labor Sonor, Berlin
- March 20th: *What the Frog's Eye tells the Frog's Brain* Brötz, Gothenburg
- March 14th: *What the Frog's Eye tells the Frog's Brain* Fylkingen, Stockholm
- February 23rd: *What the Frog's Eye tells the Frog's Brain* Koncertkirken, Copenhagen
- January 27th: *What the Frog's Eye tells the Frog's Brain* Church of All Nations,
Melbourne
- January 24th: *What the Frog's Eye tells the Frog's Brain* 107 Projects, Sydney
Durational performance for the NOW now Festival

Appendix B

Training neural networks on audio feedback

As mentioned in section 3.1.5, a neural network was trained to govern the grain size and density of the granular synthesis algorithm in *Frog*. Machine learning was adopted to explore alternatives to analytically proceeding through a scaling and mapping of audio descriptor data to processing parameters. Rebecca Fiebrink's (n.d) *Wekinator* software was chosen for its flexibility and ease of use, having been designed specifically for artists working with real-time audio and visual media. Neural networks were chosen for their stability and ease of implementation in processing continuous input and output data, such as the mapping of audio feature descriptors to grain parameters.

In a supervised training environment such as *Wekinator* one would usually extract a set of audio features i from an audio input x . The neural network n provides a mapping function for i to a signal processing algorithm d . Supervised learning s consists in comparing d to a desired goal state g , consequently training and adjusting the architecture of n according to the discrepancy between d and g , until a satisfactory outcome has been achieved.

When x is largely decoupled from y , it is possible to design for complex and nonlinear behaviour by experimenting with various goal states and adjusting the neural network accordingly, while continuously monitoring the result. However, in the case of *Frog*, $x[t] = f(d[t - 1])$ and consequently $x[t] = f(n[t - 1])$. Any change in $n[t]$ will therefore cause a change in $i[t + 1]$. This circular condition should come as no surprise, but the coupling of output to input compromises the training, as the trainer will not be able to manually adjust the desired output in response to d without disturbing the entire system, rendering a comparison between d and g difficult. The proposed solution is to decouple n from d by means of a gate z (implemented as a gate for OSC communication between *Wekinator* and *SuperCollider*)

Figure B.1 Training neural networks on feedback

during training. This allows for the adjustment of $n[t]$ without causing a change in $d[t]$ and, consequently, $x[t+1]$.

Figure B.2 Training neural networks on feedback with OSC gate

Admittedly, this also decouples y from s , in the sense that one must guess how d might respond to changes in n . During work with the *Frog*, I became increasingly confident in training Wekinator without immediate auditory reference of the actual output. To the best of my knowledge, apart from work by Alice Eldridge and Chris Kiefer ((2021) and in personal conversation), little research exists discussing machine learning on feedback. While being beyond the scope of this thesis, it appears to be a field of research worth exploring in greater detail.

Using machine learning eased the mapping process. More importantly, since it is not realistic (let alone desirable in the current context) to assign a desired output to every possible input coming from a continuously and subtly changing stream of audio, a significant part of the output of the neural network consists in interpolating between a few discrete supervised behaviours. As the input states chosen for training are not equidistant in the phase space of the system, and the same condition applies to the control values to which these inputs were

mapped to, the output of the system achieves a nonlinearity that would have been practically unfeasible to achieve by using simple linear or logarithmic mappings. As such, a degree of complexity was introduced into the system, that fuelled further explorations of the behaviour of the *Frog*.

While machine learning and the work with Wekinator offered promising results, I have ultimately chosen to abandon it in favour of other approaches to mapping. One reason is my increasing focus on the Bela board that does not support Wekinator, let alone affords the computational headroom required by machine learning ¹. More significantly, I have chosen to focus my attention on mapping strategies that rely on simple adaptive structures involving feedforward and feedback couplings between audio descriptors and processing parameters. These strategies are discussed in detail in chapter 4.

Wekinator did, however, resurface for an online performance with 3BP for the NIME conference in June 2021 (Melbye et al. 2021). Here, I used it in combination with the FluCoMa toolkit (n.d) to create two bots, each of which, on a very low-level, mimicked the behaviour of my collaborators John Bowers and Paul Stapleton (who each also created bots of the other two performers). Wekinator was used to train the recognition of a limited set of salient sonic gestures that I associate with Paul and John, respectively. The algorithm was consequently employed in performance, to filter and modulate the signals from my collaborators through each other, based on its recognition of their behaviour.

¹ Admittedly, this could be circumvented performing the training on a laptop.

Appendix C

Tuning on the FAAB

The tuning on the FAAB used for my solo work is based on a 23-limit *just intonation* tuning used on the acoustic double bass between 2017 and 2019. For an overview of the theory and practice of just intonation, I can refer to (Doty 2002). Here, it suffices to say that just intonation is based on integer ratio multiples of a fundamental frequency, in contrast to the traditional tempered tuning used in Western classical music since around the 18th century. The use of the term *limit* refers to the highest prime number in any given tuning. For example, a tuning based exclusively around justly tuned fifths (denoting the ratio $3/2$), is considered 3-limit, while thirds ($5/4$) would be 5-limit. Harry Partch's music was composed using an 11-limit scale with 43 pitches. Since the pitch space of just intonation is theoretically infinite, intervals are expressed as ratios.

In my own work, I have not used just intonation systematically, although its effect on stringed feedback instruments would be an interesting path to explore. However, as I have used it for generating the tuning used in *We're running out of Sand*, *Answer use replace*, *insert*, *append*, *attics for all*, *floors for none* and *Di s Co nT*, the chart below illustrates the ratios of the harmonics on all four strings.

The 1/1 fundamental of the tuning is A440. Ratios in circles are relative to this frequency, with the ratios in diamonds at the left-hand side of the chart describing the ratios relative to the open strings, that is, the physical division of the string. As can be seen, the fundamental, as a harmonic node, is only accessible on the 2nd string. The ratio calculations observe octave-equivalency. Only the ratios produced up until the 7th harmonic on each string is represented, as I rarely bow identifiable pitches above this ratio.

Figure C.1 Tuning chart of the FAAB

The above tuning was initially derived from a 23-limit pitch set of $16/23$, $23/16$, $2/3$, and $11/8$. The ratios, expressed in tempered tuning would be $D\# -28$ cent, $D\# +28$ cent, $D -2$ cent, and $D\# -49$ cent and as such, represent different flavours of D and $D\#$. The bass was tuned such that $11/8$ would correspond to the $3/2$ harmonic of the 1st string, $2/3$ to the $1/1$ of the 2nd string (which is identical to how this is string is tuned in standard tempered tuning, bar the 2 cent difference in the just tuning), $23/16$ to the $3/2$ of the 3rd string, and $16/23$ to the $1/1$ of the 4th string. While the pitch set is 23-limit, when actuating other string harmonics up until the 7th, we get much higher ratios, such as $161/192$.

Appendix D

Differences between early and later Sync algorithms

D.1 Oscillator waveform and range

Rather than the current sinusoidal oscillator used to modulate the gain of individual strings, in the early design stages of the Sync algorithm a triangular oscillator was used, the output of which was scaled according to a decibel distribution (which causes the waveform to approximate a sinusoidal waveform). In SuperCollider, if given a negative frequency, the *LFTri* Ugen (a non band-limited triangular oscillator), once it has reached its lower bound (in this case the 0 of the normalised range of 0 – 1), instead of inverting its direction from a decrease to an increase, will proceed into the negative range. To avoid too much clipping caused by extreme negative amplitude values, the range of *LFTri* was therefore limited to between -10 to +10. In addition, when used as an amplitude modulator, the effect of a negative value is that of a polarity shift of the signal. By the time of the performance of *Sand*, I was aware of these features and had embraced them as creative components of the system. While resulting in sometimes unpredictable and conceptually less rigorous behaviour (amplitude pumping and signal polarity shifts) the algorithm nonetheless resulted in dynamic and surprising behaviour that afforded interaction and improvisation.

The sinusoidal oscillator of the current C++ algorithm does not perform fundamentally different compared to the early algorithm, apart from the gain modulation feeling somewhat smoother. I have tried implementing a polarity shift similar to the one discussed above, but found no marked improvement or interesting change in the outcome.

D.2 Binary calculations in the evolutionary algorithm

When writing the original SuperCollider code, due to an incomplete understanding of binary numbers and floating-point representation in SuperCollider, an error was introduced into the calculations of the EA. This mainly affected the floating-point resolution, as the binary calculations were erroneously in 16-bit, rather than 32-bit, effectively reducing the size of each chromosome.

In the current C++ code, in addition to being calculated correctly, binary calculations are performed more efficiently, freeing up computational space. Binary numbers are currently represented as strings, but in a future improvement will be implemented as bits, taking up even less space and affording direct bit-shift operations and cheaper mutation calculations.